

RES4LIVE

ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING
TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

Inventory of market available RES technologies, machinery, energy efficiency solutions and practices

Deliverable 2.1

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ATB – LEIBNIZ INSTITUTE FOR AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING AND BIOECONOMY

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	Bioenergy	The Leibniz Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy
	Biogas	The Leibniz Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy
	Hydrogen	The Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas
	Geothermal energy	Terra Energy Partners
	Heat pump	PSYCTOTHERM
	Combined heat power	Ghent University
	Organic rankine cycle	Agricultural University of Athens
	Thermal storage system	Ghent University
	Electrical storage	University of Bologna
Energy Efficiency Solution	Farming practices	The Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas
	Barn monitoring and advanced control strategies	Plegma Labs
	Smart ventilation	Aarhus University
	Heating and cooling distribution systems	Ghent University
	Heat recovery	Ghent University
	Local heating and cooling	Aarhus University
	Energy efficient lighting	Aarhus University
	Building Envelope	University of Bologna
	Electric tractors	The Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Livestock sector is lagging in the transition forward zero-emission and zero-energy. Plenty of market-available renewable energy sources (RES) and energy efficiency solutions/products (EES) adopted in residential buildings could be implemented in livestock farm.

The overall objective of this Deliverable is to summarize the market-available RES technologies, machinery, energy efficiency solutions and practices. Their basic working principle, installation and maintenance, performance, cost and return, supplier and potential application in farm will be introduced individually. The implementation and combination of discussed technologies in livestock farm are fundamental for achieving fossil-free livestock farm.

This Deliverable provides general information of market-available RES technologies, machinery, energy efficiency solutions and practices to both livestock industry and policy makers.

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1 INTRODUCTION

It is estimated that the livestock supply chains, including feed production, processing and transport as well as energy used on and off farm and post-farm emissions, contributed 14.5% of the total anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions worldwide [1], and the proportion was up to 10% in the EU [2]. By improving manure management and adopting energy-saving technologies and low carbon energy, the emission could be reduced by approx. 30% [3]. Meanwhile, agriculture sector took up 3.3% of the final energy consumption in the EU in 2019 [4]. Hence, adopting renewable energy source and improving energy use efficiency of livestock building are vital for both animal welfare and sustainability of livestock sector.

The concepts of zero-emission building and zero-energy building have been widely addressed to reduce the emission and energy consumption of residential buildings by improving energy efficiency and adopting renewable energy sources. The European Commission proposed that all new buildings must be zero-emission from 2030 [5]. Up to date, plenty of renewable energy sources and energy efficiency technologies have been successfully applied in residential buildings. While the progress of transforming toward zero-emission and zero-energy is lagging in livestock sector. With the goal of achieving fossil-free livestock farming, this delivery aims to summary the market-available renewable energy sources and energy efficiency solutions, and further discuss their possible application in livestock farming.

2 RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES

The market-available **renewable energy sources** discussed in this delivery are as follows:

Photovoltaic (PV) system is made up of one or more solar panels that converts the solar radiation into electrical energy. PV system is now a mature technology used for mainstream electricity generation.

Solar thermal (ST) system transforms the solar energy into thermal energy. ST system is associated with passive heating and cooling technologies in buildings.

Photovoltaic thermal collector (PVT), combination of PV and ST system, converts solar radiation into usable thermal and electrical energy spontaneously.

Wind energy is transformed into usable electrical energy by wind turbine. Wind energy is one of the fastest-growing renewable energy technologies.

Bioenergy, also known as energy from biomass. Bioenergy can be used to generate electricity, heat or transport fuel, as well as solid, liquid, and gaseous energy carriers.

Biogas, production from organic waste. Power generation from biomass is currently the most popular and growing market worldwide. The application of biogas can transform the on-farm waste into valuable renewable energy and decrease the reliance on fossil-based energy.

Hydrogen can be produced from methane or by electrolysis of water and provides a carbon-free process of energy utilization. The farm equipment like trucks and tractors could be powered by hydrogen.

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Geothermal energy is the thermal energy in the Earth's crust which is estimated to be more than adequate to supply humanity's energy needs. The geothermal energy is typically used for heating and cooling of buildings.

Combined heat power (CHP), also known as Cogenerations, uses heat engine or power station to generate electricity and useful heat at the same time. CHP systems allow for a substantial potential of increasing the energy efficiency and reducing the environmental impact.

Heat pumps (HP) is used for extracting heat from a lower temperature zone or system and sending it to higher temperature space or system. It is an energy-efficient alternative to burners and works also for cooling.

Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) systems are used for power production from low to medium temperature heat sources. This technology allows for recovering low-grade heat that otherwise would be wasted.

Thermal storage system is a technology that stores thermal energy by heating or cooling a storage medium, so that the stored energy can be used at a later time, e.g., for heating or cooling applications or power generation.

Electrical storage system is a battery which is useful in a situation where it is impossible to generate electricity. The electrical storage system is essential for optimizing the sustainability of renewable energy sources.

3 ENERGY EFFICIENCY SOLUTIONS

The market-available *energy efficiency solutions* discussed in this delivery are as follows:

Farming practices not only affect animal welfare but also determine on-farm energy consumption. Good practices e.g., precision feeding, manure management and optimized milking process are essential for improving indoor environment and reducing energy consumption.

Barn monitoring and advanced control strategies employ market-available sensors to monitor environmental condition and energy consumption trend as baseline for developing smart control system to optimize indoor climate condition with minimum energy consumption.

Smart ventilation (namely hybrid ventilation) combines the advantages of mechanical and natural ventilation. The indoor climate condition is controlled, and emission is collected by mechanical ventilation system, while energy consumed by fans is reduced via natural ventilation.

Heating and cooling distribution systems are essential for guarantying the overall comfortable conditions of livestock farms. Optimising the heating and cooling distribution systems and combining with other renewable energy e.g., geothermal energy can largely reduce the on-farm energy consumption.

Heat recovery can reduce the heating or cooling loads of livestock farm by transferring and reusing the thermal energy from waste streams (air and liquid). Consequently, the energy efficiency of heating/cooling system is improved, and operational cost of livestock farm is reduced.

Local heating and cooling can precisely modify the local thermal environment of the individual animal for maintaining thermal comfort with minimum energy consumption. Meanwhile, local heating and

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cooling can be achieved by combining with heat recovery or using renewable energy e.g. geothermal energy.

Energy efficient lighting provides optimum lighting conditions for livestock welfare with lowest total life-cycle energy consumption and carbon footprint. Meanwhile, products as LED are free of mercury and have lower negative impact on the environment.

Building envelops are fundamental for thermal insulation, which have great impact on the heating and cooling demand of buildings. Advance building material and mechanical shading products/control are essential for reducing energy consumption.

Electric tractor is a hotspot in the electrification of farm machinery. The 100% battery-powered electric tractors can be charged by electricity powered by renewable energy e.g., wind energy, biogas, bioenergy, hydrogen, and geothermal energy. These diesel-free tractors also contribute to emission reduction.

4 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

Most of the summarized renewable energy sources and energy efficiency solutions are already mature and available in the market. Based on the farm type, farm location and farm energy demand, the combinations between renewable energy sources and energy efficiency solutions could be designed and implemented. The agricultural waste can also serve as renewable energy sources (bioenergy, biogas, and hydrogen) and reduce on-farm demand of fossil energy. As livestock farms are usually locate in remote and open area, solar energy, wind energy and geothermal energy could also be implemented in large scale which enlarge its energy self-sufficiency potential. The usage of high efficiency energy conversion machinery (combined heat power, organic Rankine cycle and heat pump) and thermal/electrical storage system generate an ideal fossil-free energy supply chain. Meanwhile, the application of energy efficiency solutions/products could further strengthen the sustainability of fossil-free livestock farming.

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Part I: Renewable energy sources

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Appendix 1: Photovoltaic systems

1. Technical description

1.1. Working principle

The Photovoltaic (PV) cell is the semiconductor device that converts the light into electrical energy. The voltage induced by the PV cell depends on the intensity of light incident on it. The name Photovoltaic is because of their voltage producing capability [6].

A typical photovoltaic cell consists of semiconductor material (usually silicon) having a P-N junction. As illustrated in Fig. A1. 1, Sunlight striking the cell raises the energy level of electrons and frees them from their atomic shells. The electric field at the P-N junction drives the electrons into the N region while positive charges are driven to the P region. A metal grid on the surface of the cell collects the electrons while a metal back-plate collects the positive charges [7].

Fig. A1. 1. P-N junction of a semiconductor.

Photovoltaic systems is made up of one or more solar panels, which in turn are made up of the previously named cells, combined with an inverter and other electrical and mechanical hardware. Each panel produces a relatively small amount of energy but can be linked together with other panels to produce higher amounts of energy as a solar array. The electricity produced from a solar panel (or array) is in the form of direct current (DC). Therefore, in order for the solar electricity to be useful it must first be converted from DC to AC using an inverter. This AC electricity from the inverter can then be used to power electronics locally, or be sent on to the electrical grid for use elsewhere [8].

Fig. A1. 2. Main components of a photovoltaic system.

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1.2. Classification of PV system

There are three typical classifications of solar PV system grid-tied, grid/hybrid and off-grid.

Grid-tied system is a basic solar installation that uses a standard grid-tied inverter and does not have any battery storage. This is perfect for customers who are already on the grid and want to add solar to their house. These systems can qualify for state and federal incentives which help to pay for the system. Grid-tied systems are simple to design and are very cost effective because they have relatively few components. The main objective of a grid-tied system is to lower your energy bill and benefit from solar incentives.

Grid-tied system with battery back-up is a grid tied system with battery back-up, otherwise known as a grid-hybrid system. This type of system is ideal for customers who are already on the grid who know that they want to have battery back-up. Good candidates for this type of system are customers who are prone to power outages in their area, or generally just want to be prepared for outages.

Off-grid system is great for customers who can't easily connect to the grid. This may be because of geographical location or high cost of bringing in the power supply. In most cases, it doesn't make much sense for a person connected to the grid to completely disconnect and do an off-grid system.

1.3. Components

Solar panel

A solar panel consists of many solar cells with semiconductor properties encapsulated within a material to protect it from the environment. These properties enable the cell to capture light, or more specifically, the photons from the sun and convert their energy into useful electricity through a process called the photovoltaic effect. On either side of the semiconductor is a layer of conducting material which "collects" the electricity produced. The illuminated side of the panel also contains an anti-reflection coating to minimize the losses due to reflection. The majority of solar panels produced worldwide are made from crystalline silicon, which has a theoretical efficiency limit of 33% for converting the Sun's energy into electricity. Many other semiconductor materials and solar cell technologies have been developed that operate at higher efficiencies, but these come with a higher cost to manufacture [9].

Inverter

An inverter is an electrical device which accepts electrical current in the form of direct current (DC) and converts it to alternating current (AC). For solar energy systems, this means the DC current from the solar array is fed through an inverter which converts it to AC. This conversion is necessary to operate most electric devices or interface with the electrical grid. Inverters are important for almost all solar energy systems and are typically the most expensive component after the solar panels themselves [9]. Most inverters have conversion efficiencies of 90% or higher and contain important safety features including ground fault circuit interruption and anti-islanding. These shut down the PV system when there is a loss of grid power [9].

Racking system

Racking refers to the mounting apparatus which fixes the solar array to the ground or rooftop. Typically constructed from steel or aluminium, these apparatuses mechanically fix the solar panels in place with

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a high level of precision. Racking systems should be designed to withstand extreme weather events such as hurricane or tornado level wind speeds and/or high accumulations of snow. Another important feature of racking systems is to electrically bond and ground the solar array to prevent electrocution. Rooftop racking systems typically come in two variations including flat roof systems and pitched roof systems. For flat rooftops it is common for the racking system to include weighted ballast to hold the array to the roof using gravity. On pitched rooftops, the racking system must be mechanically anchored to the roof structure. Ground mounted PV systems, can also use either ballast or mechanical anchors to fix the array to the ground. Some ground mounted racking systems also incorporate tracking systems which use motors and sensors to track the Sun through the sky, increasing the amount of energy generated at a higher equipment and maintenance cost [9].

Other Components

The remaining components of a typical solar PV system include combiners, disconnects, breakers, meters and wiring. A solar combiner, as the name suggests, combines two or more electrical cables into one larger one. Combiners typically include fuses for protection and are used on all medium to large and utility-scale solar arrays. Disconnects are electrical gates or switches which allow for manual disconnection of an electrical wire. Typically used on either side of an inverter, namely the "DC disconnect" and "AC disconnect" these devices provide electrical isolation when an inverter needs to be installed or replaced. Circuit breakers or breakers protect electrical systems from over current or surges. Designed to trigger automatically when the current reaches a predetermined amount, breakers can also be operated manually, acting as an additional disconnect. An Electric meter measures the amount of energy that passes through it and is commonly used by electric utility companies to measure and charge customers. For solar PV systems, a special bi-directional electric meter is used to measure both the incoming energy from the utility, and the outgoing energy from the solar PV system. Finally, the wiring or electrical cables transport the electrical energy from and between each component and must be properly sized to carry the current. Wiring exposed to sunlight must have protection against UV exposure, and wires carrying DC current sometimes require metal sheathing for added protection [9].

1.4. Types of panels

Monocrystalline: To make solar cells for monocrystalline solar panels, silicon is formed into bars and cut into wafers. These types of panels are called "monocrystalline" to indicate that the silicon used is single-crystal silicon. Because the cell is composed of a single crystal, the electrons that generate a flow of electricity have more room to move [10].

Polycrystalline: Polycrystalline solar panels are also made from silicon. However, instead of using a single crystal of silicon, manufacturers melt many fragments of silicon together to form the wafers for the panel. Polycrystalline solar panels are also referred to as "multi-crystalline," or many-crystal silicon. Because there are many crystals in each cell, there is less freedom for the electrons to move [10].

Thin Film: A thin-film solar cell is a second generation solar cell that is made by depositing one or more thin layers, or thin film (TF) of photovoltaic material on a substrate, such as glass, plastic or metal. Thin-film solar cells are commercially used in several technologies, including cadmium telluride (CdTe), copper indium gallium diselenide (CIGS), and amorphous thin-film silicon (a-Si, TF-Si).

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Fig. A1. 3. Photos of (a) monocrystalline solar panel, (b) Polycrystalline solar panel and (c) thin-film solar cell.

1.5. Electrical output characteristics

The electrical characteristics of a photovoltaic array are summarised in the relationship between the output current and voltage. The amount and intensity of solar insolation (solar irradiance) controls the amount of output current (I), and the operating temperature of the solar cells affects the output voltage (V) of the PV array [11]. As Fig. A1.4 shows, Solar cell I-V characteristic curves that summarise the relationship between the current and voltage are generally provided by the panels manufacturer and are given as:

Open-Circuit Voltage (VOC) is the maximum voltage that the array provides when the terminals are not connected to any load (an open circuit condition). This value is much higher than V_{mp} which relates to the operation of the PV array which is fixed by the load. This value depends upon the number of PV panels connected together in series [11].

Short-Circuit Current (ISC): The maximum current provided by the PV array when the output connectors are shorted together (a short circuit condition). This value is much higher than I_{mp} which relates to the normal operating circuit current [11].

Maximum Power Point (MPP) relates to the point where the power supplied by the array that is connected to the load (batteries, inverters) is at its maximum value, where $MPP = I_{mp} \cdot V_{mp}$. The maximum power point of a photovoltaic array is measured in Watts (W) or peak Watts (W_p) [11].

Fill Factor (FF) is the relationship between the maximum power that the array can actually provide under normal operating conditions and the product of the open-circuit voltage multiplied by the short-circuit current, ($VOC \times ISC$) This fill factor value gives an idea of the quality of the array and the closer the fill factor is to 1 (unity), the more power the array can provide. Typical values are between 0.7 and 0.8 [11].

Percent Efficiency (eff) is the efficiency of a photovoltaic array is the ratio between the maximum electrical power that the array can produce compared to the amount of solar irradiance hitting the array. The efficiency of a typical solar array is normally low at around 10-12%, depending on the type of cells (monocrystalline, polycrystalline, amorphous or thin film) being used [11].

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Fig. A1. 4. I-V characteristic curve of a panel.

Photovoltaic panels can be wired or connected together in either series or parallel combinations, or both to increase the voltage or current capacity of the solar array. If the array panels are connected together in a series combination, then the voltage increases and if connected together in parallel then the current increases. The electrical power in Watts, generated by these different photovoltaic combinations will still be the product of the voltage times the current, ($P=V \cdot I$). However the solar panels are connected together, the upper right hand corner will always be the maximum power point (MPP) of the array [11]. Some solar panels are rated at slightly higher or lower voltages than others of the same wattage value, and this affects the amount of current available and therefore the panels MPP. Other parameters also important are the open circuit voltage and short circuit current ratings from a safety point of view, especially the voltage rating. An array of six panels in series, while having a nominal 72 volt (6 x 12) rating, could potentially produce an open-circuit voltage of over 120 volts DC, which is more than enough to be dangerous [11].

1.6. Electrical Output based on sizes

The size of the PV panel depends on the quantity of cells that compose it, summarized in Table A1. 1.

Table A1. 1. Capacity of the panel depending on the size.

Number of cells	Capacity
36 solar cells	Approximately 150 W and are used for 12 V batteries
60 cells and 120 half cells	Between 320 W and 340 W for self-consumption. They are also often referred to as 24 V solar panels.
72 cells and 144 half cells	Between 385 W and 415 W, for self-consumption and also allow charging 24 V batteries.
Shingle Cells	A type of panel with very advanced technology where photovoltaic cells cut "in tiles" are joined so that they behave like a "super cell". The number of solar cells can vary
Half Cell	They are photovoltaic cells cut in two and serialized. It has the advantage of improving the performance in shadows but a great disadvantage is that the welds and metal contacts are duplicated, so they are more exposed to failures

The size of the panel ranges between 200 (height) x 100 (width) cm and 110 (height) x 100 (width) cm, leaving us an average size of 165 cm (height) x 100 cm (width).

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1.7. Mechanical constructions

Construction of the mechanical portion of a PV system design involves a review of drawings, assembly instructions, material selection, engineering documentation, and weather sealing. Drawings and engineering documentation are particularly important to local jurisdictions reviewing the system plans to prove that the structure does not pose a safety hazard. It's critical to provide detailed instructions for the installation of the different structural parts so that installers knowledgeable with the system can put the structure together correctly and efficiently. Some important considerations of the mechanical constructions are **Guidelines and Drawings, Mounting Design, Array Assembly Instructions and Hardware, Structural Assembly Instructions and Hardware** and **Weather Sealing**.

1.8. Installation and maintenance

1.8.1. Installation

A typical commercial PV cell with a surface area of 25 square inch produces about 2 W of power under peak sunlight conditions. If sunlight intensity is 40% of peak, the cell produces about 0.8 W. To become useful as an electrical energy source, PV cells must be connected in series and/or parallel circuit configurations to produce higher voltages and current. Wiring modules in series to produce “strings” increases voltage, wiring the strings together in parallel increases current. An array of 30 135 W rated modules can produce 4 kW [12].

Manufacturers combine PV cell circuits in sealed environmentally protective laminate to construct PV modules—the fundamental building blocks of PV generating systems. PV panels include several PV modules assembled and pre-wired to be field-installable. A PV array is a complete power-generating unit, which can include any number of PV modules and panels [12].

PV arrays can be placed on the roof of a facility—as with the store in Bakersfield— or on land adjacent to the facility. Typically, solar arrays require around 3 to 5 acres/MW. Roof and building-mounted arrays maximize the total sunlight-collection footprint available for a site. However, the potential for roof penetrations and roof loading as well as their consequences should be considered [12]. The conceptual basis for nearly every useful solar energy installation starts with the PV panels collecting sunlight. The PV array supplies dc voltage to an inverter, which converts the dc into 60 Hz ac. The ac from the inverter supplies energy to the facility or home [12].

Depending on the facility requirements, a system can also include any number of dc switching and protection devices, such as dc combiner boxes, circuit breakers, disconnect switches, and contactors. A “real-world” system also includes ac switching and protection devices such as ac panel boards and switchboards, disconnect switches, circuit breakers, low- and medium-voltage switchgear, and low- and medium-voltage transformers. Some installations may also have batteries, automatic transfer switching units, monitoring and metering equipment, and devices that allow electricity to be back-fed to the grid [12].

Functional and operational requirements, component configurations, and how the equipment connects to other power sources and electrical loads determine PV power system classifications. The two main classifications are grid-connected (or utility-interactive) systems and stand-alone systems. Grid-connected systems operate while interconnected with the utility grid. Besides the PV array itself, the main component in a grid-connected system is the inverter. The PV system, specifically the

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inverter, interfaces bi-directionally with the electric utility network, typically at an on-site distribution panel or service entrance [12].

1.8.2. Maintenance

Maintenance requirements for PV installations depend on the type of system design and equipment used. Some installations require very little attention, perhaps just annual inspections. Others—especially those with batteries—may require maintenance intervals of four to six months, or even component (usually battery) replacements over the system’s lifetime [12]. Typical maintenance items that PV installations may require include:

- Inspecting wiring connections and terminations for looseness and corrosion
- Inspecting wiring harnesses to ensure they are neatly bundled and protected
- Inspecting the PV array for cleanliness, absence of damage, and structural integrity
- Inspecting roof penetrations and weather sealing
- Maintaining batteries, which may include cleaning, adding electrolyte, charge equalization, and replacement if needed [12].

1.9. Selection of appropriate type model

There is not a one solution PV system for Solar PV arrays, in fact, can vary greatly in terms of general design, size, and application. That's why it's critical for customers to know exactly what they're looking for when choosing to buy a solar array. When selecting a solar PV system, the two most important factors to consider are the system's size and the type of solar cells it contains.

Right Sizing a Solar PV System: From an investment aspect, choosing the proper solar PV system is critical - too small a system and buyers' energy demands will go unfulfilled; too large a system and buyers will overspend on a system that provides too much electricity and may fail to generate a return on their investment. The first step for consumers is to determine how much electricity they require for their system to produce. Assuming a standard solar PV system with no energy storage, buyers should figure out how much electricity they use during the day so they can choose a system that meets their needs. Because solar PV systems only generate electricity during daylight hours, this is critical. The only exception is if a farmer has or wishes to invest in an energy storage system that allows them to use electricity generated by their solar PV system at any time of day or night. Consumers should be aware that daylight hours vary by geographical location and even by season, so they should be aware of local conditions.

Selecting the Right Solar Cell: Another major consideration is what type of solar cell you want within your PV system since different modules generate different levels of electricity per square foot than others. At a very basic level, monocrystalline silicon systems have traditionally been known for being the most efficient type of solar cell - generating the most electricity relative to size; however, they are also the most expensive. Polycrystalline silicon cells are less efficient than monocrystalline arrays, but they're also less costly. And they are a particularly good choice for climates that have more overcast days. Finally, thin film technologies are also a new option that are becoming increasingly popular - they're typically as efficient as polycrystalline models and are cost-competitive.

2. Performance

2.1. Factors affecting the performance

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2.1.1. Type of panel

Monocrystalline solar panels have the highest efficiency rates, typically in the 15-20% range, and tend to be more efficient in warm weather. Polycrystalline panels have lower efficiency rates typically in the 13-16 % range and tend to have lower heat tolerance.

2.1.2. Work temperature

Most solar radiation reaching a PV cell is converted not into electricity but into thermal energy which increase the cell temperature. Temperature increases in photovoltaic (PV) modules lead to immediate efficiency losses and can accelerate long-term degradation. Silicon PV modules operated at elevated temperatures exhibit lower efficiency in converting solar energy into electrical energy. A 1K increase in crystalline silicon cell temperature typically decreases absolute conversion efficiency by 0.08%, reducing power output by 0.45%. A 15K temperature rise thus reduces power output by about 7%.

2.1.3. Location

For the calculation of the energy production of a photovoltaic installation, it is essential to know the solar irradiation in the plane corresponding to the installation and the solar path in the place at the different times of the year. The situation of the sun at any time is determined by the height and azimuth of the sun [13]. The performance of photovoltaic panels is influenced by their orientation and tilt (inclination), which affects the amount of producible energy [13].

2.2. Efficiency

The ability of a solar panel to convert sunlight into useful electricity is measured by the efficiency of the panel. When the sun shines on a solar panel with a 20% efficiency rating, for example, 20% of the sun's energy is transformed to solar energy. If two solar panels with differing efficiency ratings are exposed to the same quantity of sunlight for the same period of time, the more efficient panel will produce more power than the less efficient panel. The production of electricity by solar cells determines the efficiency of solar panels, which is impacted by the composition of the cells, their electrical configuration, the surrounding components, and other factors.

2.3. Life cycle Emissions

Statistical analysis of different studies and estimates reveals a range of greenhouse gas emissions over the course of solar PV's lifecycle at the extremely low end of 1 g CO₂-eq/kWh and the high end of 218 g CO₂-eq/kWh. Accounting for the average values of emissions associated with each part of solar PV's lifecycle, the mean value reported is 49.9 g CO₂-eq/kWh, numbers providing estimates for operation and maintenance and decommissioning is low. At the end, cultivation and fabrication are responsible for about 71% of solar PV's emissions, followed by construction (19%), operation (13%), and decommissioning, which offset 3.3% of emissions [14].

2.4. Stability

The correct operation of a photovoltaic system depends on multiple factors throughout its life.

These vary from small occasional changes during the day, such as the interposition of clouds, to the season in which we are. That is why the functional stability of photovoltaic systems can become irregular. Fortunately, the implementation of inverters, meters, regulators and other types of

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monitoring has managed to give this chaotic source of energy a certain stability. This may not help to improve energy production during the months with less favorable values, but it ensures constant energy during day-to-day climatic changes, and a correct annual operation. For these reasons, it is very important to pay attention to the local climate where we intend to establish the installation and to establish a safe monitoring system.

2.5. Practical lifetime

Lifetime is difficult to quantify because most PV systems introduced are still in operation or were produced in the early stages of the technology's development. However, many researchers have studied the life expectancy of components in PV systems as below.

- **PV Modules:** 25-50 years for mature module technologies.
- **Inverters:** 15 years for small plants or residential PV systems; 30 years with 10%-part replacement every 10 years for large plants.
- **Structure:** 30 years for rooftop- and facade-mounted units, and between 30 to 60 years for ground-mounted installations on metal supports.
- **Cabling:** 30 years.

Monocrystalline has a minimum lifespan of 25 years and can last more than 50. Meanwhile, polycrystalline have a lifespan range around 25 years. Due to the up-to-day recycling technology [15], that more than 88% of the materials that make up a photovoltaic panel are recoverable.

3. Cost

3.1. Operation or Maintenance Cost

The annual maintenance and recurring costs are almost negligible, since there are no moving parts, and the input fuel (sunlight) is free. For optimum performance, the system only requires cleaning of modules and basic preventive and corrective maintenance. However, for off-grid systems where batteries are used, the maintenance costs are higher on account of battery replacement every 3-5 years. To ensure high generation and low maintenance cost, regular monitoring through data loggers is highly recommended. Typically, the maintenance costs for smaller Solar PV systems is about 2% of the initial system cost, and for larger systems is about 1% of the initial cost [16].

The two primary aspects of maintaining a solar PV system are: 1) to regularly monitor your system's performance through the data logger and 2) to clean the panels about 6-10 times in a year.

Beyond this, it is advisable to have your installer conduct at least two visits in a year just to check the general health of your system.

3.2. Tariff

Feed-In Tariff: A Feed-in tariff is the rate/cost at which you sell the electricity generated by your solar system to your DISCOM either via net-metering or gross metering. This tariff rate varies from state to state depending upon the solar policy of the state. The tariff also differs across consumer categories. This tariff is often referred to as net feed-in tariff in case of net-metering and gross feed-in tariff in case of gross metering [17].

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Solar Tariff: Solar tariff is the rate/cost at which you purchase the electricity from the installer/owner of a solar system under a Power Purchase Agreement (PPA). The rate is agreed upon for a certain period of time as per the clause of the agreement. This insulates you from any tariff hike in the near future. However, the solar tariff may be subject to an increase depending on the terms and conditions of the signed agreement¹.

3.3. Cost savings

PV projects are long-term investments, highlighting the fact that solar panel manufacturers guarantee at least 80% of initial production over the PV system's 25 years lifetime. Cost saving of solar system depends on a number of factors. Direct hours of daily sunlight, sun tracking system and size and angle of your roof are both important, but local electricity rates play the biggest role in determining how much solar can save.

3.4. Return on Investment (ROI)

Solar PV systems cost between € 1,637 and € 2,045 per kWp of installed capacity, depending on system size and complexity. To give an accurate quote, factors such as ease of access to the roof, the nature of mounting system / roof covering, the length of cable runs, and shading and monitoring requirements needed to be taken into consideration. The table below gives some sample system outputs, based on a nearly east facing expected to generate 866 kWh per kWp (PVGIS forecast). An optimal south facing system is expected to generate 985 kWh per kWp and the returns will be even higher [18].

Table A1. 2. ROI for different system sizes.

System size (kWp)	Annual generation (kWh)	Total annual savings (€)	ROI (%)
2	1675	210	5
3	2792	350	8
4	3350	420	9
10	8659	1164	10
30	25968	3490	14
50	42993	5780	16

3.5. Funding schemes

There are a number of different financing schemes that can be used to raise money for solar PV. Some of them are self-funding, mezzanine financing, crowdfunding [19].

3.6. Possible suppliers

Table A1. 2. PV panel suppliers.

Name	Country
SolarWorld	Germany
Q cells	South Korea & Germany
Photowatt	France
Atersa	Spain
Trina Solar	China
C Sun	China
DelSolar	Taiwan, China

¹ <https://www.itsmysun.com/faqs/what-is-solar-tariff/>

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4. Applications

4.1. Existing farming applications

Solar electric energy can be used to move sprinkler irrigation systems [20]. PV systems are also extremely well-suited for pumping water for livestock in remote pasture, where electricity from power lines is unavailable (EREC, 2002) [21].

4.2. Existing non farming applications

PV systems have been widely used to provide supplemental power source for homes, businesses, municipalities, military installations, etc.

4.3. Typical combinations with other technologies

Photovoltaic system can be feasibly combined with other renewable energy solution such as geothermal, wind energy, solar thermal system etc.

The generated electric energy could also be stored in electrical storage system.

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Appendix 2: Solar thermal systems

1. Technical description

1.1. Working principle

Contrary to the photovoltaic panels which convert it directly into electricity, the solar thermal panels transform the energy from the sun into heat. The purpose of using this technology is to get hot water or hot air for heating/cooling applications. The heat can also be converted into power using other engines/machines, but this report will focus on the heat only.

In order to convert the sun rays into thermal energy, solar thermal panels use an absorber which will absorb the sun rays and transform this energy into heat. The absorber can be made from copper, or aluminium, because of their good thermal conductivity. Its absorption coefficient (ratio), necessary for the solar thermal efficiency, will depend on the material used. Then by conduction, the absorber will transfer this heat to tubes in which flows the fluid we want to be heated. Here, it is important for the tubes to get an important conduction transfer (usually copper tubes). The type of fluids used can be liquid ones, or air: water, oil, salts, air, nitrogen, helium are some examples. Usually, the liquid heat transfer fluid is a mix of glycol and water, the glycol being used for its antifreeze properties.

To avoid the loss of heat in the environment, solar panels also have an insulation part, on their bottom face. Furthermore, the panels can be glazed or not, depending on the application; the glazing being used as a protection usually (against dust for instance) but also permitting to avoid some energy losses. The solar thermal panels can either be active or passive. If passive, not other components than the collector are needed for their running. At contrary, an active solar thermal panel means other technological and mechanical devices are needed for its running such as pumps, sensors, controllers, check valves etc. In some cases, a heat exchanger is also needed.

Nonetheless, no matter if the systems are passive or active, for both need a storage tank would be necessary to store the hot fluid. The storage capacity of the solar thermal gives them advantages compared to photovoltaic panels.

1.2. Classification

1.2.1. Collectors

There are different types of solar thermal collectors and can be divided into two main types as **non-concentrating collectors** and **concentrating collectors**, as illustrated in Fig. A2. 1.

The non-concentrating collectors are the ones who's the absorption area is the same as the intercepting area. They include flat plate and ETC (evacuated tube collector). The flat plate collector can be either glazed or unglazed, and the ETC can have either direct flow or heat pipe.

The concentrating collectors are the ones which intercept the sun rays in a much smaller area, thanks to a specific geometry/design, which includes an increased flux. They include CPC, parabolic dish, parabolic trough, and solar tower. They usually use different types of heat transfer fluids: the parabolic trough can have Molten Salt for instance.

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Fig. A2. 1. Classification of the different types of solar thermal collectors.

- Flat-plate collector** is usually made of an outer cover, an inner one, (glazing cover), a black absorber plate, a fluid conduit, an insulation material, and a collector box. The three most important parts of these collectors are the absorber, a black surface “energy absorbing”, which will transfer this energy to a fluid, a back insulation to reduce some conduction losses and a transparent envelope which will reduce both convection and radiation losses. Water and air heaters are quite similar, except the fact that for the water heater, the fluid conduits are tubes and for the air heater these conduits are ducts.

Furthermore, usually these collectors do not require any tracking systems. They are usually fixed in position, as a part of the roof/wall structure, and so oriented appropriately. In the northern hemisphere, their orientation should be south and the contrary for the northern hemisphere.

Their working temperature can go from moderate one to 100 °C above ambient temperature. “At an ambient temperature of 30°C, absorbed solar radiation of 1000 W/m², and UL in the range of 8.33 to 3.70 W/m² °C for single-cover flat-plate collectors (nonselective to highly selective absorbers), the maximum equilibrium temperature ranges from 150 to 300 °C.” [22]. For low temperatures, an antifreeze fluid can be used. Corrosion phenomenon should also be considered.
- Evacuated Tube collectors (ETC)** is interesting for their anti-freezing/overheating properties. They are also usually more efficient than flat plate solar thermal collector. They are compounded of 10 to 30 tubes connected to a header pipe to form a panel.

The ETC tubes are made of glass in which appears a heat pipe. This heat pipe is made of copper and has a black copper fin acting as the absorber. This one will heat a phase change material fluid. A condenser, at the end of the tube, will permit to condensate the gas (created during the evaporation of the initial liquid due to hot temperatures) into liquid. The latent vapor/energy released during this transformation will be transferred to an antifreeze fluid (water+ glycol for example) thanks to a heat exchanger, and this heated fluid will give its heat

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to water for hot water applications systems, or air for heating systems, again with the help of a heat exchanger [23].

Fig. A2. 2. Scheme of (a) flat-plate collector and (b) evacuated tube collector.

1.2.2. Systems

The system can be catalogued as active and passive as shown in Fig. A2. 3 [24]. A passive water heater is also called natural circulation system or thermosyphon. In this system, a tank is located on the top of the receiver and the water heated by the collector will remain on the top because of a density difference. The water will circulate by convection, there is no need of pumps or electricity. Because of the tank which might be heavy, the contractors must consider the roof design. Another type of passive solar system is ICS. ICS is usually cheaper than thermosyphon. They are usually not adapted to cold climates, but mid-freeze ones instead, due to the risk of freezing for the outdoor pipes.

In an active system, or so called forced-circulation systems, the use of a pump is required. A differential thermostat will control when this pump can be turn on: usually it is when the difference between the top header and the bottom of the tank is positive and sufficient. A check valve can also be part of these system; its aim is to prevent the phenomenon of reverse circulation and the thermal losses implied that can happen in the night-time. A non-freezing fluid can also be used in an active system: in this case, a heat exchanger with water is needed so that we have hot water at the end (if it is for a water heater application; otherwise, it can be air also, for heating applications). This system is called indirect circulation system and is popular in climates where freezing temperatures might be reached. If only water is used on an active solar thermal system and flows from the collectors directly to the household, through a pump, then it is called a direct circulation system. These systems are more used in climates not prone to low temperatures.

Globally, the passive solar thermal systems are the cheapest of all solar systems. They can also have a longer longevity and a better reliability. They are nonetheless usually less efficient than active solar systems.

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Fig. A2. 3. Scheme of (a) passive direct system and (b) active indirect one-tank system.

1.3. Mechanical construction

The production process for the collectors consists in different steps such as first the metals transformation and then the assembly of these parts with other components. The collector, water tank and support, after their production are packed and stored in warehouses and thereafter sold from external companies which can transport and install them to the final users. The materials used in the production process are really important for the global performance of the solar thermal system. Typical construction of solar collector is shown in Fig. A2. 4.

Fig. A2. 4. Scheme of solar collector.

The polyurethane foam is used both for the collector and the tank for insulation purposes. It ensures good performances and reduced heat losses. However, this material should be in a dry environment to maintain all its qualities. Avoiding the moisture which can appears in solar collectors because of the air trapped, in the assembly process, can be avoided with desiccants (moisture absorbers).

The enclosure which supports the collector and glazing, has also for purpose to protect it against heat losses due to the environment (the wind for instance), to avoid the moisture and keeping the system dry (or at least protecting it from the adverse effects of the rain/humidity). It furthermore contains the

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insulation part. This solar collector part can be made from wood, aluminium, galvanized steel, and in any case should be fireproof, resistant to the weather, perfectly sealed (to avoid moisture intrusion), being stable and durable. Usually, aluminium and galvanized steel are the most used, but fiberglass reinforced plastic can be too.

The components chosen for the absorber are also very important. Copper was the main material for years, until the prices increased, and other solutions were searched to replace it. Aluminium can be used even though this material is not as conductive as copper.

It is also possible to use selective coatings to improve the performance. They can work better than a normal coating in poor conditions (low irradiance). They permit a bigger solar radiation proportion to be converted into heat. Black chrome can be used, and titanium-nitride-oxide for this purpose [25].

1.4. Installation and maintenance

The installation of a solar thermal panel requires a professional, considering the different parameters important to consider such as the “solar resource, climate, building code requirements and safety problem” [26]. However, the maintenance of a solar thermal panel will depend on the technology chosen. As a matter of fact, the passive system requires less maintenance (almost not maintenance at all) than the active ones. It is nonetheless important to maintain the system in good conditions regarding the possible bad consequences which might occur if not, for instance a decrease in the efficiency.

The cleaning part can be done by the owner, depending on the size of the system, because the cost of a professional might exceed the energy gains after this process. The frequency of cleaning depends on the location especially. The solar panels systems being in an environment with agriculture dust, bird dropping, pollution, sand is more exposed to the dirt build up than others. Also, a very dry environment will require a special attention because of the lack of natural flushing and so cleaning (due to the lack of rain). For these reasons, in the context of using these technologies in farms, a frequent maintenance should be done. The average one recommended is an annual one.

For the mechanical maintenance, it is advised to check the components every 3 to 5 years. The electrical ones can usually be replaced after 10 years. Of course, a preventive maintenance can be done more often, every year for instance. This maintenance should be distinguished from the curative maintenance which consists in repairing actual/current failures identified in the system. The preventive maintenance, permitting to check if everything is in order, should be done annually then, and the cleaning can be done at the same time. It is better to plan this maintenance in your contract with your solar installer.

The ideal period to clean the solar panels is at the end of the winter, when the sun starts to shine more and the energy output increase, and during the day at a moment where the panels are not that warm. You can also notice a need of cleaning just by analysing the energy output of your system. Usually, an unclean panel induce a decrease of energy, as said before [27].

There are some specifications regarding how to clean and maintain a solar thermal system which are important to know. First, the water used for the cleaning: it has not to be hard, otherwise some residues can appear on the panel, neither cold, because of a possible thermal shock with a hot thermal panel, and not with high pressure, so to prevent the panel to be damaged. For this reason, washers should be avoided, but also abrasive sponge, due to the possible scratches on the panels. The type of

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products used for the cleaning such as solvents and detergents also have to be avoided to avoid any damages.

About more technical facts, which are specified usually in manuals, many parts of the solar thermal system must be controlled. At first the water pressure: the pressure should not be below 1 bar, to permit the glycol water to circulate well in the installation. The glycol itself, which is the antifreeze necessary in solar thermal fluids should have an appropriate quantity to prevent the freezing, and controlling this quantity is essential, especially for cold environments. The safety devices also must be controlled, such as the mixing valve, for instance, at the outlet of the hot water tank. Furthermore, it is important to check if there are not leakages if the installation is waterproof enough and perfectly sealed. The electrical devices and connections should in the same way be controlled, as much as the tank and pumps, necessary components of the system. Connectors housing also must be cleaned of dust and their lights functioning be verified.

2. Performance

2.1. Factors effecting Performance

The thermal output of the solar collector depends on different parameters such as the energy received from the sun (solar radiation), its area, its materials properties, orientation, inclination, geometry.

- **Solar radiation**

Depends on different parameters such as the time of the day, the local landscapes and weathers, the season, the geographic location. The location is really important because of the sun angle crucial for the energy received. The poles (northern and southern) for instance have a lower irradiance than the other regions. This can be explained by the Earth geometry and its position related to the sun. The optimum angle to receive the solar energy is 90°.

The local climate is also of great importance. In colder climates, more collectors will be necessary to reach the same energy output than in hot climates. It is however possible to increase the sun radiation by using planar reflectors.

The shading can also have an impact on the global performance of the system. It is for this reason, important to analyse the environment and the possible sources of shadings, as well as locating the collectors in some positions in order to avoid the shading issues.

- **Properties of materials**

The different materials of a collector have properties such as absorptance or emittance. These properties will be crucial for the heat transfer. The monochromatic directional absorptance is a property of a surface and is defined as the fraction of the incident radiation of wavelength (λ) from the direction (ν, ϕ) that is absorbed by the surface. The absorptance ratio is called α . The monochromatic directional emittance of a surface is defined as the ratio of the monochromatic intensity emitted by a surface in a particular direction to the monochromatic intensity that would be emitted by a blackbody at the same temperature. The emittance ration is called ϵ . The different materials and surfaces can also be reflective [22].

All these parameters are important to consider. Indeed, for a flat-plate collectors, the number of covers, the type and thickness of the glazing, the reflective properties of the coating on the cover glass, but also the type of coating on the collector, and the type of insulation will have

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an impact on the global performance. Other parameters, such as the wind speed, the mass flow rate and the dust deposition on the cover will affect the performance.

2.2. Efficiency

The thermal efficiency of a solar heat collector is not static. It changes as the operational conditions change. This can make a fair comparison of one collector to another rather difficult since panels come in different sizes, are made of different materials, and can be used in different climates and temperature applications

Fig. A2. 5 shows the efficiency of solar panels as the average temperature inside the panel increases from ambient at the left-hand side. Evacuated tube systems generally start off with lower efficiency than flat plate systems due to the inefficient geometry of packing glass tubes together. However, as the temperature of the panel increases, the superior insulation of the vacuum is demonstrated, and the efficiency decreases more slowly than for flat plate panels. Evacuated tube systems are best suited to industrial process heat applications, where higher temperatures are required. For domestic hot water applications, much of the available energy is collected at the left-hand half of the curve and both types of products perform well. Some suppliers of solar panels misleadingly quote the optical efficiency as if it were the overall efficiency of their product. Some even use the efficiency of the black surface at absorbing light - ignoring the effect of the cover glass. This simplification is extremely misleading. As the grey line shows, it is easy to create a panel with a high optical efficiency, just leave out the glass.

Fig. A2. 5. Varying efficiency of panel with temperature.

2.3. Life cycle emissions

The energy analysis includes the energy consumed for the production, installation, and transport of the collectors. Most of the energy consumption in this case is related to the transport. The environmental impacts are the resources consumption, the air and water emissions, the wastes, and solid pollutants. They can be translated into indexes such as global warming potential (GWP),

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acidification potential (AP), ozone depleting zone (ODP), nitrification potential (NP), photochemical ozone creation potential (POPC). The result of a case study is summarized in Table A3.1 [28]. The CO₂ payback time is when the CO₂ savings are equal to the CO₂ consumed for the production of the solar collector. In this case study, the CO₂ payback time is less than 2 years, for a GWP of 721 kgeq CO₂. In General, the average CO₂ consumption for the manufacture of a solar thermal system including the tank, collector, and other components is about 1000 kg of CO₂. For a flat-plate collector, the average payback period is about 1.5 years, but this will depend on many factors such as the climate, used components, energy sources of the back-up system for instance.

Table A2. 1 Potential environmental impacts of solar thermal collector.

GWP (kgCO ₂ eq.)	721
AP (kgCO ₂ eq.)	5
ODP (kgCO ₂ eq.)	Negligible
NP (kgCO ₂ eq.)	0.7
POPC (kgCO ₂ eq.)	0.4

2.4. Sizing

The size of the panels used will depend on the chosen type of panels. The size of the entire system will depend on the needs, the hot water demand.

2.5. Practical lifetime

Solar thermal panels have very few moving parts so can last for a long period of time after installation has been completed. They have been around for some time, so they are a well understood technology that operates to a very high standard. The pump for example may need replacing after around ten years although it is a relatively inexpensive component. Other parts that may need replacing are electrical components like the controller. There are different types of solar thermal heater which will require varying types of maintenance and will vary depending on individual project.

3. Cost

3.1. Installation costs

The installation costs include the costs which depend on the collector area, such as items for installation and purchase of collectors and also a bit of the storage costs, and other costs independent from the collector area which can be the control equipment but also construction equipment on site.

Then the total installation costs can be synthesized as: $C_s = C_a * A_c + C_e$ [22].

Where C_s : total installation costs, C_a : cost area dependent installation costs, C_e : cost area independent installation costs.

3.2. Operational costs

It includes the cost for the pumps and blowers, the one for the auxiliary energy, the taxes related to the building.

3.3. Maintenance costs

It depends on specific system size and requirements.

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3.4. Cost savings

It depends on specific system size and requirements.

3.5. Return on investment (ROI)

It depends on specific system size and requirements.

3.6. Funding possibilities

Solar thermal can be applied for heating and cooling purposes. The European Union agrees with the fact SCH (cooling and heating systems) can be used in most of the European countries [29]. Its reliability and economically viability for industrial and commercial purposes is necessary to be financed/supported by EU research and innovation. The horizon 2020 for instance, a European program, can finance low carbon technologies, including the solar thermal one.

The Norwegian Energy agency ENOVA finance energy efficient technologies and include the renewable ones, as solar thermal. The PAREER-CRECE programme in Spain can give grants for solar thermal systems up to 20% of the investment cost. The Conto Termico in Italy supports renewable energy, and so that solar thermal energy in Heating and Cooling. More detail information could be found in the Report [30].

3.7. List of suppliers

There are different suppliers for solar thermal applications, European and international ones. Here on Table A2. 2 are some examples:

Table A2. 2 List of suppliers.

Suppliers	Country	Activities and trading areas
European		
VESTA SOLAR HEATERS	Cyprus	manufacturing solar thermal systems for 36 years.
FABRISOLIA SLU	Spain	Activity: manufacturer/producer Trading areas: regional, national, European, international
THERMIC ENERGY RZ GMBH	Germany	Activity: manufacturer/producer since 2005 Trading areas: regional, national, European (not international)
International		
ZHEJIANG SHENDE NEW ENERGY CO. LTD.	China	Activity: manufacturer/producer since 1998 Trading areas: regional, national, European, international
SOLAR COLLECTOR INC	USA	Activity: manufacturer/producer since 2001 Trading areas: regional, national, European, international
SUNDRUM	USA	Activity: manufacturer/producer
XIAMEN DNSOLAR ENERGY CO.LTD	China	Activity: manufacturer/producer Trading areas: regional, national, European, international

4. Applications

4.1. Existing farming and non-farming applications

Solar thermal energy can be used in many types of industries. However, depending on the industry, the energy requirements will not be the same. Indeed, food and pharmaceutical industries need a lower temperature than pulp and paper ones for instance. It is therefore important to determine the field and requirements in term of energy output and temperature to choose the right technologies and

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sizing. Depending on the use of the solar thermal collectors (swimming pool heating, home water heating, home heating, process heat production), the appropriate collectors will be different (flat plate collector, evacuated tube collector, etc). Indeed, they do not work at the same temperatures.

The solar hot water systems can be used for industrial units. Solar energy permits also to heat the buildings as seen previously. This energy can be transferred to the spaces needed to be heated when needed, by using equipment's such as fans, radiators, air outlets, ducts. Etc. When not needed, the energy can be stored in insulated tanks until the next use. If not, enough energy is available with the solar collectors, in this case a back-up system for heating is necessary: this one will use different sources of energy (which can be oil, gas or electricity).

In the agriculture field, solar energy can also be used for drying purposes. The solar drying is usually applied to fruits, chillies, ginger, cashew nuts, but it can also be applied to milk or fishes (spray-dring). The traditional way (spreading them on the floor, manual labour and space needed) have some disadvantages than a solar technology can solve, making the process faster and less laborious.

It is also possible to use solar thermal energy in a different way, using mirrors concentrated onto the object we want to heat (solar furnaces). It is normally used for metallurgical and chemical applications, but it could also be used soon to permit to produce nitric acid and fertilizers.

4.2. Typical combinations with other technologies

It is possible to couple a geothermal heat pump with solar hot water systems collectors. Heat pumps can be considered as back-up system, and are interesting because of their performance: indeed, their efficiency is about 400% (for a COP of 4.0). There are different types of pumps such as the air to water (A-W) and the water to water(W-W).

If the solar thermal array is small, the loads will be mainly carried by the heat pumps and electric resistance elements. The price of these elements, related to PV, are quite expensive. For this reason, it is better to minimize the PV investment (and so that elements) and thus maximize the solar array. However, this one should not be too big neither because of the increase of their cost if they produce too much heat (which cannot be stored).

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Appendix 3: Photovoltaic thermal collectors

1. Technical description

1.1. Working principle

Photovoltaic thermal (PVT) collectors, also known as hybrid solar collectors, are power generation technologies that convert solar radiation into usable thermal and electrical energy. PVT collectors combine photovoltaic solar cells, which convert sunlight into electricity, with a solar thermal collector, which transfers the otherwise unused excess heat from the PV module to a heat transfer fluid. By combining electricity and heat generation within the same component, these technologies can reach a higher overall efficiency than solar photovoltaic (PV) or solar thermal alone. These hybrid systems have the benefits of increasing the electrical efficiency of the PV, obtaining thermal energy, and avoiding thermal degradation of PV solar panels [31]. On the other hand, it also saves space by combining the two structures to cover less area than two systems separately [32]. Fig. A3. 1 shows a very simplified diagram of a solar liquid PVT system [31].

Fig. A3. 1. Simple diagram of the electrical and thermal parts of a common PVT system.

1.2. Classification

There exist three common types of PVT collectors already readily available on the market, namely: PVT Air Collector, PVT liquid collector, and the concentrating PVT collector. Each of these have some additional features that affect the performance. They can come as glazed (or covered) and unglazed, and insulated or uninsulated. Vacuum tube collectors are still early in the market and will not be considered in this study.

1.2.1. Air Collectors

The basic air-cooled design, shown in Fig. A3. 2, uses either a hollow, conductive housing to mount the photovoltaic panels or a controlled flow of air to the rear face of the PV panel. PVT air collectors either draw in fresh outside air or use air as a circulating heat transfer medium in a closed loop. Using air as a heat transport medium compared to a heat transfer fluid has significant advantages however as (1) there can be no freezing and no boiling of collector fluid; (2) there is no risk of damage if leakage occurs [33], and (3) the infrastructure required has lower cost and complexity.

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1.2.2. Liquid PVT Collectors

PVT water collector satisfies the need of electricity along with a heat transfer fluid (HTF). In the PVT liquid collector, water or in locations where freezing can occur, a water/glycol mix is used. Mineral oil can also be used in higher temperature applications. The basic liquid-cooled design uses channels to direct fluid flow using piping attached directly or indirectly to the back of a PV module. The heat from the PV cells is conducted through the metal and is transferred to the working fluid (presuming that the working fluid is cooler than the operating temperature of the cells) [34].

1.2.3. Concentrating PVT

A concentrator system, such as the Solarus collector shown in Fig. A3. 2 (c), has the advantage to reduce the photovoltaic (PV) cell area needed. Therefore, it is possible to use more expensive and efficient PV cells, e.g., multi-junction photovoltaic cells. The concentration of sunlight also reduces the amount of hot PV-absorber area and therefore reduces heat losses to the ambient, which significantly improves the efficiency for higher application temperatures. Using concentrators to increase the electric output from a PV cell array can have big economic advantages in terms of lowering the cost of PV electricity. This can be done using lenses and reflecting mirrors. By decreasing the required cell area for production of electricity environmental gains can also be made. For the thermal part, using concentrators is a possibility of increasing the heating capacity in a solar water heater, by increasing the intensity of the irradiation. Concentrator systems can include an accurate sun tracking system; however, this can incur higher costs and reliability issues. Under ideal conditions, about 75% of the sun's power directly incident upon such systems can be gathered as electricity and heat [35].

Fig. A3. 2. Scheme of (a) PVT air collector, (b) PVT water collector and (c) concentrating PVT collector.

1.3. Mechanical Components:

The PVT Collector consists of PV module glazing, Encapsulant, Solar PV cells, Backsheet, Heat exchanger and thermal insulation, as showing in Fig. A3. 3.

Fig. A3. 3. Different components of a PVT water collector.

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In addition to the PVT collector the following main components are required for the transfer of electricity and heat:

Inverter: An inverter is an electrical device which accepts electrical current in the form of direct current (DC) and converts it to alternating current (AC). Most inverters have conversion efficiencies of 90% or higher and contain important safety features including ground fault circuit interruption and anti-islanding.

Racking: This is the mounting apparatus which fixes the solar array to the ground or rooftop. Typically constructed from steel or aluminium, these mechanically fix the solar panels in place with a high level of precision. Some ground mounted racking systems also incorporate tracking systems which use motors and sensors to track the Sun through the sky, increasing the amount of energy generated at a higher equipment and maintenance cost.

Heat exchanger and storage tank: Once the transfer fluid in the collectors heats up, it moves into a storage tank that stores the hot water. Inside the storage tank is the heat exchanger that transfers the heat to the heat use.

Fluid circulation system: The control system ensures the main operation of the thermal circulation. It controls the functioning of the pump and valves based on the temperature and pressure parameters that are received from the sensors. This prevents over-heating of the system and also prevents cold water from being cycled through the system when it's extremely cold outside and the transfer fluid isn't being warmed sufficiently.

Backup heater: Lastly, every system comes with a backup system. On days when it's too cloudy to generate enough heated water from solar energy, your backup heater will kick in and generate hot water for your home with gas or electricity.

Other Components: The remaining components of a typical solar PVT system include pipes, combiners, disconnects, breakers, meters and wiring.

1.4. Installation and Maintenance

Hybrid solar panels are installed in the same way that regular solar panels are. Roof hooks are fixed to the roof trusses or rafters, depending on where the panels will sit in relation to the roof cladding, to which aluminium rails are then fixed horizontally. The panels are bolted to these rails. Solar PVT panels will require the wires from the PV function to lead back to an inverter to turn it into usable energy, as well as pipes connecting to the hot water storage for its solar thermal component. It's important to know the PVT's theoretical maximum temperature so that it does not exceed the temperature for which the components are approved [36].

1.5. Selection of appropriate type

Air collectors: Using this type of PVT collectors makes sense if there is a demand for heated air. Advantages over liquid type are that air type collectors have lower cost and there is no risk of freezing, boiling or any damage to the system in case of a leakage. On the other hand, there are some major disadvantages of using air type PVT collectors such as they have lower thermal performance characteristics compared to liquid types [37].

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Liquid type: Using a liquid-PVT collector is advantageous if there is a demand for hot water. Flat structure allows convenient integration on a building, usually rooftops. Furthermore, hot water may be stored in an external tank for a period of time. Its drawback is that leakages and freezing may occur in extreme conditions. However, these can be prevented by robust construction and by using water-ethylene-glycol mixture [37].

Concentrating type: The advantage of concentrating PVT collectors is that usage of reflector material, which is less expensive than PV modules, allows using less PV modules compared to flat type PVT collectors. By doing so, expensive PV modules are replaced by less expensive reflector material. The drawback of the concentrating PVT collectors is that because of the high temperatures, stable cooling is required, and the system becomes problematic if thermal load (cooling) decreases [37].

2. Performance

2.1. Fuel or electricity use

In a solar PV panel, photovoltaic cells typically reach an electrical efficiency between 15% and 20%, while the largest share of the solar spectrum (65% - 70%) is converted into heat, increasing the temperature of PV modules as illustrated in Fig. A4. 4. PVT collectors, on the contrary, are engineered to transfer heat from the PV cells to a fluid [38]. It is shown that by reducing 1 °C in PV cell temperature, the electrical efficiency increases by 0.4–0.5%. For amorphous silicon (a-Si), this increase is smaller, about 0.25%/°C [31]. This excess heat is transferred to the heat transfer fluid as usable heat. Thus, PVT collectors make better use of the solar spectrum.

Fig. A3. 4. Utilisation of the solar spectral irradiance in a common PVT collector

By co-generating solar electricity and heat in a single component, PVT collectors increase the combined efficiency and yield an optimized utilization of available space. In this way, despite the fact that the increase in electrical efficiency leads to a reduction in the thermal efficiency, the result is a greater use of space and the need for a smaller number of panels, so that the final efficiency is higher, and the costs are lower.

As a special mention, it should be known that the use of concentrating PVT (C-PVT) can also generate great benefits. Due to their configuration, C-PVT panels suffer from a greater loss of optical efficiency since the energy received is reflected. Despite this, concentration provides a greater energy benefit with less use of space, and because the way C-PVT is made, the use of material is reduced, so the cost

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is also less. Therefore, if one needs to use PVTs in the smallest possible space, a C-PVT collector could be the indicated option. Compared to non-concentrating PVTs, CPVTs are also able to operate at higher efficiencies for higher temperature outputs above the ambient temperature. This is because of the increased heat from concentrating the incoming radiation.

2.2. Factors affecting performance

The impact of the local climate on the performance of PVT collectors is very important. One particular impact is the given solar radiation of a location. Fig. A3. 5 shows the irradiance of a given location in Europe, and as shown the irradiance in the northern areas has on average almost half of the solar irradiance of the southern parts [39].

Fig. A3. 5. Average annual global horizontal solar irradiation in Europe.

Not only does the output of the electrical and thermal energy of the collector increase proportionally with increasing solar radiation, but the thermal efficiency of a PVT collector increases as well. This is clearly shown in Fig. A3. 6. The electrical efficiency remains the same after a certain threshold, however more radiation is needed for high levels of thermal efficiency. In comparison to flat plate solar thermal collector, concentrating PVTs can reach a higher efficiency at very low solar radiation, but has a lower peak efficiency than flat plate collectors. This is only valid for low temperature differences above the ambient temperature. At higher temperature differences in the collector above ambient temperature, it is the opposite effect, as shown in Fig. A3. 6. Higher solar radiation is needed for a concentrating collector to output useful energy; however, its peak efficiency will be higher than a flat plate collector.

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Fig. A3. 6. Efficiency comparison of thermal and electrical technology used in PVT collectors based on solar radiation for average operating temperatures of 20 °C (left) and 80 °C (right) above ambient temperature.

2.3. Efficiency

The overall efficiency of a PVT collector adds the electrical and thermal efficiency

$$\eta_T = \eta_{ele} + \eta_{th}$$

η_{ele} of the system is significantly improved by cooling of the modules by the working fluid and it can be represented by the following equation [40]

$$\eta_{ele} = \eta_o [1 - \beta(T_c - T_0)]$$

η_o , which is the actual efficiency of module can be given as

$$\eta_o = \frac{V \times I}{A \times G_t}$$

The thermal efficiency η_{th} of PVT system changes with the change fluid flow rate, type of solar collector, modifications in the absorber geometry as is usually expressed as

$$\eta_{th} = \frac{Q_u}{A \times G_t}$$

2.4. Lifecycle emissions

There has been plenty of studies to study the emissions for solar thermal and PV systems, but literature review shows that those on PVT systems have been very few. The study showed that nearly the whole of the environmental impacts were due to PV module production, aluminium parts (reflectors and heat-recovery-unit) as well as copper parts (for heat-recovery-unit and hydraulic circuit), with barely significant contributions from the other system components, such as support structures or electrical/electronic devices. The disposal phase contribution is again almost negligible [41].

2.5. Operation strategies

Glazed, or covered PVT collectors, feature an additional glazing, which encloses an insulating air layer between the PV module and the secondary glazing. This reduces heat losses and increases the thermal efficiency. Moreover, a glazed collector usually has an iron tempered glass covering, which is the reason they usually are more expensive. Glazed and insulated PVT collectors can reach significantly higher temperatures than PV modules or uncovered PVT collectors. These collectors have higher working temperatures, due to the reduction of convective heat losses on the front and back side of

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the collector. Despite this, these kinds of collectors have a lower efficiency rate, since PV cells are negatively affected by high temperatures. Thus, these collectors work as primarily heat energy generating systems. In contrast, uninsulated collectors work under lower temperatures, which reduces the heat energy output, but leads to higher electrical earnings. Anti-reflective coatings on the front glazing can reduce the additional optical losses [42].

Unglazed collectors do not have any glass covering. Generally, they are made of heavy-duty rubber or plastic treated with an ultraviolet (UV) light inhibitor to extend the life of the system.

Fig. A3. 7. Comparison of solar efficiencies for the electrical and thermal part of an uncovered (uninsulated) and covered (insulated) PVT collector.

Due to the cheaper parts and the easy design these unglazed collectors are less expensive than glazed collectors. Unglazed collectors are also used for indoor pools in colder climates because then the water will go back to the pool when not used.

Even if you need to shut off the system for a while during colder weather unglazed collectors are more cost efficient than installing more expensive glazed collectors [43]. Uninsulated PVT collectors are beneficial for operation near and below ambient temperatures and are normally not so sensitive to condensation. This is because condensation stays on the outside of the product and causes no damage when temperature go below the dew point. An unglazed PVT thus also has a rapidly decreasing efficiency as the working temperature rises and the wind load increases, meaning that it is recommended to use unglazed PVTs in colder climates and with low radiation [42].

2.6. Practical lifetime

Like PV technology panels, PVT collectors offer a practical life of at least 20 years, and usually come with a 10 - 20 years warranty. It is important to mention that, thanks to the cooling provided by the thermal system, and under proper maintenance, the loss of efficiency of the electrical part due to the passage of time is reduced.

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3. Cost

3.1. Cost savings

The saved costs by installing a PVT varies depending on many factors and Fig. A3. 8 shows the annually saved fuel costs from using different types of PVT collectors to supply heat to various applications compared to their current heating system according to a study. The average for the systems with available data is about 22 EUR/m² annum. Therefore, higher investment costs of about 550 EUR/m² are covered by saved fuel costs considering the typical lifetime of a PVT.

Fig. A3. 8. Saved fuel costs compared to their current heating systems calculated based on different applications and type of collector.

3.2. List of brands/suppliers

Common suppliers of PVT collectors are shown in Table A3. 1 below. The table is also split into the different types of PVTs the suppliers are most commonly associated with. However, many suppliers also deliver other types of PVT collectors as well as solar thermal and PV technology.

Table A3. 1. Most common suppliers of PVT collectors differentiated by their most common technology.

Glazed and insulating	Abora (Spain) EndeF (Spain) Consolar (Germany)
Unglazed and uninsulated	DualSun Wave (France) Fototherm (Italy)
Concentrating PVT	SunOyster (Germany) Solarus (Netherlands)

4. Applications

4.1. Existing farming applications

PVT collectors have been used in large greenhouses as a source of heat in the ground and electricity for the fans, however there is little documentation for PVT use in livestock farming. This could be because conventional PVT systems are typically operated below 100 °C, which prevents their application to industrial and agricultural processes where higher temperature heat is needed (see Fig. A3. 9) [39]. One way to overcome this is to combine the PVT with heat pumps. Furthermore, a promising solution to tackle this limitation is to split the incident solar spectrum into two separate

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bands, one that is directed to PV modules and is well-suited to conversion into electricity, while the rest is absorbed as heat by a thermal absorber. However, this technology is still in its early research phase [44].

Fig. A3. 9. Temperature requirements for heating processes in agriculture.

4.2. Existing non-farming applications

The range of applications of PVT collectors, and in general solar thermal collectors, can be divided according to their temperature levels as shown in Fig. A3. 10:

Fig. A3. 10. Typical applications of different types of PVT collectors based on their operating temperature.

Low temperature applications include heat pump systems and heating swimming pools or spas up to 50 °C. Low and medium temperature applications for space heating and domestic hot water provision are found in buildings, with temperatures from 20 °C to 80 °C. The temperature of the specific system depends on the requirements of the heat supply system for domestic hot water.

Swimming pool: Hot water from the collector can be used for heating of swimming pools as it can generate an optimum temperature (20 °C – 40 °C) for use in swimming pools.

Domestic hot water heating: The main components of a solar system for heating provision are the solar collector array, a thermal energy transfer circuit (circulation pump, valves, piping and heat exchanger) and a water storage tank.

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Space heating: Regarding PVT collectors for space heating purposes, several authors focus on PVT air collectors PVT water collectors can also provide space heating. The hot water generated by the PVT collectors is usually collected in a hot water storage tank.

Process heat: PVT can be used to produce relatively high temperature for any kind of process heat in industry (pasteurization, car washing, bottles washing, etc..). Evacuated and concentrating collectors can be used in industrial processes where heat over 80 °C is needed. Applications are very few and not enough documented in 2019.

4.3. Combinations with other technologies

PVT collectors can be used in combination with heat pumps. The collector delivers heat from solar radiation and ambient heat to the cold side of the heat pump, lifting the efficiency of the heat pump. The efficiency of the thermal energy production is high and can be over 100% when calculated in reference to the solar energy incident on the plane of the collector since the additional heating energy from the heat pump is to be added [35].

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Appendix 4: Wind energy

1. Technical description

Wind energy is currently considered as one of the most viable alternatives to fossil fuels. The wind energy is renewable and widely distributed, meanwhile its operation process is 'clean' without producing greenhouse gas. The wind energy could be harnessed through wind turbine and transformed into electrical power or mechanical work [45].

1.1. Working principle

Fig. A4. 1 presents the typical domestic system of wind turbine, which is not connected to the grid. The wind turbine is coupled directly to an asynchronous generator mounted on the same shaft. The domestic system do not have variable pitch rotor blades so the rotor speed varies with the wind speed. The generator output voltage and frequency are proportional to the rotor speed and the current is proportional to the torque on the shaft. The output is rectified and fed through the voltage regulator to an inverter which generates the required fixed amplitude and frequency AC voltage. Partial of the generated power is stored into the battery.

Fig. A4. 1. Basic workflow of wind turbine (domestic system).

1.2. Classification

Based on the output power, the wind turbine is catalogued as small (300 W to 100 kW), medium (100 kW to 1 MW) and large (>1 MW). Regarding the on-site electricity consumption of livestock building/farm, the small size wind turbine(s) is adequate.

Based on the structure, wind turbines could be divided into horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTs) and vertical axis wind turbines (VAWTs) [46], their basic forms are shown in Fig. A4. 2. The HAWTs are very sensitive to the direction of the wind and do not cope well with turbulent flow and buffeting. Therefore, HAWTs are suited to be installed in open areas with fairly smooth horizontal airflow and few upstream obstacles. VAWTs are less influenced by changes in wind direction, evoke lower noise levels and tend to be more aesthetically pleasing. The comparison between HAWTs and VAWTs were summarized in Table A4. 1 [47]. At present, HAWTs is commercially more efficient than VAWTs [48].

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Fig. A4. 2. Basic forms of (a) three-bladed HAWT and H-Darrieus VAWT.

Table A4. 1. Comparison between HAWTs and VAWTs.

Performance	HAWT	VAWT
Power generation efficiency	50%-60%	>70%
Gear box	Above 10 kW: YES	NO
Blade rotation space	Quite large	Quite small
Wind resistance capability	Weak	Strong
Noise	5-60 dB	0-10 dB
Starting wind speed	High (2.5-5 m/s)	Low (1.5-3 m/s)
Failure rate	High	Low
Maintenance	Complicated	Convenient
Rotating speed	High	Low
Effect on birds	Great	Small

The conversion of available wind power into actual power varies nonlinearly due to the transfer functions of the electrical generators. The relationship between the wind speed and generated power is depicted by the wind turbine power curve [49]. The wind turbine power curve is essentially comprised of three regions, as Fig. A4. 3 shows. When the incoming wind speed is lower than the cut-in speed, the minimum speed for starting up, the output power is zero. Rated speed is the wind speed at which the rated power, which is the maximum output power of the electrical generator, is obtained. The cut-out speed is usually limited by engineering design and safety constraints. It is the maximum wind speed at which the turbine is allowed to produce power. Power curves for existing machines, derived using field tests, can be obtained from the wind turbine manufacturers. The approximate shape of the power curve for a given machine can also be estimated by using the power characteristics of rotor, generator, gearbox ratio and efficiencies of various components [50].

Theoretically, the power (P) available in the wind impinging on a wind driven generator is given by:

$$P = C_p(0.5\rho AV^3) \quad (1)$$

in which C_p is the power coefficient, A is the swept area (m^2), ρ is the air density (kg/m^3) and V is the average approaching wind speed (m/s) [51]. Equation (1) denoted that the output power is determined

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by the characteristic of selected wind turbine (C_p and A) and local wind distribution. C_p is varies with wind speed [52], and could be enquired from product supplier.

Fig. A4. 3. Wind turbine power curve.

1.3. Mechanical construction

The basic construction could be referred to section 1.1. The following parts are the essential mechanical construction of wind turbine [53].

Rotor Blades: The rotation of blade caused by wind flow convert the wind energy into mechanical energy which are thereafter transferred to the shaft.

Shaft: The shaft is connected to the electrical generator directly or via gearbox for transferring mechanical energy generated by the rotation of blade into an electrical generator.

Gearbox: The gearbox increases the rotation speed of blades to much higher value so as to generate electricity at a desired voltage level.

Generator: The generator is an electrical device that converts mechanical energy received from the shaft into electrical energy.

Power Converter: The power converter is an electrical device that stabilizes the alternating output voltage transferred to the grid/battery.

Anemometer: measures the wind speed.

Wind Vane: senses the direction of the wind.

Pitch Drive: control the angle of blades.

Yaw Drive: rotate the nacelle whenever any change in wind direction to yield maximum wind energy.

1.4. Installation and maintenance

The installation process depends upon the size and type of wind turbine. Before installation, it is necessary consult professional installer for technical survey of location and wind speed distribution.

The suggested annual maintenance items include [54]:

- Checking and tightening bolts and electrical connections as necessary.

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- Checking machines for corrosion and the guy wires for proper tension.
- Checking for and replace any worn leading-edge tape on the turbine blades, if appropriate.
- Replacing components such as turbine blades and/or bearings as needed.

2. Performance

2.1. Fuel or electricity use

During the generation of wind energy, the wind turbines do not consume fuel or electricity.

2.2. Factors affecting performance

Beside the products' own characteristic, local wind distribution is another factor affecting the output power. The stability of output power is affected by the varying wind speed and direction. It is important to select sufficiently windy site and best tower height to guarantee the stability and economy of output power.

2.3. Efficiency

As showed in Fig. A4. 3 and equation (1), the efficiency of wind turbine is related to wind speed and product characteristic (the C_p value).

2.4. Lifecycle Emissions

The lifecycle of wind turbine contains four main processes as manufacturing, transport and installation, operation and maintenance, dismantling and disposal. As reported by reference in 2016, the emissions of greenhouse gases amounted to less than 7 g CO₂-eq/kWh for onshore (with 2.3 and 3.2 MW turbines) [55].

2.5. Scope of Circularity

Currently, 85-90% of an entire wind turbine can already be recycled. Recycling circles have been established for most of the components as steel, cement, copper wire, electronics and gearing. However, wind turbine blades are more challenging to be recycled [56]. Up to day, the wasted wind turbine blades could be reused or repurposed in varieties way as street furniture and building structures [57]. Leading companies (e.g. Siemens Gamesa and Vesta) launched plans to make wind turbine fully recyclable by 2040 [58,59].

2.6. Stability/continuity

The icing condition also needed to be considered when wind turbine is installed in high altitudes and arctic latitudes, e.g. Finland [60]. Ice accretion on turbine blades can degrade turbine performance and durability, and even lead to safety concerns associated with ice shedding (if ice were thrown from the rotating blades) [61]. The implementation of wind turbine in livestock farming is well adaptable to the type of farm, since it could be installed stand-alone away from the livestock building. However, the impact of noise generated by wind turbine on the productivity of animal needed to be evaluated before implementing wind turbine. Meanwhile, the implementation of wind turbine could not affect the present power and heat (or cooling) delivery system. Since wind turbine is implemented as assistant energy supply and not directly connected to the present power system.

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2.7. Sizing

The sizing depends on the energy demand, which should be consulted with professional installer.

2.8. Operation strategies

In order to maintain its stability in livestock farming, it is suggested to combine wind turbine with other RES technologies (e.g. solar photovoltaic, geothermal and biogas [62]) and energy storage technologies (e.g. compressed air energy storage [63] and Hydrogen-based energy storage system [64,65]).

2.9. Practical lifetime

The design lifetime of wind turbines is estimated to be 20 to 25 years [66].

3. Cost

3.1. Installation costs

As reported by International Renewable Energy Agency, the averaged total Installed cost of onshore wind turbine in Europe was 1515 USD/kW in 2020 [67] lower than 1800 USD/kW in 2019 [68]. The detailed installation cost varies from country to country, it is suggested to enquire professional company for budget of the specified project.

3.2. Operation and maintenance costs

Operation and maintenance (O&M) costs for onshore wind often make up a significant part (up to 30%) of the wind turbine [69], but their share is keep decreasing. The average O&M cost between 2016 and 2018 were 33 USD /kW per year and 56 USD /kW per year in Denmark and Germany respectively [67]. The detailed O&M cost varies from country to country, it is suggested to enquire professional company for budget of the specified project.

3.3. Cost saving

The concept of Levelized Costs of Energy (*LCOE*) is generally used for the discussion of the economic merit of electricity generating technologies. *LCOE* offers a measure of the overall costs of a technology over its life cycle per unit of electricity produced [70]. The *LCOE* is given by:

$$LCOE = \frac{I_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{A_t}{(1+i)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{M_{t,el}}{(1+i)^t}} \quad (2)$$

in which I_0 is the investment expenditure in EUR (USD); A_t is annual total cost in EUR (USD) per year t ; $M_{t,el}$ is the electricity produced in the year t ; i is the real interest rate (discount rate) in %; n is the economic lifetime in year and t the year of lifetime (1, 2, ... n). Total annual costs A_t contains fixed operating costs and variable operating costs. For wind turbine, the lifetime is 20 to 25 years.

The average *LCOE* for onshore wind turbine and offshore wind turbine in Europe were 0.045 USD /kW and 0.083 USD /kW respectively in 2020 [67].

3.4. Payback Period

The payback period of wind turbine needed to be analysed with local wind condition, terrain type and the selected wind turbine. With the field measurement data in North East of Ireland, the payback

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period of a 3.5 MW wind farm (consisted of multi medium size wind turbines) was estimated to be 6.7 years [71]. Kelleher and Ringwood indicated that the payback period was negatively correlated with the output power of wind turbine [72]. With the wind data of Ireland, the payback periods of 2.5 kW and 0.6 kW wind turbines (Proven) were estimated to be 5.43 years and 14.78 years respectively. Therefore, it is suggested to pre-evaluate the local wind condition and define the specified solution for the targeted livestock farm. Thereafter the detailed payback period could be evaluated and discussed thoroughly.

3.5. Funding Schemes

The possible EU funding for supporting wind energy are summarized in Fig. A4. 4 [73]. The application timetable of each funding could be enquired in the corresponding website.

Fig. A4. 4. EU funding for wind energy landscape (2021-2027).

3.6. Suppliers

The Table A4. 2 summarizes the suppliers that could supply small horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTs) and vertical axis wind turbines (VAWTs) from European countries. For large size wind turbine, world famous brand as Vestas (Denmark) and Siemens Gamesa (Germany) are available in Europe.

Table A4. 2. Suppliers of small wind turbine in Europe.

Company	Country	Typical product
Bornay	SPAIN	Small HAWTs (0.8 kW – 5 kW)
BRAUN Windturbinen GmbH	Germany	Small HAWTs (2.5 kW – 12 kW)
Viking Wind ApS	DENMARK	Small HAWTs (10 - 25 kW)
Ergycon	ITALY	Small HAWTs (50 kW)
BaiWind S.L.	SPAIN	Small VAWTs
Aeolos Wind Turbine	UNITED KINGDOM	HAWTs (0.5 kW – 100 kW) VAWTs (0.3 kW – 10 kW)

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4. Application

4.1. Existing farming applications

Couples of researches had testified the possibility of combining wind turbine and solar photovoltaic for water pumping system in livestock buildings [74–76]. Ozgener proposed using small wind turbine for driving the secondary water pumping, brine pumping and fan coil of the solar assisted geothermal heat pump in the greenhouse [75], as Fig. A4. 5 shows. The small wind turbine system was expected to meet 3.13% of the annual electricity energy consumption of the system. Meanwhile, wind turbine was also proposed for recovering energy from livestock building' ventilation system [77,78]. Hong et al installed small wind turbine behind ventilation fans of broiler house [77], shown in Fig. A4. 6. The test result indicated that the small wind turbine system could recover 30% of the energy emitted by the ventilation fan.

Fig. A4. 5. Schematic of proposed solar assisted geothermal heat pump and small wind turbine systems.

Fig. A4. 6. Installation of wind power system behind ventilation fans at a broiler house.

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4.2. Existing non-farming applications

Wind turbine is a mature technology, the worldwide installed capacity of onshore and offshore wind farms were 698,043 MW and 34,367 MW respectively by 2020 [79].

4.3. Potential farming applications

The wind turbine could be either installed standalone in open areas or integrated with building (e.g. installed at walls or roof-top). For the implementation in livestock farm, installing the wind turbine stand-alone in open areas away from the buildings is preferred for maximum energy harness.

4.4. Status of implementation in Europe

By 2020, the total installed wind power capacity is 220 GW in Europe. 88% of the installed wind power capacity is onshore [80]. The reports on farming application of wind turbine in Europe is seldomly seen so far.

4.5 Best practices/typical combinations with other technologies

As the wind turbine is powered by wind, which is not stable and unpredictable, the application of wind turbine on farm is suggested to be combined with energy storage technology.

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Appendix 5: Bioenergy

1.1. Overview: Bioenergy

The term bioenergy refers to the energy extracted from organic matter of plant or animal origin such as agricultural and forest residues, energy crops, wood, or organic wastes, also known as biomass. Bioenergy is considered a low-carbon form of energy as the CO₂ released during its conversion is atmospheric CO₂ absorbed into organic matter through photosynthesis. Characterizing bioenergy as low carbon in comparison to fossil fuels is, in principle, a comparison of time scales as the carbon emissions from fossil fuels are also ultimately atmospheric CO₂ captured millions of years ago.

Bioenergy is the major renewable energy form worldwide, making up about 70% of all primary renewable energy sources [81]. Approximately 2.5 billion people worldwide rely on traditional uses of biomass, i.e. in form of fuelwood, charcoal, agricultural waste, and animal dung for cooking and heating in the Global South. These traditional methods are generally inefficient, unsustainable and unhealthy. The use of bioenergy in traditional cooking systems is particularly problematic due to the health implications of the particulate matter resulting from incomplete combustion [82]. Modern bioenergy technologies, on the other hand, can replace fossil fuels as a sustainable and clean source of energy and reduces GHG emissions significantly. The remainder of this report focusses on modern uses and applications of bioenergy.

Due to its high flexibility for integration into a wide of energy systems, bioenergy is a highly attractive energy option for countries at all stages of development [83]. Conversion through combustion gives bioenergy its great flexibility and versatility, and advantage over other renewable sources such as wind, solar, hydro, or tidal. Another key advantage of bioenergy is its ease of storage, e.g., in form of feedstock or energy carrier (solid, liquid, or gashouse fuel). Bioenergy can be used to generate electricity, heat or transport fuel, as well and solid, liquid, and gaseous energy carriers. Fig. A5. 1 below provides an overview of the various bioenergy conversion systems and end-uses [84].

Fig. A5. 1. Overview of bioenergy conversion technologies and end-uses.

Bioenergy systems can be easily integrated into existing energy infrastructures, technologies, and applications. For example, wood pellets can be used by up 15% in cofired coal power plants without

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converting the boilers [85]. Large-scale power plants have been converted to 100% biomass, leading to significant carbon reductions compared to coal [86]. Lignocellulosic and dry biomass such as straw, mill dust, firewood, and other combustible materials can be used well in solid fuel heating boilers to generate room and process heat.

Another example of integration in existing infrastructures and technologies is the blending of bioethanol and biodiesel with fossil fuels. Biofuels are increasingly being blended with conventional transport fuels, thus reducing the carbon intensity [87]. Biomethane, for instance, can be used for heating and transport and can be injected directly into an existing gas grid.

It is noteworthy that bioenergy can also be a waste management solution as organic waste, especially wood-based materials, provide valuable feedstock. Using anaerobic digestion for treating and managing livestock manures and slurry and organic waste (mainly food) is a long-established application across the world. Capturing gas from landfills, wastewater and sewage sludge are also common sources of bioenergy in some countries [88]. The use of agricultural and forest residues for bioenergy is another example of managing waste that would otherwise be burned in the fields, leading to significant CO₂ and particle emissions [89].

Although bioenergy is typically considered carbon-neutral, there are challenges to its wide implementation, including concerns about land use, crop usage, energy efficiency, and cost [90]. The life cycle impacts of the bioenergy industry, particularly GHG and aerosols emissions from conversion processes, must be further examined and understood [91]. Sustainable production of biodiesel, for instance, which is technologically established, can be challenging. In addition to high prices, the production of biodiesel relies on high-quality oil seeds such as rapeseed and sunflower while the use of such high-energy crops for energy is in direct competition with their use as food and animal feed. Other concerns about bioenergy include food security, deforestation and loss of biodiversity, and international trade imbalances [92].

1.2. Conversion Technologies

1.2.1. Thermochemical processes

Direct combustion is the most common form of bioenergy conversion and is typically used at fossil-fuel power plants. The process involves the combustion of solid biomass feedstock, often wood-based, in the presence of excess oxygen in boilers to produce steam. The heat produced from the combustion process can also be used in direct thermal applications, e.g., to heat buildings. Thermochemical conversion uses heat and chemicals to break down the cellulose in the feedstock to make the so-called syngas. There are two main thermochemical processes:

a) Pyrolysis uses high temperature and pressure in the absence of oxygen to decompose organic matter, resulting in gas, pyrolysis oil (bio-oil), or charcoal (bio-char), depending on the reaction temperature. Bio-oil is the most common product as with the widest end-uses, e.g., space or water heating in buildings and power generation.

b) Gasification converts solid fuel to gas through either a chemical or thermal process. Solid biomass like wood-waste temperatures above 700 °C with limited oxygen, creating a flammable synthesis gas known as “syngas”. Syngas is then either combusted to produce steam in a boiler for electricity or heat for thermal applications.

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1.2.2. Biochemical Processes

Cellulosic materials that are difficult to break down and thus cannot be directly burned can be converted into ethanol using biochemical processes. Biochemical conversion relies on a variety of high-temperature, high-pressure treatment techniques to break down the lignin and hemicellulose that surround the cellulose. Through hydrolysis using enzymes and acids the cellulose is then broken down into sugar which in turn is fermented to produce ethanol. The related processes are:

- a) Anaerobic digestion which entails the decomposition of organic waste by microorganisms in the absence of oxygen. This process produces a gas composed largely of methane and carbon dioxide. The methane can then be separated for use in power or heat generation, or any other application traditionally using natural gas. This process is discussed in a separate report.
- b) Fermentation of starchy plants leads can convert sugars into alcohol. This process is commonly used to produce ethanol from corn and sugarcane.

1.2.3. Transesterification

Transesterification is the process of converting oils or fats into biodiesel. The process involves the removal of water and contaminants from the feedstock, mixing with alcohol (typically methanol), and a catalyst such as sodium hydroxide. Fatty acid methyl esters and glycerin are produced as by-products of the process. The glycerin can be used in pharmaceuticals and cosmetics, while the esters are considered biodiesel and can be used as vehicle fuel or for other fuel purposes.

Using algae to produce biofuels based through transesterification is an area of increasing interest in research and development, mainly due to the high photosynthetic efficiency of algae. Short-term prospects algae-based energy remain nevertheless low due to the relatively high cost of cultivating and harvesting algae [93].

2. Cost

The cost of biomass technologies varies significantly by technology and country. As an example, the maturity stage and cost of various power generation technologies are shown in Fig. A5. 2 [91]. A detailed costing analysis is available in reference [94].

Fig. A5. 2. Biomass power generation technology maturity status (2011).

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Generation capacity is a key factor in the cost of bioenergy. As shown in Fig. A5. 3 [95], the specific cost of bioenergy-based power generation [€/kW] decreases by more than 70% as the generation capacity increases from 75 kW to 1,000 kW [92].

Fig. A5. 3. Specific power generation cost of bioenergy as a function of plant size.

Among renewable energy sources bioenergy remains a relatively expensive option. A 2016 study concluded that, despite the increasing bioenergy supply in absolute terms, the share of bioenergy in the EU’s renewable energy mix will decrease by 2030 due to the lower price of other renewable sources, particularly solar and wind, see Fig. A5. 4 [96].

Fig. A5. 4. Gross final renewable energy demand in 2014 (actual demand) and optimal RES mix for meeting the 27% EU renewables target.

According to a 2020 study [97], bioenergy costs are in the range of 65 to 158 €/MWh (17-44 €/GJ) for biomass feedstocks and 48 to 104 €/MWh (13-29 €/GJ) for waste-based bioenergy, compared to the fossil fuel prices in the range of 30-50 €/MWh (8–14 €/GJ). Significant potentials for cost reduction

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have been identified, mostly through non-technical developments, e.g. additional commercial plants, more favourable financing terms and supportive policies [93]. It is estimated that such measures can reduce the production costs for biofuels produced from biomass feedstocks to between 42 and 119 €/MWh (12-33 €/GJ) and 29-79 €/MWh (8-22 €/GJ) for waste-based fuels [93].

3. Bioenergy in Europe

In the Europe Union, bioenergy has long been the main renewable energy source (60%), with heating and cooling the largest end-users of bioenergy (75%) [98]. Fig. A5. 5 shows the share of bioenergy in the EU's energy sector [95]. More than 90% of the EU's biomass supply for bioenergy is sourced from within the EU. See Fig. A5. 6. As shown in Fig. A5. 7, forestry is the main source of biomass for energy in the EU (logging residues, wood-processing residues, fuelwood, etc.), with the share of waste, and agricultural crops and by-products rapidly growing in the last 15 years. In 2019, Germany, France, Italy, Sweden and the UK were the largest bioenergy consumers in absolute terms, while the Scandinavian and Baltic countries, as well as Austria, consume the most bioenergy per capita [95].

Fig. A5. 5. Bioenergy in the EU: share in gross final energy consumption, renewable energy supply and end-uses (2016).

Fig. A5. 6. Bioenergy supply in the EU (2016).

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Fig. A5. 7. EU's domestic bioenergy supply. (Data from 2006, 2016 and initial projections for 2020).

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Appendix 6: Biogas

1. Technical Description

1.1. Biogas

Biogas is a mixture of methane, carbon dioxide and small quantities of other gases produced by anaerobic digestion of organic matter in an oxygen-free environment [99]. The precise composition of biogas depends on the type of feedstock and the production pathway. The main methods of biogas production are the controlled digestion of biomass as well as recovery of the gas generated in landfills. For use as a transportation fuel or for injection into the natural gas grid, biogas must be upgraded to a higher grade, i.e. higher methane concentration, also known as “biomethane” or “renewable natural gas” [99]. Fig. A6. 1 [99] shows the general processes of biogas production from organic waste and applications in heating, power generation and fuel production (biomethane). The production of biogas through anaerobic digestion is one of the most energy-efficient and environmentally beneficial bioenergy technologies and has advantages over other forms of bioenergy production [100]. In addition, emission regulations, carbon taxes and subsidies on biomass energy has made anaerobic digestion an increasingly attractive and competitive waste management solution [100,101].

Fig. A6. 1. Overview of biogas production, upgrading to biomethane and end-uses.

1.2. End Use

1.2.1. Power Generation

Power generation from biomass is currently the most popular and growing market worldwide, due to technological improvements, decreasing reliance on fossil-based energy, and reduction of greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions. Biogas is used for electricity generation through internal combustion engines or gas turbines.

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1.2.2. Heat generation

Biogas can be directly combusted in boilers for heat generation only. With slight modification, natural gas boilers can be operated with biogas. In agriculture, the heat generated from biogas can be used for heating digesters, farm buildings, greenhouses, as well as aquafarming, cooling/refrigeration of farm products, and drying purposes.

1.2.3. Combined heat and power (CHP) generation

In heat- or power-only systems, the conversion efficiency is typically between 30% and 40%, which can be even lower when using biogas. Combined generation of heat and electricity improves the energy conversion efficiency of biogas up to 80%.

1.2.4. Transportation Fuel

Biogas upgraded to biomethane can be readily used in natural gas-powered vehicles as another option for fossil natural gas. Generally, biogas can be improved to transportation fuels (bio-CNG) that can be stored in the form of liquefied biogas (LBG), syngas/hydrogen, methanol for gasoline production, ethanol, and higher alcohols.

1.3. Anaerobic Digestion

Anaerobic digestion or decomposition is a process by which symbiotic microorganisms (bacteria and archaea) transform organic materials in oxygen-free conditions into biogas, nutrients and additional cell matter, leaving salts and refractory organic matter. Raw biogas typically consists of 40-60% methane, with the remainder being mostly carbon dioxide and water vapor along with trace amounts of hydrogen sulphide. In nature this process occurs in environments such as marshes, ponds, swamps, paddy fields, lakes, hot springs, landfills, sewage digesters, oceans and intestinal tracts of humans and animals [100]. Industrial application of the anaerobic treatment process far exceeds biogas production. Anaerobic digestion is used in waste management includes septic tanks, sludge digesters, industrial wastewater treatment, municipal wastewater treatment, hazardous waste management (aromatic and halogenated compounds), and agricultural waste management. Much of the fermentation used industrially to produce food and drink products is based on anaerobic digestion.

Fig. A6. 2. Biomethane potential and theoretical biogas contents.

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Conventionally, biogas production has mainly been coupled with the treatment of cattle manure and sewage sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) [102]. Currently, most of biogas plants digest cattle manure with other substrates to increase the organic content for enhanced biogas production. Co-substrates commonly include harvest residues, agricultural waste, food waste, and household waste. While fats provide the highest biogas yields, their retention times are high as well as having poor bioavailability, as shown in Fig. A6. ² [102,103] Carbohydrates and proteins, on the other hand, get rapidly converted into biogas, but provide relatively low gas yields.

Various factors like biogas potential of feedstock, design of digester, inoculum, nature of substrate, pH, temperature, loading rate, hydraulic retention time (HRT), carbon nitrogen ratio, volatile fatty acids (VFA) etc. influence the biogas production. Anaerobic digestion can be performed as a batch process or a continuous process. In batch system biomass is added to the reactor at the start of the process while in continuous digestion processes, the biomass is constantly added to the reactor. Anaerobic digestion is both a waste treatment technology, which enhances environmental quality and a sustainable energy producing technology.

1.4. Upgrading to Biomethane

Various technologies can be used to increase the methane (CH₄) content of the biogas, i.e., remove carbon dioxide (CO₂), water and vapor hydrogen sulphide (H₂S). Largely derived from other sectors (e.g., cryogenic separation of gases for medical or other industrial applications), these technologies include physical and chemical absorption, adsorption, membrane and cryogenic separation. The following review of the upgrading technologies currently available at commercial scale is adopted from reference [104] which should be consulted for further details.

- **Pressure Swing Adsorption** is a technique based on the selective adhesion of one or more components of a gaseous mixture, on the surface of a microporous solid; the material for biogas upgrading is typically equilibrium-base adsorbents. The pores of the adsorbent should allow an easy penetration of the CO₂ molecules, whereas filtering the larger CH₄ molecules.
- **Absorption techniques** are based on the solubility of the gases contained in biogas in certain liquids. Typically, either water or an organic solvent (e.g., methanol, N-methyl pyrrolidone, and polyethylene glycol ethers) is used in **physical absorption** plants, whereas amine scrubbing is widely used for chemical absorption.
- **Water scrubbing** is used as an upgrading technique as well as a pre-treatment (e.g., before PSA) for the removal of H₂S. The main limit of the WSC is that significant plant size is required to achieve high final concentration of methane.
- **Chemical scrubbing** involves reversible reactions between absorbed substances and solvent. The most common solution for biogas upgrading is based on amines: diethanolamine, monoethanolamide, methyl diethanolamine and piperazine.
- **Membrane separation** uses permeable barriers, specifically designed to be selective to specific molecules. Differences in concentration, pressure, temperature, or electric charge drive the gas mixture across the membrane, where undesirable contents (CO₂, H₂S) are removed. The main categories are polymeric, inorganic, and mixed matrix membranes. Inorganic membranes have several advantages compared to polymeric, mainly due to their higher mechanical

² TS: per total solids tonne

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strength, chemical resistance and thermal stability. The current trend in industrial applications is to use mixed matrix membranes.

- **Cryogenic separation** is a well establish technology for gas separation in various large-scale industrial applications. The physical principle behind cryogenic technique is that gases like CO₂ and H₂S liquefy under different pressure and temperature conditions. cryogenic plants operate at very low temperatures (-170 °C) and very high pressures (80 bar).
- **Biological upgrade techniques** are an emerging alternative to the current chemical and physical upgrading techniques. The working principle is separation via microorganisms (hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis) that convert CO₂ and H₂ into CH₄. Despite its potential, challenges are limiting the market deployment and the current practical interest.

Water scrubbing, membrane separation and chemical scrubbing are the most common upgrading techniques. Fig. A6. 3³ below shows the number of biogas upgrading plants using each of the techniques enumerated above, based on data from 37 leading countries participating in an International Energy Agency project on bioenergy [105].

Fig. A6. 3. The use of biogas upgrading techniques at operational units in the participants countries in the IEA Bioenergy Task (2016-2019).

1.5. Methanation

A second, less common method for converting biogas to biomethane is thermal gasification followed by methanation whereby woody biomass is first broken down at high temperature (between 700 - 800 °C) and high pressure in a low-oxygen environment. Under these conditions, the biomass is converted into a mixture of gases, mainly carbon monoxide, hydrogen, and methane (sometimes collectively called syngas). To produce a pure stream of biomethane, this syngas is cleaned to remove any acidic and corrosive components. The methanation process then uses a catalyst to promote a reaction between the hydrogen and carbon monoxide or CO₂ to produce methane. Any remaining CO₂ or water is removed at the end of the process [99].

The possibility of methane leakage from bioenergy technologies should be highly attached attention.

³ PSA: pressure swing absorption

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2. Performance

Biogas is a rapidly expanding source of renewable energy. Between 2000 and 2018, the global biogas production increased from 0.29 EJ to 1.36 EJ, with a global volume of 59.3 billion m³ biogas [106]. In the European Union, primary energy production from biogas has increased from just 167 PJ in 2005 to 710 PJ in 2018, accounting for half of the global biogas production [106]. While the contribution of landfill gas (LFG) recovery has plateaued, anaerobic digestion (AD) plants have contributed a major growth to the EU's increased biogas production, followed by sewage gas from wastewater treatment.

In the United States, there were more than 2100 biogas plants in 2017, of which 250 farm-based digestion plants using livestock manure [107], 654 biogas recovery plants from landfills [108]. Biogas in the US plants had an installed electricity capacity of 2400 MW in 2015 and 2438MW in 2016 and generated 1030 GWh electricity [108–110].

In developing countries, biogas is mainly produced in small, domestic-scale digesters to provide a fuel for cooking or even lighting, in comparison to developed countries, where biogas developments focused on larger scale, farm based and commercial, electricity and heat biogas plants. Different biogas support programmes have been carried out to develop household biogas systems to provide people with biogas for cooking, as an alternative energy source, to reduce firewood consumption and avoid deforestation, decrease indoor air pollution, and improve soil fertility. Several countries in Asia (China, Thailand, India, Nepal, Vietnam, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, and Pakistan) have large programmes for domestic biogas production.

3. Cost

3.1. Production costs

Globally, biogas production costs lie in a relatively wide range between USD 6.6/kWh to USD 66/kWh. In Europe, the average cost is around 16/kWh [99]. Between 70% and 95% of the total biogas costs are for installing biodigesters, with the remainder involving feedstock collection and processing costs [99]. There is huge variability, as feedstocks can be zero-cost or even negative in cases where producers of waste are obliged to pay to dispose of their waste, whereas in other cases “gate fees” for certain agricultural feedstocks may be as high as USD 100/tonne in some regions [99]. Fig. A7. 4 [99] shows the global average cost of biogas production through various technologies⁴.

Biogas is produced and consumed locally, meaning transportation costs are negligible. However, these estimates exclude the investments required to transform biogas into electricity or heat, and this can be considerable in some cases; for example, adding a cogeneration unit and including power grid connection and heat recovery distribution can add an additional 70% to the costs of an integrated project. While constructing larger and more industrialised facilities could provide some economies of scale, in general there is only modest scope for cost reductions as the main production technologies are already mature. Cost-competitive production routes do exist, however, in all regions, landfills equipped with a gas recovery system could provide biogas for less than USD 10/kWh; this represents around 8% of the global supply potential.

⁴ 1 MBtu ≈ 0.29 kWh

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Fig. A6. 4. Average costs of biogas production technologies per unit of energy produced (excluding feedstock), 2018.

In Europe, the cost of anaerobic digestion plants has a large spread: €49/MWh to €90/MWh (~€0.50/m³ to €0.90/m³), mainly depending on feedstock and digester size [111]. The production cost for thermal gasification, in contrast, is estimated around €90-€100/MWh (~€1.0/m³). The cost drivers for biogas production include capital and operational costs, the size of the digester, the production technique, and the feedstock cost (Table A6. 1). Biomethane production costs additionally include the cost of the upgrading unit. The costs of larger plants with certain waste stream feedstocks are gradually decreasing. Table A6. 1 provides an overview of the biogas production costs in Europe [99,111].

Table A6. 1. Overview of the cost values (2018) for the most important parameters in biomethane anaerobic digestion production process.

Technology	Digester size (Nm ³ /hr)	Biogas digester		Upgrading to Bio-methane (€/MWh)	Feedstock cost (€/tDM)
		CAPEX (€/MWh) ⁵	OPEX (€/MWh)		
Small anaerobic digestion	100	25	22	2 - 4	Range: 0 - 120
Medium anaerobic digestion	500	20	17		
Large anaerobic digestion	1000	15	12		Average: 19-36
Very large	>2000-3000	Not available	Not available		

3.2. Investment and Revenue

Due to the characteristically high specific cost of biomethane projects, in many cases, a single farmer or even a consortium of investors cannot finance the whole project by equity capital [112]. Therefore, borrowed capital is essential for the implementation of a biomethane plant. The Renewable Gas Trade Centre in Europe (REGTRACE)⁶ has recently published a detailed report of the various financing schemes that could be used for biomethane plants along with several case studies from various European countries [112]. Fig. A6. 5. [112] shows the general financing scheme and case and services flow of biomethane plants. The reader is referred to reference [112] for details.

⁵ Converted from USD/MBtu and rounded, assuming 1 USD = €0.85

⁶ <https://www.regatrace.eu/>

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Fig. A6. 5. General financing scheme of biomethane projects.

Fig. A6. 6 provides an overview of the revenue generation sources for a biomethane plant. The main source is feeding the produced renewable gas into the grid or sales of a bio-CNG or bio-LNG substitute [112].

Fig. A6. 6. Revenue streams of biomethane.

4. Applications

Biogas has numerous end-use applications compared with other renewable energy resources. applications Biomethane in particular is a flexible and easily storable fuel that can be used wherever natural gas is used without the need to change any settings on equipment designed to use natural gas. Where a natural gas grid exists, it can be readily used to distribute biomethane. The main challenge

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facing biomethane grid injection is cost [113]. Moreover, there is a growing need for balancing gas supply and demand, particularly in low-pressure parts of the network and at times of low demand such as in the summer months [113]. Managing a grid with several many feed-in points will become a greater challenge as the amount of biomethane injected increases. At the same time, the storage capacity of the gas grid offers great potential to absorb fluctuations in power production from renewable energy sources such as wind and solar [113].

4.1. Non-farming applications

Traditionally, biogas has been used as fuel for boilers to produce heat or for cogeneration of heat and electrical power in combined heat and power (CHP) generation plants where electricity is generated by burning fuel (natural gas or biogas) and then a heat recovery unit is used to capture heat from the combustion system’s exhaust stream. This heat can be converted into useful thermal energy, usually in the form of steam or hot water [114]. These CHP systems are normally provided with a four-stroke engine or a diesel engine. Biogas can also be used in a boiler to produce steam for driving engines or turbines; examples include the organic Rankine cycle (ORC), the Cheng cycle, the steam turbine, the steam piston engine and/or the steam screw engine [114]. Biogas properties will have a significant impact on the selection of technology for conversion to heat and/or electricity. In general, the biogas composition and production rate are influenced by the type of digestion process and feedstock used [114]. Fig. A6. 7 provides an overview of the heat and/or power generation applications of biogas. Working principles and schematics of the corresponding systems can be found in [114].

Fig. A6. 7. Use of biogas for various stationary applications (S-removal: removal of sulphur compounds).

Biomethane is a high-quality energy carrier, fully miscible and interchangeable from a combustion point-of-view with its fossil counterpart, natural gas [115]. This is the main advantage of biomethane over other biofuels. Moreover, biomethane offers an opportunity to make the natural gas vehicle (NGV) market green, while forming a virtual gas grid in areas where an extensive gas grid does not exist. Fig. A6. 8 (reproduced from [115]) shows compressed natural gas mobile units are handled with hook lift trucks, forming a virtual grid supply for refuelling stations far from the natural gas grid or biomethane production plants in courtesy of FordonsGasSverige AB. And J. Murphy.

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Fig. A6. 8. (a) Natural gas mobile units and (b) refuelling stations for biomethane.

4.3. Farm Applications

There is great synergy for the implementation of biogas and biomethane plants in the agriculture sector. In addition to economic benefits from energy and fuel generation, anaerobic digestion plants provide additional environmental benefits such as reducing the use of chemical fertilizers in farms, nutrient runoff and methane emissions [116]. Traditionally, manure is directly used as fertiliser in agriculture, which could cause environmental problems, water contamination and pollution. Moreover, natural degradation of manure leads to the emission of methane and carbon dioxide. Anaerobic digestion contributes to mitigate odours associated with manure storage and decomposition and removes pathogens that can pose risk to human and animal health. Digestate from biogas production can still be used as fertiliser, just like manure, having the same content of nutrients as manure. Fig. A6. 9 presents the layouts and energy flows of two example biogas plants from farms in Germany [117].

Fig. A6. 9. Continue

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Fig. A6. 9. Small biogas plants in Germany with aim of (a) minimum investment cost and (b) treating a large share of solid substrates from organic farming.

4.4. Biogas in Europe

Within the EU, biogas production varies greatly in terms of both capacity and source. As of 2015, the leading countries in the biogas production in the EU were Germany, UK, Italy, Czech Republic and France. Germany is the European leader with a biogas production of 329 PJ and a share of 50% of total biogas production. The appendix provides detailed information about biogas production in Europe. Latest data show that the number of biomethane plants in Europe has increased by more than 50% in only 2 years [118]. Germany has the highest share of biomethane plants (232), followed by France (131) and the UK (80) [118]. See Fig. A6. 10. It is estimated that, continuing the current trajectory, Europe's biogas and biomethane sectors combined can almost double their production by 2030 and more than quadruple by 2050 [118]. The estimated potential is in the 34 - 42 billion m³ (equivalent to 370 - 467 TWh) range by 2030 and up to 95 billion m³ (1,008 - 1,020 TWh) by 2050 [118].

Fig. A6. 10. The number of biogas plants in Europe.

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Europe’s biogas comes from a wide range of diverse feedstocks: agricultural residues (livestock manure, crop residues and energy crops), industrial residues from food and beverage industry, biowaste and municipal organic waste, sewage sludge, etc. The use of energy crops (grasses, silage maize, etc.) for biogas production has increased significantly, especially in Germany, in the past two decades due to high biogas yields and favourable support schemes. As shown in Fig. A6. 11, agricultural residues are also a major source of the feedstock in many European countries [119].

Fig. A6. 11. Feedstock use in biogas plants in Europe.

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Appendix 7: Hydrogen

1. Hydrogen application in Livestock/Agricultural

Livestock and agricultural facilities can have significant power consumption in the form of electricity from the grid and fossil fuels for climate control, irrigation, machinery etc. Renewable energy sources such as photovoltaic cells, wind turbines and geothermal plants have been steadily gaining popularity over the recent years since they can lower the operational costs for energy and help meet the national/European environmental goals for carbon neutrality.

It is thus clear that energy self-sufficiency is a desired outcome from both an economical and an ecological perspective, especially for these types of facilities that are often located in rural and natural areas with limited accessibility, where the cost and environmental impact of power line installation and resource transportation can be significantly higher. Nonetheless, the intermittent power production from RES and the variable energy demands from such facilities can pose several challenges [120].

The design and sizing of the renewable energy system requires a careful consideration of the power generation potential and the local energy demand, which includes the difficulties derived from the inherently different daily and seasonal profiles of energy consumption and demand. To achieve the goal of energy self-sufficiency, a considerable energy production surplus is usually required even if smart energy management algorithms are implemented. Energy storage systems, usually in the form of batteries, are often installed to mitigate these problems. This results in a stable supply, which can meet the demand independently of the instantaneous production of energy.

Nonetheless, batteries are only usable for short term storage (a few days) due to technical and economic limitations. Hydrogen production, storage, and usage can be a viable, eco-friendly alternative to batteries for long-term energy storage. In this case, hydrogen molecules act as an intermittent energy carrier, helping to bridge the gap between the times of energy generation from RES and consumption at the facility, respectively. Power generation from RES can have a strong seasonal variation due to the climate, and the demand for energy can also have a seasonal profile for the same reason. Therefore, hydrogen tanks can act as an adequately sized energy reserve for the most unfavourable period, and as a long-term energy storage system during the period of considerable energy surplus.

Nonetheless, hydrogen technologies are far less developed than battery-based alternatives and commercially available solutions are not particularly common. Additional research through pilot units, along with governmental support and subsidies might be a necessity for the successful implementation of hydrogen technologies in such a context, until market is achieved. However, the possibility of hydrogen leakage should be highly attached attention.

2. Hydrogen Production

In the context of a livestock/agricultural facility, hydrogen can be produced either from surplus RES power through electrolysis, or from biomass through gasification.

Electrolysis: Hydrogen production through electrolysis requires a system consisting of a water purifier, an electrolyser, a compressor, and storage tanks [121]. Due to the possibility of an explosive failure,

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the system must be enclosed in a suitable space that follows the ant-explosion regulations (ATEX) and be continuously monitored for temperature and hydrogen leaks [122].

In the electrolyzing reaction, water is fed into the electrolyser and electricity is applied to the electrodes, causing the water to split into hydrogen and oxygen. The electrolyser can either use an alkaline water solution or a proton exchange membrane fuel cell, which can also operate in reverse to convert stored hydrogen to electricity. Most commercially available electrolysers for industrial applications operate at an efficiency of approximately 80% [123]. The hydrogen produced through electrolysis is subsequently compressed and stored in composite material vessels specifically designed for pressurised/liquified hydrogen storage. An example of a green hydrogen production unit has been installed in a winery in Spain, as shown in Fig. A7. 1.

Fig. A7. 1. (a) Flow chart and (b) photograph of the green hydrogen production unit installed at the pilot unit placed at the Vinas del Vero winery, at the Somontano region, north of Aragon (Spain).

Biomass: It is possible to produce hydrogen from agricultural/livestock waste through processes based on biomass gasification. A biomass to hydrogen conversion efficiency of up to 69% has been reported in literature [124]. Gasification is the thermochemical conversion of a carbonaceous solid fuel into a product gas in the presence of a specific gasification agent [123]. The main difference between the

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existing gasification technologies is the gasification agent being used and the way heat is supplied, which is necessary because of the endothermic gasification reactions. This heat can either be added externally or generated internally by the full combustion of some biomass. These processes can also differ significantly regarding the reactor design, which distinguishes between fixed bed, fluidized bed, and entrained flow reactors and the used gasification agent. Adding steam as a gasification agent is the most common practice, not only due to the stoichiometric effect, but also for temperature moderation within the reactor [125,126].

Hydrogen production through gasification generally requires the following steps:

- Evaporation of moisture at temperatures up to 150 °C
- Pyrolysis, therefore releasing of volatiles (H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄, tar, etc.) between 200 and 650 °C
- Reaction of volatiles in the gas phase between 700 and 1000 °C
- Heterogeneous reaction of char between 700 and 1000 °C

After completing the steps of product gas upgrading and hydrogen separation (Fig. A7. 2), a hydrogen stream with a purity of as high as 99.97% can be produced.

Fig. A7. 2. Flow chart of the general process layout for hydrogen production via gasification.

An example of hydrogen production through biomass gasification was installed and tested in the U.S., at the Thermal and Catalytic Process Development Unit for Gasification (TCPDU) of the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) [127], as shown in Fig. A7. 3.

Fig. A7. 3. Facility for Hydrogen production through biomass gasification.

3. Hydrogen Applications

The energy stored in the form of hydrogen can be converted back to electricity by feeding the hydrogen gas to fuel cells. The most common technology employed for small scale facilities is the Proton

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Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC), as shown in Fig. A7. 4 [128]. In this type of fuel cell, Hydrogen is fed into the anode of the fuel cell and air into the cathode. A catalyst embedded in the anode strips ionises the hydrogen atoms and the resulting protons migrate through the electrolyte to the cathode, while the free electrons are diverted to an external circuit where they create a continuous electrical current (DC) on their way to the cathode. At the fuel cell cathode, they reunite with the protons and oxygen from the atmospheric air to produce clean water. Heat is also a by-product of this reaction [129]. All the products of the fuel cell operation (electricity, heat and clean water) can be utilised at a livestock farm or any agricultural facility in general.

Fig. A7. 4. Flowchart of the principle of operation and the schematic of a PEM Fuel Cell.

The fuel cells can either be permanently installed at a facility as a stack part, providing electricity to the installation, or on vehicles powered by electrical motors (fuel cell vehicles) [130]. The potential of using hydrogen fuels for agricultural applications was recently demonstrated by a series of fuel-cell powered tractor that also make use of mobile communications, resulting in agricultural machinery that can either be used in self-driving mode or be remotely controlled (Fig. A7. 5) [131].

Fig. A7. 5. Concept of a Hydrogen Fuel Cell powered tractor (Valtra H202).

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Another method for using the stored hydrogen is by feeding it to a suitably designed internal combustion engine. This engine can either be coupled to an electrical generator to power the installation, or it can be mounted on a vehicle (Hydrogen internal combustion engine vehicle-HICEV). A HICE can either come in the form of a modified gasoline engine, or as a microturbine (Fig. A7. 6 [132,133]). An obvious advantage of this type of engine is that the combustion of hydrogen with oxygen produces water vapour as its only product, therefore their carbon footprint is zero. Nonetheless, due to the high temperatures achieved by hydrogen combustion, oxides of nitrogen, known as NO_x, are also produced. As a result, hydrogen combustion engines are not considered zero emission.

Fig. A7. 6. (a) A hydrogen fuelled piston engine and (b) a hydrogen microturbine.

The efficiency of any HICE is, by definition, lower than that of a fuel cell-electric motor combination, but the cost once technology maturity has been achieved can be lower. Hydrogen combustion engines are particularly sensitive to transience in load, in terms of efficiency, and therefore more suited to constant load operations [134].

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Appendix 8: Geothermal Energy

1. Technical description

1.1. Working Principle

Geothermal energy technologies consider all technologies that use the soil for energetic applications. In general, a distinction is made between **shallow and deep geothermal systems**. Deep systems make use of the rising soil temperature at greater depths (> 500 m). Shallow systems make use of the natural and constant temperature at a depth between 10 and 150 m. This temperature fluctuates between 5°C in the extreme north to 20°C in the extreme south of Europe. Every hundred meters deeper means a temperature increase of average 2 to 3 K. In some European regions the thermal gradient can be substantially higher (Iceland, Italy, France, and etc.). The aim of deep geothermal applications is to extract high-temperature heat (>120°C) at great depths for electricity production (high-enthalpic applications) or medium-temperature heat (<120°C) for direct heating (low-enthalpic applications).

1.2. Classification

Shallow systems (limited to a depth of 150 - 250 m) can be further divided into different categories. There are the heat extraction systems on the one hand, the energy storage systems on the other and finally Earth-to-Air Heat Exchangers (EAHE), also known as Canadian Wells (Fig. A8. 1).

Fig. A8. 1. Schematic of Canadian Wells.

With heat extraction, the natural and constant temperature of the soil is used for heating. The ground-coupled heat pump systems that extract heat from the ground are best known. A heat pump transfers the heat from a lower (5 – 15 °C) to a higher (35 - 45 °C) temperature level. This is done at a high efficiency; the heat supply is on average 4 times the electricity consumption of the heat pump. Heat extraction can be done using available groundwater (open system) or via vertical or horizontal loops (closed systems). These are the options for ground-coupled heat pumps. With energy storage, thermal energy is stored seasonally with the intention of recovering this energy at the desired moment. The soil offers opportunities to store the winter cold for use in the summer and to recover summer heat in

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the winter. The geothermal system acts as a kind of gigantic underground buffer. Energy storage uses the same basic technologies as for heat extraction but makes better use of the storage capacity of the subsurface (creating an Underground Thermal Energy Storage or UTES system). The use of groundwater results in **Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (ATES)**, the use of vertical heat exchangers leads to **Borehole Thermal Energy Storage (BTES)**. When using Canadian Wells, a concrete or plastic (sewerage) pipe is placed in the ground at a depth of a few meters (horizontal). This system is typically linked to the ventilation system of a building for the purpose of pre-heating the cold outside air in the winter period and pre-cooling the ventilation air in the summer. All horizontal systems (with air or water) cannot be used as a storage system. Due to the shallow depth in which they are located and the less compact activation of the soil, there is a significant natural discharge of introduced cold or heat.

When applying on a medium to large scale, such as in the applications in RES4LIVE, an energy storage system (ATES or BTES) should be considered in the first instance. Systems that only extract heat or cold risk becoming saturated when used on a large scale because the possibilities for natural soil regeneration have limits. The possibilities of Canadian Wells can be described as limited (only for small integrated ventilation applications < 10 kW). Also, deep geothermal systems are not considered in this overview, they are only useful at very big applications (> 5 MW).

For the construction of geothermal, it is best to use local drilling companies, they have best knowledge of the specific geological conditions at local project sites.

1.2.1. Electrical and/or thermal power output

A shallow geothermal application is typically constructed at a depth of 50 to 200 m. The temperature of the sediments during thermal activation is 5 to 25 °C. Of course, this only implies the possibility of thermal application of shallow geothermal energy, no electrical output can be achieved.

In a closed geothermal system (BTES), the achievable thermal power is on average 3.5 kW (between 2.5 - 5 kW) per borehole of 100 m depth. By bringing several boreholes together in a circuit, large power capacity can be achieved. With BTES, the power is therefore determined by the number of borehole meters, in combination with the thermal conductivity of the subsoil (type of sediment).

In an open-source system (ATES), the thermal power is expressed per doublet, whereby depending on the source capacity (up to 150 m³/h, for example), the power can vary between 10 kW and no less than 1500 kW. Also here, several doublets can be applied in order to increase the thermal output.

1.2.2. Typical sizes

Geothermal installations can be built according to the need, ranging from small residential installations with just one well to hundreds of wells for large applications. For smaller applications, BTES is especially suitable, for large applications both BTES and ATES can be used. ATES systems are only cost-effective from a thermal capacity of 75 to 100 kW, because of the minimal investment cost required for a high-quality construction.

1.3. Mechanical construction

1.3.1. Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (ATES)

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In order to realize Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (or ATEs), shown in Fig. A8. 2, two or more wells are drilled in an aquifer at a mutual distance of 20 to 200 meters. The depth of the wells is typically 50 to 150 m. Too shallow wells can cause problems with clogging as groundwater can be oxygenated, too deep wells are too expensive and not cost effective.

Fig. A8. 2. Schematic of Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (ATES).

In typical summer situation, when there is a demand for cooling, cold groundwater is pumped from one of the wells and the cold is delivered to the stables or all relevant livestock buildings using a separation heat exchanger. The cold is extracted from the pumped groundwater, so that this water is heated. The heated groundwater is injected into a second well, thereby called the warm well. In winter, when there is a need for heat, the stored warm groundwater is pumped from the warm well(s). The heat is delivered to the buildings using the same heat exchanger (usually with a heat pump in heating mode). The groundwater cools down as a result of this release of heat and is injected back into the second well, called the cold well. Groundwater is used, not consumed, and this means that valuable groundwater remains available for high-quality applications in the future. It is stored here until there is a need for cooling again the following summer. The extracted groundwater is injected again and again, so that no groundwater is consumed. In an ATEs system, both the stored cold and the stored heat can be valorised. There is one major drawback to the ATEs technology, namely a suitable aquifer is not available everywhere. Furthermore, it is important to emphasize that a high-quality ATEs installation requires a minimal investment so that it is not suitable for installations smaller than 100 kW.

An alternative to ATEs for year-round cooling is Cold Storage/Recirculation (CS/R). The difference is that with cold storage/recirculation, the groundwater flows in one direction throughout the year. This variant therefore consists of one extraction and one infiltration well. In summer, when there is a need for cooling, the naturally cold groundwater (approx. 10 – 15 °C) is withdrawn from the extraction well and, after heating as a result of the cooling process, is injected into the infiltration well at an increased temperature. If we continue this process year after year, we will thermally pollute the subsurface. After some time, the extraction well would start to heat up. To prevent this, the underground is cooled

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below the natural soil temperature in winter. For this purpose, groundwater is cooled by means of a cooling tower, or a dry cooler, or an air handling unit, or with surface water, etc. and injected into the infiltration well. Cold Storage/Recirculation is most commonly used for industrial cooling processes but can also be used for permanent cooling processes in agricultural applications.

Fig. A8. 3. Schematic of Cold Storage/Recirculation.

1.3.2. Borehole Thermal Energy Storage (BTES)

Borehole Thermal Energy Storage (BTES) is a more simple technique with fewer restrictions, it can be applied in every geological structure, shown in Fig. A8. 4.

Fig. A8. 4. Schematic of Borehole Thermal Energy Storage.

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The thermal energy is introduced into the subsurface using a closed hydraulic circuit and a number of vertical heat exchangers. This concerns plastic pipes (HDPE) that are inserted as a loop, vertically, in a 20 to 150 m deep borehole. By installing several exchangers at a short distance from each other, a certain storage volume is created. Heat and/or cold can be injected and extracted from the BTES system in several ways and in different applications when circulating a fluid (typically a water/glycol mixture) through the piping system.

The BTES technology must never lead to the formation of ice or the freezing of the subsoil, this would be a sign of improper design. It is not recommended to circulate the refrigerant of the refrigeration compression cycle through the soil, the toxicity of these substances means a major burden on the environment (no direct expansion in the soil). In some architectural structures, concrete foundation piles are used under the building in areas where the ground is not strong enough to support the building. By installing plastic pipes in the longitudinal direction in these concrete foundation piles, an “energy pile” is created. The medium in the plastic pipes is water or a water/glycol mixture in a certain ratio that ensures energy transfer to the soil.

1.4. Installation and maintenance

Despite the fact that both technologies (ATES / BTES) appear to be similar, the installation is profoundly different. BTES boreholes are relatively small boreholes with a diameter of 12 to 20 cm, in which a vertical loop is installed. The driller tries to make these drillings as quickly as possible in order to realize a maximum number of drilling meters per hour. A typical installation speed is 4 to 8 hours per 100-meter vertical run.

ATES boreholes are more a specialisation with larger boreholes with a diameter between 30 cm and 1 meter. The equipment is highly specialized and complex with as main components: filter tube, casing, seals, well pump, riser, injection valve, temperature, pressure and level measurements and the associated controls.

Furthermore, the maintenance of BTES is relatively limited and simple. With ATES, on the other hand, it is necessary to periodically drain and check the technical components.

1.5. Selection of appropriate type

The choice of technology is determined by the geological conditions and the size and application of the project. For larger projects, ATES is preferable to BTES, but the geological conditions for ATES are often less good than for BTES. BTES can be applied in many (most) geological conditions.

2. Performance

The thermal output of a geothermal installation can vary between one kW and hundred MW. With vertical loops (BTES), one can literally start with one shallow borehole and expand an installation to hundreds or even thousands of boreholes. For smaller installations (< 75 kW) the simplicity and low cost of BTES is often preferred, for larger installations ATES is preferred (if the geological conditions allow it).

2.1. Fuel or electricity use

The geothermal heat is collected by means of a well pump (ATES) or circulation pump (BTES). The required electrical power is 10 to 20 times smaller than the achievable thermal power.

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2.2. Factors affecting performance

A very important advantage of geothermal energy supply concerns the independence of the supply from external factors. Geothermal works day and night, 24 hours a day. The continuity of the geothermal supply is therefore guaranteed at all times.

The application of geothermal systems and concepts must be investigated per climate zone. Fig. A8. 5 shows the average ground temperature between 10 to 150 m deep in Europe. The available average temperature of the subsurface fluctuates greatly from northern to southern Europe, which means that certain concepts are better/less suitable. For example, natural cooling is more difficult to apply in southern European countries when natural ground temperatures $>15^{\circ}\text{C}$ (e.g., in Spain, Italy or Greece).

Fig. A8. 5. Average ground temperature between 10 to 150 m deep in Europe.

2.3. Efficiency

Collecting the geothermal heat/cold is possible by using submersible pumps (at ATES) or circulation pumps (at BTES). The efficiency of the supplied geothermal energy depends on the technology (ATES/BTES), the drilling depth (BTES), the height of the groundwater level (ATES) and the achievable temperature difference at delivery. One strives for a minimum COP of 10, which can go up to 25 to 30.

When considering the current default primary energy factor (PEF) in EU as 2.5 (each unit of electricity requires an average input of 2.5 units of primary energy), the impact on primary energy use can be calculated. When using a geothermal heat pump, an annual average COP of 4.5 is achievable in combination with BTES and 5.5 with ATES as the source. This gives primary energy savings of 45% (with BTES) to 55% (with ATES). With direct use, the savings can be up to 80 to 85%.

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Geothermal energy systems can be used for all livestock applications where there is a need for heating and/or cooling, regardless of the farm type. Of course, a delivery system must be present, but this can take many forms.

2.4. Lifecycle emissions

The emission reduction of the geothermal technology during the life cycle is determined by the efficiency compared to classical technologies (see also previous section).

2.5. Operation strategies

A geothermal installation can function in several ways.

The most important part of the operating strategy concerns the choice of only extracting heat or providing both extraction and injection of heat. Large geothermal installations will be exhausted if only heat extraction is used, smaller installations can count on natural regeneration and can therefore cope with this.

The basic operating mode for an ATES installation concerns the use of the natural temperature of the subsoil for both heating and cooling, whereby the groundwater is always pumped in one direction (CS/R). In this case, the heat and cold stored in the underground will not be used any further. An ATES installation can also be operated in which the pump direction is reversed per season, whereby the stored cold from winter will be used in summer and vice versa.

Unlike ATES, with a BTES such mode will not be possible, the vertical loops will activate the underground and will warm up or cool it down.

Geothermal cooling can be used in various ways, with either passive cooling being pursued or only active cooling. With passive cooling, the geothermal temperature is used directly for the cooling application. With active cooling, only the condenser heat from the chiller will be diverted to the underground.

Finally, a geothermal installation can often also be used to make a match between the availability of heat or cold and the demand for this energy. In the summer there is a lot of solar heat available, but it cannot be used. The geothermal installation is perfectly capable of realizing a long-term, seasonal storage of this heat.

3. Cost

3.1. Installation, operation and maintenance costs

The construction of geothermal systems requires drilling boreholes where a wide variability of geological conditions is encountered. This means that an overview of the cost is subject to large deviations. There can be a price difference per kW of thermal energy that increases with a factor of 10. This is of course a very important difference of this renewable energy source compared to other sustainable sources where target prices are more common. An important distinction must then be made between the two technologies, being ATES and BTES.

BTES installations require rather easy to drill boreholes, in a borehole (15 to 20 cm diameter) a single or double U-loop is placed (or possibly a coaxial tube). These loops are connected to each other via a horizontal piping network and connected to a common collector, from which the energy is transferred

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to the consumer or the heat pump. An indication of the total construction cost can be given, this includes the entire geothermal drilling field (drilling, vertical loops, drilling completion, connection of the loops up to and including the collector). In practice, this is expressed in a cost price per running meter of borehole (regardless of the loop type). This can fluctuate between 25 €/m in excellent drilling conditions to 75 €/m in difficult geological conditions with an average of 35 to 40 €/m. The maintenance cost for a BTES installation is very limited as it has a simple construction without moving parts. The maintenance cost is on average $\leq 1\%$ of the investment cost per year. This involves a few checks on the proper flow of all loops and checking of the glycol content in the loops.

The construction of ATES systems is much more complex and varied. The drilling activities are a more limited part of the entire system. The required number of boreholes strongly depends on the achievable pump capacity for each pair of wells (called doublet), this can be a minimum of 5 m³/h (strict minimum to make sense) but can go up to 150 m³/h or even more. Furthermore, the well equipment is important with at least a submersible pump and injection valve and the necessary accessories to control the groundwater level, the pressure and temperature in the circuit. There is also connecting piping and an extensive technical, indoor installation with separation heat exchanger and fittings. Finally, an electrical and control installation is also part of an ATES system. The construction cost for a fully operational ATES installation is therefore highly dependent on the achievable capacity per doublet. The investment fluctuates according to the Table. A8. 1. Furthermore, the maintenance cost is significantly higher than with closed systems with vertical loops. In many European countries there are more obligations with open-source systems, such as annual water analysis and reporting of transported groundwater volumes. This means that an annual maintenance cost of approx. 2.5% of the investment must be foreseen.

Table A8. 1 Investment of ATES depends on well capacity.

Well capacity (V) [m ³ /h]	Power Range (P) per doublet [kW]	Investment (I) [€/kW]
V \leq 10	P \leq 60 kW	I \geq 1500 €/kW
10 < V < 25	60 < P < 150 kW	1000 < I < 1500 €/kW
25 < V < 50	150 < P < 300 kW	650 < I < 1000 €/kW
50 < V < 75	300 < P < 450 kW	500 < I < 650 €/kW
75 < V < 100	450 < P < 600 kW	400 < I < 500 €/kW
V \geq 100	P \geq 600 kW	I \leq 400 €/kW

3.2. Payback Period

The payback time of a geothermal installation for livestock applications is shortest with low investments (i.e., simple applications) that supply a lot of energy. As a result, there is always an economy of scale for larger applications compared to smaller applications. For example, a direct use application with many running hours will come out best. The best cost-benefits are achieved with large ATES systems in good geological conditions, payback times between 5 – 15 years are possible. For BTES installations, payback times will typically be slightly longer, between 8 – 20 years. The local energy rates have a major influence on the end result, which means that the relationship between gas and electricity prices differs greatly between European countries.

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4. Applications

4.1. Existing farming applications & typical combinations with other technologies

Regardless of the applied geothermal technology (ATES or BTES), different energy concepts can be developed. Below is an overview of some promising concepts, including some that already have applications in livestock.

4.1.1. Heating and cooling concept with heat pump

A first concept is based on the most widely used way of utilizing geothermal energy, mainly known in the buildings sector (offices, apartments, hospitals, residential care etc.).

Within this concept, an installation is realized with a ground-coupled heat pump with the use of “natural cooling” in the summer. In this case, a UTES system (ATES or BTES) is linked to a heat pump, providing heat (at 35 – 45 °C) to the buildings during heating season when extracting heat from the soil. This process leads to a global cooling of the subsurface at the end of the heating season. Provided proper dimensioning, this system can make free use of the stored geothermal cold (without a cooling machine) during the summer. In livestock applications, thermal energy can be brought to the barn/stable using floor heating/cooling or ventilation/air treatment units. The bidirectional use of the geothermal system is important for installations > 25 kW. This ensures sustainable cooling and avoids depletion of the soil through regeneration.

In a variant application of this concept, passive cooling is replaced by active cooling. The heat pump operation can often be reversed, whereby the condenser heat is discharged to the geothermal installation. Due to the efficient removal of heat at a relatively low temperature, the seasonal cooling factor is increased. This concept also offers possibilities to offer simultaneous heating and cooling. For example, stable heating can take place together with cooling of milk tanks. The heat pump can provide both energy flows at the same time. The geothermal installation then functions as a heat sink or heat source to store surpluses or extract shortages.

Although heating of livestock stables is a necessity, stable cooling is not always appreciated. However, it has been proven that better summer comfort has a significant positive impact on the health of the animals and the quality of the animal products.

4.1.2. Heating and cooling concept with direct use

The simplest concept is the direct utilization of geothermal energy (ATES or BTES). By combining an air heat exchanger with a geothermal source, it is possible to condition the incoming barn air. With this system, the heat from the summer period is used for the winter and the cold from the winter period is used for the summer. As a result, there are virtually no temperature fluctuations between day and night or winter and summer. The result is a more constant stable climate, which results in better technical figures and more constant operational management. As a result, a healthier stable climate is created, and this is possible with a lower ventilation flow rate (no extreme air volumes are necessary in the summer to ventilate the stable).

This system can be used with both ATES and BTES. Nevertheless, ATES offers the best possibilities since the natural groundwater temperature (ie 12 °C in Central Europe) can be used at all times. This

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temperature remains constant and is suitable for both heating (warming up cold winter air) and cooling (cooling down hot summer air).

Fig. A8. 6. Photo of geothermal direct use at livestock stable.

4.1.3. Central Solar Heating Plant with Seasonal Storage (CSHPSS)

Another possible concept also has a limited number of applications in the building sector, the so-called Central Solar Heating Plant with Seasonal Storage (CSHPSS). The geothermal installation mainly functions as a seasonal storage medium for the storage of solar heat. In the summer as much heat as possible can be captured via solar panels (classic panels or PVT). All surplus solar heat can be stored in the underground, with the aim of reuse in winter for direct heating or in combination with a heat pump. The geothermal installation functions as long-term storage, short-term storage vessels can optionally be used to store useful heat for a few hours or a maximum of several days.

Fig. A8. 7. Schematic of Central Solar Heating Plant with Seasonal Storage.

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Appendix 9: Heat pump

1. Technical description

1.1. Working principle

Heat pump (HP) refers to a device used for extracting heat from a low temperature surroundings and sending it to high temperature space or system, while operating in a cycle. In other words, heat pump maintains a space or system at temperature higher than temperature of surroundings, while operating in cycle. Heat pump transfers heat from low temperature to high temperature, which is non-spontaneous process, so external work is required for realizing this process according to the Second Law of Thermodynamics. Therefore, the working principle of a heat pump is based on the reversed Carnot cycle, also called refrigeration cycle.

As shown in Fig. A9. 1, the cycle of the heat pump consists of the following four processes for the selected refrigerant:

1-2: Isothermal heat transfer from cold medium to refrigerant (Evaporator)

2-3: Isentropic (Reversible adiabatic) compression

3-4: Isothermal heat rejection (condenser)

4-1: Isentropic Expansion

Fig. A9. 1. Heat pump cycle (left) and typical pressure-enthalpy diagram (right).

A heat pump is not a work producing machine, while its objective is to maintain a body at higher temperature, so its performance cannot be defined using efficiency as in case of heat engine. The performance of heat pump is quantified through a parameter called coefficient of performance (COP). Coefficient of performance is defined by the ratio of desired effect (heating or cooling thermal load) and network done for getting the desired effect. The higher the COP is, the more efficient a heat pump is and the less energy it consumes. Heat pumps do not generate any CO₂; however, they do use electricity to run. At the moment, electricity production generates lots of greenhouse gas emissions due to the burning of fossil fuels. Nowadays however, the heat pump is considered as a RES technology due to its low energy consumption.

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1.2. Classification of the technology

Heat pumps can be broadly classified, depending on their heat source (air, water and geothermal), there are also sub-types of heat pump systems: Hybrid Heat Pump, Solar Heat Pump and Absorption or Gas-Fired Heat Pump (more typical to industrial applications). In terms of installation there are Split Systems, Package Systems, Mini Split or “Ductless” and Window Heat Pumps.

1.3. Mechanical construction

As was described above, the cycle consists of four processes, therefore there are four main components of the cycle, namely the compressor, the expansion valve, the evaporator and the condenser. The components are selected based on the working refrigerant, the system’s specifications and the range of the temperature levels, in order to cover all possible operating conditions. Moreover, extra components are suitably coupled with the main equipment in order to make the total assembly totally functional (such as receiver, filter, solenoid valves, three-way valves, control panel). In general, the design of a heat pump is affected by the heat source (e.g., air, ground, solar), while the components’ dimensions, as well as the heat pump’s overall size, depend on the desired conditions that have to be met. Depending on the application, various types of compressors and heat exchangers are used for heat pump systems.

Moreover, the refrigerant of the heat pump has an important role on the heat pump performance, since its thermodynamic properties affect strongly the components selection and design. Various refrigerants have been employed for heat pumps systems, while the most typical in the previous years’ installations were R134a, R245fa, R404a, R22 etc. Today, special attention has been given on the environmental aspect and the so-called HFO (4th generation) refrigerants are getting more and more space in the market, according to the F-Gas Regulation. The most studied and used HFO refrigerants are R1234ze(E), R1224yd(Z) and R1233zd(E), presenting a low ozone depletion potential (ODP) and ultra-low global warming potential (GWP), while keeping high COP.

Fig. A9. 2. Capacity and applications of different compressor types.

The most critical component of a heat pump is the compressor, since the whole operation depends on the high and low pressure of the cycle. The most common types of compressors used in heat pumps systems are the single-acting reciprocating, scroll and screw, based on the desired power of the

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system. The capacity of the compressor leads to the appropriate selection of compression system. Most of the applications in residential and industrial heat pump systems are designed with scroll and screw compressors for smaller and larger capacities, respectively. Fig. A9. 2 presents the capacity and the application for various types of compressors and their range of operation.

Apart from the compressor, the heat exchangers are also critical for the system operation, while their size is strongly affected by the thermal load that has to be transferred. The two heat exchangers used in HP systems are the condenser and the evaporator. The condenser is used to condense the refrigerant, transferring heat from the hot side (refrigerant) to the cold side (secondary fluid-usually water, air, or another mixture). On the other hand, the evaporator is used to heat the refrigerant, until it is (super) saturated vapor before it enters the compressor. Therefore, for the case of condenser, heat is transferred from the refrigerant to the surroundings, while for the evaporator occurs the opposite. This is the reason, that for the cooling of a room, the evaporator is placed in the space (heat is transferred from the room-air to the refrigerant), while the condenser is placed outside (heat is transferred from the refrigerant to the ambient). There are various types of heat exchangers, but the most common in heat pump systems are the plate heat exchangers (PHX) and the plate-fin heat exchangers (Fig. A9. 3), due to their low cost, compactness, and duration to the operating pressure ranges.

Fig. A9. 3. Plate heat exchanger (left) and plate-fin heat exchanger (right).

As mentioned above, the condensers are used to cool the refrigerant. The cooling capacity and the space restrictions determine the type of heat exchanger and the cooling circuit that is employed. The simplest cases require an air-cooled condenser, so a plate-fin heat exchanger is employed. In the case that the system requires hot water or high heat transfer rate, then a plate heat exchanger is employed.

Table A9. 1. Types of heat pump's heat exchangers that be employed.

Heat exchangers	Plate heat exchangers Plate-fin heat exchangers
Condensers	Air-cooled (dry or wet cooling) Water-cooled
Evaporators	Depends on the heat source

The evaporator is used to heat the refrigerant, therefore other medium could be used depending on the heat source and the plate heat exchanger is the most common solution. In simpler cases, such as

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residential air-conditioning units, plate-fin heat exchangers are used, for low cost and simplicity of the unit. Table A9. 1 presents the different types of heat exchangers for HP discussed above.

The last main component of a heat pump is the expansion valve. The expansion valve is the pressure reducing device. When the high pressure, and medium temperature refrigerant enters the expansion valve its pressure reduces suddenly and along with it its temperature also becomes very low suddenly. The expansion valve most used in the heat pumps is copper capillary tube. The refrigerant leaves the expansion valve at extremely low pressure and low temperature in partially liquid state and partially gaseous state. The thermostatic expansion valve (TEV) has as main purpose the controlling of the refrigerant's quantity passing through the heat pump system's evaporator before reaching the compressor. The TEV improves the system efficiency, avoids overheating problems, and often reduces the amount of energy a system uses. In more recent years, the electronic expansion valve (EEV) is also employed to control the flow. Fig. A9. 4 presents the configuration of an expansion valve in a HP unit [135].

Fig. A9. 4. Expansion valve configuration in a heat pump.

1.4. Installation and maintenance

The use of heat pumps in livestock buildings is not by any chance as widespread as in residential or other commercial facilities. For that reason, there are no specific data available regarding installation and maintenance guidelines. In both new and retrofitted livestock facilities, engineers, technicians, and farm personnel will have to cooperate in order to reach the best approach for each case. A good quality and well installed air or ground source heat pump system will require relatively little maintenance and annual check by a qualified installer or engineer. The installer/supplier can provide details of each system's exact maintenance requirements, and also how to optimize its performance.

1.5. Selection of appropriate type

Size is a critical factor when considering the selection of a unit or system. By choosing the right size, someone avoids issues such as inflated energy costs, extreme temperature fluctuations, imbalance in indoor humidity, and short cycling of the system. A too small heat pump will be unable to cover the heating/cooling needs, while a too big one will work inefficiently.

Indicative factors to consider when choosing the heat pump's size are the:

- Desired conditions to be achieved

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- Local climate, including the average seasonal high and low temperatures
- Space thermophysical properties, e.g., level of the building's insulation

The selection of appropriate type is heavily depended on each application's needs as well as on limitations in terms of installation and operation.

2. Performance

2.1. Electricity use

By knowing the heat pump's COP and thermal output, it is easy to calculate the electrical power input. For example, a heat pump operating at a COP in the range of 4 - 5, needs 1 kW_{el} as input, in order to produce 4 - 5 kW_{th}. In comparison modern condensing boilers may attain approximately 1.07 kW_{th} out of 1 kWh energy content of the fuel in use.

2.2. Factors affecting performance

2.2.1. Impact of local climate

As was mentioned above, the ambient conditions have an important impact on the heat pump performance and efficiency. The heat that is transferred from the refrigerant to the ambient through a heat exchanger, is strongly affected by the ambient temperature and can drastically deteriorate heat pump's performance. The heat pumps can operate in a more efficient way in the northern countries, where the ambient temperature is less, while more complicated systems such as cascade heat pumps are used in warm climates. Fig. A9. 5 presents the COP variation with the ambient temperature for various refrigerants [136].

Fig. A9. 5. COP variation with the ambient temperature for various refrigerants.

2.2.2. Impact of farm type

The type and size of the animal farm can significantly affect the size of the heat pump, as well as its different functions, such as dehumidification and reheating. Of utmost importance is the kind of hosted animals, as each kind, breed and age have different needs. The energy profile of each farm should be thoroughly studied, considering - at least - the needed temperature (air and water) and humidity.

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2.3. Efficiency

When comparing the performance of heat pumps the term “performance” is preferred to “efficiency”, with Coefficient of performance (COP) being used to describe the ratio of useful heat movement per work input. An electrical resistance heater has a COP of 1.0, which is considerably lower than a well-designed heat pump which will typically be between COP of 3 to 5 with an external temperature of 10°C and an internal temperature of 20°C. A ground-source heat pump will typically have a higher performance than an air-source heat pump. A heat pump cooler operating at a COP of 2.0, removes 2 units of heat for each unit of energy consumed (e.g., an air conditioner consuming 1 kWh would remove 2 kWh of heat from a building's air).

The European standard EN 1451, sets out standardised performance and rating terms for air-conditioning units, heat pumps and liquid chilling packages that supply space heating or cooling. Heat pumps should achieve a certain COP rating, as tested under EN14511: 4.5 (Water/water), 4.0 (Brine/water), 4.0 (Direct evaporation) and 3.0 (Air/water).

Other parameters used to describe the performance of a heat pump are:

- the 'Seasonal Coefficient of Performance' (SCOP), which is a measure of the aggregate energy efficiency measure over a period of one year, which it is very dependent on region climate
- the “Energy Efficiency Ratio” (EER), which a measure of the cooling efficiency of a heat pump at peak load capacity, and Integrated Energy Efficiency Ratio (IEER), that accounts for both full load and part load efficiencies.
- Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio (SEER) that measures the seasonal cooling efficiency of a heat pump or a consumer central air conditioning system, and
- the Heating Season Performance Factor (HSPF), which is a measure of the overall heating efficiency of a heat pump during the season.

A wide deployment of heat pumps will contribute to a reduction of final energy demand and is estimated to have only a small impact on the maximum load on the electricity grid. Fig. A9. 6 presents the advantages of the heat pumps against other heating solutions regarding the efficiency.

Fig. A9. 6. Comparison of final energy demand of different heating systems.

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2.4. Lifecycle emissions

The different processes involved during the heat pump lifetime are presented in Fig. A9. 7 [137]. Emissions are distinguished in direct emissions (chemical) and indirect emissions (energy use) of greenhouse gases from production, transport, operation, and recycling.

Fig. A9. 7. Involved processes during the heat pump lifetime

Fig. A9. 8. Comparison of the lifetime emissions of different heating solutions.

Fig. A9. 8 shows a comparison of the lifetime emissions of different heating solutions. The figure shows that a fast reduction of emissions from electricity has a bigger impact on the life cycle-based emissions of heat pumps, than the deployment of refrigerants with a low GWP. It shows also that even heat pumps with the lowest currently allowed efficiency to have lower emissions than even the best fossil combustion system. From an environmental perspective, already the use of existing refrigerants - if handled properly - contributes to a reduction of greenhouse gas emissions which is accelerated by

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every reduction step of emissions from electricity. From an industry perspective the development of low and no GWP alternatives to be deployed in efficient heat pump systems must be the goal to deploy a near zero emission heating technology- both from the component and the operations side [138].

Fig. A9. 9 presents the comparison of both the heat pump and the boiler systems using the Eco-indicator99 and EPS2000 methodologies [137]. The total impact caused by the heat pump is lower than the one caused by the gas boiler. According to the infrastructure, the heat pump manufacturing impact is bigger than the manufacturing impact of the boiler. This is caused by the bigger amounts of materials and energy required during the heat pump production, thus increasing the required resources, and produced emissions.

Fig. A9. 9. Comparison of heat pump and boiler systems using the Eco-indicator99 and EPS2000 methodologies.

2.5. Scope of circularity

Heat pumps are material intensive products. Thus, a resource efficient, material conscious design and manufacturing is an essential part of cost-efficient production. Heat pump systems are designed, installed, and dismantled by skilled and certified experts, and due to their high material content and their specific dismantling procedure (because of the F-gas regulation content), they are part of existing recycling schemes in Europe [139].

2.6. Stability/Continuity

Today, applications that require reliability, continuity of operation, high performance, reduced management costs and carbon dioxide emissions, can be covered by modern HP units, which are designed to present high performance over a wide range of such applications.

2.7. Operation strategies

The traditional control implemented in commercially available heat pump units is based on the so-called heating curve that provides a static estimation of the required supply temperature to the heating distribution system depending on the ambient temperature. The heating curve control approach can be classified as a non-predictive Rule-Based Control (RBC), that determines all control inputs based on a series of rules such as “if-condition-then-action”, typically involving numerical control parameters and threshold values. A strong point in favour of non-predictive rule-based controls is that the design of rules can be relatively simple, and the controls still show good performances [140], and their implementation does not require a mathematical model. For these reasons, according to some Authors

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this approach is expected to remain the dominant control strategy in the building sector for the next two-three decades [141].

The computational power of electronic device has been increasing in the last decades together with storage and connection capability [141] and there has been a growing interest in the possibility to introduce advanced features in the heat pump system controllers. With the decreased costs of data processing, storage and communication over recent years, the design and implementation of more complex control techniques have become accessible [142], and several studies have been dedicated to the development of advanced system control.

Model based methods, commonly named Model Predictive Controls (MPC), represent a constrained control approach that has been proposed in many areas over the last decades. In principle, MPC approach is based on the formulation of the buildings control as an optimization problem. The aim of the optimization is to minimize the energy consumption while ensuring that all comfort requirements are met. When applied to buildings, Model Predictive Controls employ a model of the building dynamics to predict the future evaluation of the system and solve an optimization problem subjected to a number of constraints, in order to determine the optimal control signals, depending on these predictions.

2.8. Practical Lifetime

Heat pumps can last 10 to 20 years, depending on usage frequency, though 15 is average. Functionally, heat pumps are similar to air conditioners, but because they can provide both heating and cooling, they are typically used longer each year. Heat pumps in coastal areas will also fail prematurely, with typical life spans of seven to 12 years.

There are many things that can reduce the life span of HVAC equipment, including:

- Poor maintenance practices
- Poor initial quality or defective components
- Oversizing or undersizing the system
- Improper installation procedures
- Inordinately high usage or high loads
- Improper usage, such as heating or cooling with windows and doors open
- Installation in salty or corrosive environments, such as coastal areas

Of these, poor maintenance and oversizing are the most detrimental. A lack of maintenance can lead to accelerated component wear and a dramatically shorter life span, while oversizing can cause frequent on-and-off cycling, leading to compressor or blower motor failure.

3. Cost

3.1. Installation, Operation & maintenance costs

In order to increase the share of heat pumps in residential and non-residential applications, policies need to address barriers to adoption, including high upfront purchase prices, operational costs, and

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the legacy of the existing building stock. In many markets, the installed costs for heat pumps relative to potential savings on energy spending (e.g., when switching from a gas boiler to an electric heat pump) often mean that heat pumps may be only marginally less expensive over 10 to 12 years, even with their higher energy performance.

Since 2015, subsidies have proven effective to offset the upfront cost of heat pumps and initiate market dynamics that accelerate their uptake in newly built buildings. Removing this financial support could considerably impede higher heat pump adoption, especially of ground-source heat pumps [143]. The cost factors depend a lot on the respective market framework and differ widely from country to country. This holds true in particular for the cost of equipment and the cost of fuel (often mainly influence by taxation levels). When referring to financial incentives and administration cost, these can differ from region to. The following figure presents the cost parameters such as the investment cost (A1: design cost, A2: administration cost, A3: cost of the product, A4: installation cost, A5: financial advantages based on the investment cost), the operating cost and the cost of refurbishment, exchange or dismantling for a heat pump (Fig. A9. 10) [138].

Fig. A9. 10. Factors affecting the total cost of ownership of a heating system (source: EHPA).

3.2. ROI & Cost savings

The Return on Investment (ROI) for a heat pump depends on a multitude of factors, including: Fuel to be replaced, Heat pump size, Source of heat, Available subsidy programs.

A typical ROI for an Air Source Heat Pump (ASHP) would be around 10 percent with a payback period of around 12 years. Ground Source Heat Pumps (GSHPs) are an attractive option for business and homes with well insulated premises or which is planning renovations, typically presenting at a 12% ROI year on year for the lifespan of the heat pump [144]. Below is an estimated guide to the ROI that could be achieved, based on a business heat consumption of 200,000kWh per year [145]. Fig. A9. 11 presents a rough guide for the estimation of ROI.

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Heat Pump Source	Coefficient of Performance (CoP)	RHI Eligibility/kWh	Total annual savings for 200,000kWh heat demand against oil	Total annual savings for 200,000kWh heat demand against gas
Air Source (100kW)	3	2.79p/kWh	£6,640/year	£3,580/year
Ground Source/Water Source >100kW (100kW)	4	Tier 1 6.98p/kWh Tier 2 2.08p/kWh	£13,217.6/year	£8,598.60
Ground Source/Water Source <100kW (95kW)	4	Tier 1 9.68p/kWh Tier 2 2.89p/kWh	£16,874/year	£12,255.95

*This calculation is based on purchasing electricity at 10p/kWh, gas at 1.5p/kWh and oil at 40p/L

Fig. A9. 11. Estimated guide to the ROI.

Table A9. 2. Financial savings for a heat pump compared to other technologies.

Financial savings for a heat pump replacing a boiler		Financial savings of a heat pump replacing a boiler and air conditioner	
Cost of gas boiler	€2,000	Cost of gas boiler	€2,000
Cost of heat pump	€10,000	Cost of air conditioner	€2,000
Grant for heat pump (30%)	€3,000	Cost of heat pump	€10,000
Price of gas kWh	5 cent	Grant for heat pump (30%)	€3,000
Price of electricity (c/kWh night rate)	7 cent	Price of gas per kWh	5 cent
Heat requirement (kWh)	22,000	Price of electricity per kWh	15 cent
Gas boiler efficiency	85%	Heat requirement kWh	22,000
Gas input (kWh)	25,882	Gas boiler efficiency	85%
Heat Pump COP	4.0	Gas input kWh	25,882
Electricity input (kWh)	5,500	Cooling requirement (kWh)	12,000
Boiler energy costs (25,882 x 0.05)	€1,294	Air conditioning COP	3.0
Heat pump energy costs	€385	A/C electricity input (kWh)	4,000
Heat pump additional costs less SSRH grant	€5,000	Heat pumps COP (heating)	4.0
Heat pump annual heat savings	€989	Heat pumps COP (cooling)	5.0
Simple payback (years)	5.1	Electricity input (kWh) (heating)	5,500
		Electricity input (kWh) (cooling)	2,400
		Boiler energy costs	€1,294
		Air conditioning energy costs (4,000 x 0.15)	€600
		Heat pump energy costs (5,500 x 0.15 + 2,400 x 0.15)	€1,185
		Heat pump additional cost less grant	€3,000
		Heat pump annual saving on heating and cooling	€709
		Simple payback (years)	4.2

When calculating financial viability, the offset cost of an alternative heating system - such as a gas boiler (Table A9. 2) - should also be taken into account. Heat pumps look much more viable where there is a cooling demand, and their capital cost can be spread over the heating and cooling savings, resulting a faster payback [146]. Of course, in the framework of livestock industry interventions, other

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factors- such as reduced medication, feed consumption, mortality, and quality enhancement - could also be considered [147,148].

3.3. Funding possibilities

Heat pump is a commercially mature RES technology, eligible for all European Incentive and subsidy programs⁷, initiated in the framework of Directive 2009/28/EC⁸. This technology is supported mainly through investments grants and tax exemption schemes [149], and Fig. A9. 12 illustrates the main schemes in place in the EU countries to support its deployment. Because of the - still - high purchase and installation cost of heat pumps, these schemes are crucial for their wider adoption.

So far, most of energy saving schemes concern residential facilities [150], and it seems that there is no subsidy scheme dedicated to agriculture. Recent actions though, such as UK Government’s innovative Non-Domestic Renewable Heat Incentive [151], could benefit SMEs of agricultural sector towards the transition to green energy.

Fig. A9. 12. Funding possibilities in Europe.

The examples from other European countries show us this strategy works. For instance, France and Germany have set up extensive and widely popular oil boiler replacement schemes. In addition, Italy launched its ‘Superbonus’ to promote heat pumps thanks to a 110% payback credit.

3.4. List of brands and suppliers

There is a plenty of suppliers for each main component of the unit, providing the suitable equipment for each application. A completed design of a heat pump is presented in Fig. A9. 13, as a 3D design that

⁷ General info about EU subsidy programs can be found in <http://www.res-legal.eu/home/> and https://ec.europa.eu/energy/topics/renewable-energy/national-renewable-energy-action-plans-2020_en

⁸ Directive (EU) 2018/2001 repeals Directive 2009/28/EC on 1 July 2021

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was manufactured by PSYCTOTHERM. The Figure presents all the main components of the unit, established in an integrated heat pump system. PSYCTOTHERM is manufacturer of the air-cooled heat exchangers and also specialises in the establishment and commissioning of the whole system. On the other hand, there are many suppliers of the completed heat pump system. However, these systems are standardized for specific power required usually for residential applications (for example 9000 BTU/hr, 12000 BTU/hr, etc.), and it is difficult to apply for specialized applications.

Fig. A9. 13. Industrial heat pump with the components.

The following Table A9. 3 includes the most significant suppliers of the main heat pump’s components (heat exchangers, compressors, expansion valves), but also integrated heat pump systems.

Table A9. 3. Heat pump's components and integrated heat pump systems suppliers.

Components	Suppliers
Heat exchangers	SWEP, Alfa Laval, Kaori
Compressors	Bitzer, Frigopol, Hanbell, Copeland, Panasonic, Daikin
Expansion valves	Danfoss, Parker Sporlan, Alco Controls
Integrated heat pump system	Daikin, Mitsubishi, AHI Carrier, Gree, Trane, Toshiba

4. Applications

4.1. Existing farming & non-farming applications

Heat pumps continue to meet only a small share of residential heat demand (around 5% in 2019), while fossil fuel-based and conventional electric technologies made up three-quarters of sales globally in 2019. The EU market is expanding quickly, with around 1.3 million households purchasing a heat pump in 2018 (12% annual average growth since 2015). France, Italy and Spain are responsible for half of all sales in the European Union, while Sweden, Estonia, Finland and Norway have the highest penetration rates, with more than 25 heat pumps sold per 1,000 households each year [143]. However, progress is still needed across the globe to boost uptake in existing buildings.

The heat pump’s penetration in non-residential applications - and consequently in agriculture - is relatively small, as depicted in Fig. A9. 14 [152]:

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	New building	Renovation
Non-residential (commercial)	Minority share in currently sold heat pumps. Several demonstration projects available, potential for heating and cooling projects by far not exploited. Industrial heat pumps a small yet promising application.	Increasingly important with investors that value low operating cost. Special application in sewage systems, subways and tunnels.

Fig. A9. 14. Non-residential applications of heat pumps.

The use of heat pumps in agri-food sector and drying industry has a long history [153] and has been studied in the last decades, mainly for drying of agricultural materials [154], [155]. Heat pumps have long been widely recognised as energy-efficient heating and cooling systems and have been proposed for greenhouse heating since the early 1970's. However, due to their low COP and high cost of installation, they were not reconsidered as an alternative heating system until the rise of energy costs and their technical advancement [156]. The last decade, there is increased interest for installation of heat pumps in both experimental [157] and conventional greenhouses [156], [158].

In livestock sector, dairy-related energy saving applications include milk cooling and water heating on farms for cleaning of tools and equipment [159], [159], but also off-farm pasteurization [160]. Exclusive on-farm applications, especially in confined poultry and pig building, are also present in bibliography. Heat recovery applications has been theoretically investigated during the last decades [161], [162] in pig farm facilities, and also the use of Ground Source Heat Pump (GSHP) has been tested [163]. In the case broiler houses, work has been done on modelling different systems, such as HVAC systems for precise environment control [164] in Greece, and ground-coupled heating/cooling system for typical chicken farm in Syria [165]. The coupling of PVT/heat pump system has also been experimentally investigated [166] and monitored [167]. It is evident that in the scientific community, there is strong towards applications where the heat pumps also coupled with geothermal energy and PV/Ts that especially in poultry and pig facilities (confined animal buildings).

Also, during the last years, private companies active in the field of agriculture and RES, have proceeded to the installation of heat pumps in commercial livestock facilities. IEC Heat Solutions has installed several GSHPs for heating broiler houses across the UK⁹. Inno+ BV has also use - among other technologies - heat pumps for improving indoor climate of poultry (eggs and broilers)¹⁰ and pig farms in The Netherlands¹¹. The general approach was to recover heat from air scrubbers, to exploit heat from adult animals to warm the young one and use excess heat for other functions (feed fermentation). Though still in its infancy, the integration of heat pumps in - both new and retrofitted - livestock buildings are welcomed by the stakeholders as a viable solution, environmentally and economically.

⁹ <https://www.iecsolutions.co.uk/heat-solutions/projects/>

¹⁰ <https://inno-plussystems.com/en/the-most-innovative-climate-and-energy-system-in-the-world/>

¹¹ <https://inno-plussystems.com/en/best-piglet-house-in-the-world-according-to-climate-specialist/>

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4.2. Potential farming applications

4.2.1. Pilot (experimental) farm in Belgium (swine)

The farm “Varkenscampus” operates for research and educational purposes alongside a normal commercial production. It is a farrow-to-finish pig farm with place at any moment for 105 sows, 600 piglets and 750 fattening pigs, and a total building area of ~2,500 m². Heating is provided year-round by a 60-kW gas heater with a fossil gas consumption of ~220 MWh/year. The mechanical ventilation system and heating system are steered through temperature sensors in each room. Heat is delivered through a multitude of delivery systems depending on the need and the stage of production.

Within RES4LIVE, two modular heat pumps of 30 kW each will be used to provide the heating at different temperature levels and cooling if necessary. Moreover, PVT collectors will be installed, with their heating production provided directly to the farm during summer, while during winter to assist the heat pump and lifts its COP (“solar-assisted” mode), with the possibility to use few PV panels to fix the heat-to-electricity ratio. On an annual basis, the PV electricity will be more than the heat pump consumption, with the excess reducing the electricity from the grid. The smart energy control will be installed to manage the energy flows and matching the PV production with the heat pump consumption. The overall outcome is the 100% replacement of fossil fuel – gas (220,000 kWh/year) with renewable energy plus electricity demand.

4.2.2. Pilot (commercial) farm in Italy (swine)

Golinelli pig farm is located in Modena province of northern Italy and it rears 500 sows and 2,500 sucklings. The farm consists of a farrowing barn, a nursery barn, a gestation barn, and a hog barn with gestation sector.

To eliminate the fossil gas consumption of a 34-kW LPG boiler of the nursery barn (about 7,500 kg/year), a 35-kW heat pump will be installed for the nursery barn. Additionally, a PVT system of approx.104 kW_{th} and 20.8 kW_{el} will be installed to provide electricity for the heat pump operation and the electric needs of the nursery barn, and thermal energy. The latter will be exploited through a ground heat storage with vertical boreholes of coaxial types of max. 10 m depth with the geothermal controller, thus increasing the heat pump efficiency by over 20%. A smart control system with sensors will be also installed for indoor environment and energy management. The project will lead to the replacement of 100% of electricity and 100% of LPG consumption for the nursery barn with RES and efficiency measures, thus saving a total of 29,350 kg CO₂/year.

4.2.3. Pilot (experimental) farm in Greece (poultry)

This farm occupies an area of 90 m², (two rooms of 45 m² each for growing hens and eggs production) hosting 400 animals and located within the Agricultural University of Athens campus. There is no heating/ cooling system (no fuel consumption), while relying on forced ventilation for removing the thermal loads during summer. Its electricity consumption is currently ~2,500 kWh/year mostly consumed for ventilation and lighting.

For enhancing the thermal comfort, a heat pump with capacity of 10 kW will be installed. Moreover, to eliminate the electricity consumption (including the heat pump), standard PV panels of 8 kW_p will be installed on the rooftop, as well as inverter-driven motors of the ventilators. A smart control system will be installed to manage the: (1) indoor environment for keeping the temperature and humidity

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within the thermal comfort zone, (2) regulation of the ventilator fans speed, and (3) PV power production for maximising the self-consumption.

4.3. Status of Implementation in Europe

According to EurObserv'ER's Heat Pump Barometer report¹², about 3.9 million HPs were sold during 2019, all capacities and technologies taken together, which amounts to 12.6% annual growth (3.5 million units sold in 2018). The market data, leaving aside the UK¹³, is given in Table A9. 4. These figures are representative of the residential and service sector markets, that cover a power range extending from a few kW to more than 20 kW). The medium- and high-capacity HP market is much smaller, as fewer than one thousand industrial and heating network HPs are sold in the EU.

Table A9. 4. Heat pump's components and integrated heat pump systems suppliers.

*Total number of heat pumps in operation in 2018 and 2019 in the European Union**

	2018			2019		
	Aerothermal heat pumps	Ground source heat pump	Total PAC	Aerothermal heat pumps	Ground source heat pump	Total PAC
Italy	19 569 000	14 150	19 583 150	19 600 000	14 100	19 614 100
France	6 178 756	157 950	6 336 706	6 994 156	161 250	7 155 406
Spain	3 711 035	10 595	3 721 630	4 157 961	10 793	4 168 754
Sweden	1 261 328	537 878	1 799 206	1 349 857	551 776	1 901 633
Portugal	1 536 059	909	1 536 968	1 610 677	909	1 611 586
Germany	684 439	376 902	1 061 341	762 336	392 784	1 155 120
Finland	751 242	118 976	870 218	836 620	127 964	964 584
Netherlands	509 650	60 379	570 029	660 806	71 065	731 871
Denmark	332 520	65 149	397 669	380 995	68 997	449 992
Malta	361 944	0	361 944	425 237	0	425 237
Belgium	218 535	13 209	231 744	321 593	15 804	337 397
United Kingdom	173 727	33 851	207 578	201 946	36 877	238 823
Austria	108 059	106 843	214 902	126 246	109 695	235 941
Bulgaria	214 971	4 272	219 243	214 971	4 272	219 243
Estonia	146 737	15 875	162 612	161 747	17 625	179 372
Czechia	123 327	25 005	148 332	150 440	26 316	176 756
Poland	81 636	53 486	135 122	112 950	60 196	173 146
Slovakia	45 993	3 815	49 808	94 586	3 964	98 550
Slovenia	31 100	10 648	41 748	34 300	10 648	44 948
Ireland	22 398	4 406	26 804	36 436	4 722	41 158
Hungary	9 950	2 410	12 360	12 800	2 745	15 545
Lithuania	3 466	3 268	6 734	4 145	3 311	7 456
Greece	1 270	3 129	4 399	1 403	3 700	5 103
Luxembourg	1 628	742	2 370	1 834	831	2 665
Total EU 28	36 078 770	1 623 847	37 702 617	38 254 042	1 700 344	39 954 386
Total EU 27 (after January 31, 2020)	35 905 043	1 589 996	37 495 039	38 052 096	1 663 467	39 715 563

* Estimate. Note: Datas from Italian, French and Portuguese aerothermal heat pump market are not directly comparable to others, because they include the heat pumps whose principal function is cooling. Only heat pumps that meet the efficiency criteria (seasonal performance factor) defined by Directive 2009/28/EC are taken into account. Source: EurObserv'ER 2020.

The European Union installed HP base to date at about 40.0 million units (38.3 million ASHPs and 1.7 million GSHPs). This figure is not restricted to heating uses, but covers both cooling and heating uses, for systems whose performance factors meet the Renewable Energy Directive criteria¹⁴. The 2020 report argues though that putting a figure on the number of HPs in service is a tricky exercise that is contingent on the decommissioning assumptions adopted for each county and the availability of statistics supplied by the Member States or HP industry associations.

4.4. Best practices/ typical combinations with other technologies

Heat pumps can be combined with heat from other RES in hybrid systems. These sources might be renewable in origin or waste energy from industrial processes and exhaust air from buildings. Heat

¹² <https://www.eurobserv-er.org/heat-pumps-barometer-2020/>

¹³ UK officially left the European Union on 1 January 2020

¹⁴ Heat pumps that do not meet these criteria have not been included.

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pumps can be highly efficient, although their overall primary energy efficiency depends on the efficiency of the electricity production (or other thermal energy source) they use. The most usual heat sources are the ambient air source and the ground (Fig. A9. 15). Moreover, the heat pumps can be combined with photovoltaic systems or other waste heat sources (WHR), which can provide heat to the heat pump's evaporator.

Fig. A9. 15. Air-source (left) and ground-source (right) heat pump.

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Appendix 10: Combined heat power

1. Technical description

1.1. Working principle

The production of electricity is an inefficient process. Although some plants achieve energy conversion efficiencies of 60%, most operate closer to 30% and even less [168]. In the last decades, great improvements are made regarding the energy efficiency of power generation, however, still between 40% and 70% of the primary energy is wasted as unexploited heat.

Combined Heat and Power (CHP) is an energy efficient technology consisting of a conventional power generation unit (PGU) and a heat recovery unit. The heat recovery system recovers a substantial amount of heat that would otherwise be wasted, tackling the low energy efficiency of separate generation of heat and power. In this way, the overall energy efficiency of a power generating system can be increased from 30 - 60% up to 85%, by utilizing the waste heat. As electricity and thermal energy are generated in a single integrated system, CHP is often called cogeneration (cogen). Energy demands exceeding the thermal or electrical power delivered by the CHP plant can be bridged by respectively auxiliary boilers and the local grid. An illustration of a typical CHP layout can be found in Fig. A10. 1.

Fig. A10. 1. Overview of a typical CHP architecture.

Fig. A10. 2. Energetic comparison of separate generation of electricity and heat with CHP.

A theoretical evaluation indicating the difference in primary energy consumption between the traditional (separate) generation and a typical CHP system is illustrated in Fig. A10. 2. In this example a consumer needs 35 units of electricity and 50 units of heat. If heat and electricity would be generated

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separately, with a power plant operating at an efficiency of 55% and a boiler with an efficiency of 90%, 120 units of primary energy (i.e. fuel) are used. A CHP plant, operating at an electrical efficiency of 35% and a thermal efficiency of 50% however will only use 100 units of primary energy, reducing the fuel consumption by 17%.

Generally, CHP-systems allow for a substantial potential of increasing the energy efficiency and reducing the environmental impact compared to the separate production of heat and power. Furthermore, CHP systems offer increased reliability and less grid dependency, avoiding transmission, distribution and transformation losses and ensuring security of supply.

1.2. Classification

CHP units are typically classified according to their prime mover, being the power generation unit. Depending on the applications different types of prime movers can be used.

1.1.1. Reciprocating internal combustion engines

A reciprocating internal combustion engine (ICE) is a heat engine, combusting fuel with an oxidizer (typically air), converting high temperature and high-pressure gasses into a rotary motion by use of one or multiple pistons. Reciprocating engines include both spark ignition (SI) and compression ignition (CI) engines. SI engines are commonly operated with natural gas, although biogas, propane, gasoline and landfill gas are also used [169,170]. CI engines on the other hand typically operate on diesel fuel or heavy oil and biodiesel. Typical waste heat sources of ICEs are exhaust gas, turbocharger cooling engine jacket cooling water and lube oil cooling water, providing heat at temperatures around 80°C

Reciprocating engines are a proven technology available in sizes from 3 kW to 20 MW. Making them suitable for small to midscale operation. The main advantages for ICEs are a low capital cost, quick start up, high reliability, long lifetime, good load following abilities, high part load efficiencies and the black start capability. Typical drawbacks however are the intensive maintenance needed, high vibration and a high amount of emissions. Especially CI engines have relatively high emissions of NO_x and pollutants. SI engines operating on gas however have improved emission profiles. Furthermore, the temperature level of the heat stream is limited, and ICEs typically comes along with high levels of low frequency noise.

1.1.2. Steam turbines

Steam turbines are by far the most common technology used in power plants. With typical sizes from 50 kW to 500 MW, steam turbines are commonly used in large scale operations. In steam turbines, pressurized steam is generated by an external heat source and expanded over a turbine. As an external heat source is used, the steam can be generated by any kind of fuel (nuclear, gaseous, liquid). This leaves the option for the implementation of more sustainable fuels. It must be noted that in steam turbines heat is generated and converted to electricity. Hence electricity is a by-product, contradictory to combustion turbines and combustion engines, where heat is the by-product. As a mature technology, modern steam turbines are very reliable and have extremely long lifetimes, if properly operated and maintained. Moreover, the total investment became low- and high-quality thermal output is generated. Although steam turbines are the most mature technology for power generation, several drawbacks limit their further deployment, amongst other their low efficiency. Other drawbacks are the slow start-up times and poor part load efficiencies of steam turbines, making them hard to

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combine with renewables. Additionally, the power to heat ratio is very low, although it can be easily varied in a certain extend. The total efficiency is however high.

1.1.3. Combustion turbines

Gas turbines or combustion turbines are a well-known technology and have been used in stationary electrical power generation since the late 1930s. Gas turbines typically operate with natural gas as fuel, but synthetic gas, landfill gas and fuel oils are also used. Typical sizes range from 500 kW to more than 300 MW [171], making them suitable for mid-scale to large-scale operation. Sets smaller than 1MW however are often economically not feasible [169]. The main advantages of gas turbines are the high quality thermal output (i.e. exhaust gas up to 540 °C) and reliability with overhaul times typically ranging between 25,000 – 50,000 h [171]. The main disadvantages are the bad part-load efficiencies and emissions, although these are limited compared to liquid fuel combustion, and post combustion is possible due to the large oxygen excess. The start-up time of combustion turbines is moderate and is considerably shorter than for steam turbines.

1.1.4. Micro turbine

Micro turbines are small and compact gas combustion turbines, generating both electricity and heat. Micro turbines can be used, in contradiction to conventional combustion turbines, for distributed small scale energy applications from several kW to hundreds of kW. Microturbines are able to operate at extremely high operational speeds as high as 120 000 rpm [168], allowing for small sizes and efficiently driving the electricity generator. Moreover, microturbines allows for a fast start up. Furthermore, the same advantages and disadvantages for conventional combustion turbines are present. However, the specific investment costs strongly increase, and the quality of the thermal output reduces (although still being high).

1.1.5. Stirling engine

A Stirling engine is, in contrast to an ICE, an external combustion engine in which energy (i.e., heat) is applied outside of the device. As typical sizes vary between 1 - 1500 kW, a Stirling engine can be used for small- to mid-scale operations, but is most commonly used for small-scale applications. The device itself is a closed cycle, in which the working fluid is alternatively compressed in a 'cold cylinder' and expanded in a hot cylinder. In a Stirling engine, the combustion is continuous and controlled, reducing the pollution and GHG emissions [170]. As heat is externally applied, analogously as for the steam turbines, a Stirling engine can operate at almost any kind of fuel, including more sustainable heat sources (e.g., solar driven). Hence, the pollutant and GHG emissions can be substantially decreased compared to ICEs. Other advantages over ICEs, although these can be generalised, are safer and more silent operation as the working fluid is sealed inside the engine. Moreover, a Stirling engine has limited moving parts. The main drawbacks, however, are the low specific power output and the high capital costs. Furthermore, the power output is hard to tune. Although Stirling engines are a promising technology, they are still in their development phase.

1.1.6. Fuel cell

There are a lot of different fuel cells technologies, although these all have the same operating principles. Fuel cells are available in sizes between 5 – 2800 kW and are thus applicable for small- to mid-scale operations. In fuel cells, chemical energy from a substance is converted into electricity based on a chemical reaction with an oxidizing agent, typically oxygen, producing water as by-product. The

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chemical substance used as fuel is typically hydrogen. If the hydrogen is produced in a sustainable way, fuel cells are one of the most sustainable ways to create both electricity and heat. Another advantage is that fuel cells have few or no moving parts, causing it to be a reliable and low noise technology. Moreover, fuel cells are able to operate at high electrical efficiencies under varying loads. The main drawback however is that fuel cells are not yet commercially available due to its high cost. Furthermore, the hydrogen production is commonly not emission and carbon free, the start-up time is long, and the power density is low. The temperature of the waste heat and the power to heat ratio are strongly dependent on the type of fuel cell and the operating conditions.

An overview of the main characteristics for each prime mover is presented in Table A10. 1 [169–173].

Table A10. 1. Overview of the main prime mover characteristics.

Prime mover	ICE	Steam turbines	Combustion turbines	Micro-turbines	Stirling engine	Fuel cell
Size (kW_e)	3–20000	50–500000	250–300000	15-250	1-1500	5–2800
Overall efficiency (%)	70-83	~80	65-75	63-75	65-85	55-80
Power to heat ratio	0.5-1.2	0.07-0.3	0.5-2	0.4-0.8	1.2-1.7	0.8-2
Temperature heat output (°C)	80	540	540	200-350	60-200	60-480
Part load performance	Good/Fair	Fair/Poor	Fair/Poor	Fair	Good	Good
Start-up time	10s	1hr-1day	10min-1hr	60s	— ^a	3hr-2days
Hours to overhaul	30000-60000	>50000	25000–50000	40000-80000	— ^a	32000–64000
CO_2 (kg/MWh)	500-651	— ^b	525-680	~725	— ^b	— ^b
NO_x (kg/MWh)	S.I: 0.23, C.I. 9.9	— ^b	0.14-0.5	0.1-0.18	— ^b	— ^b

—^a: No data available.

—^b: No information is given as it depends strongly on the fuel source, which is flexible

1.3. Installation and maintenance

To provide desired levels of reliability and efficiency, CHP installations require effective and reliable monitoring and maintenance. Specific maintenance requirements are depending on the type of CHP technology as listed in section 1.2. In general, however, relatively little routine maintenance is needed. Inspection at the planned service intervals should be sufficient, provided that supply of fuel, water and air to the unit are guaranteed.

2. Performance

2.1. Fuel or electricity use

A CHP unit uses fuel to generate heat and electricity. The type of fuel that is used is depending on the type of CHP unit, as listed in section 1.2. To determine the amount of fuel, an estimate can be made based on the required power output and the efficiency of the unit.

2.2. Factors affecting performance

The performance of a given CHP unit is relatively stable. Although supply air temperature will slightly influence the efficiency, local climate does not have a significant impact. To guarantee constant performance, fuel composition should be monitored, and regular cleaning is advised.

2.3. Efficiency and lifecycle emissions

Table A10. 1. provides the overview of typical efficiencies and emissions per type of CHP installation.

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2.4. Operation strategies

Several possible strategies exist for the operation of CHP systems.

2.4.1. Electric load following

In this operation strategy, the PGU generates the amount of electricity that is demanded. The corresponding waste heat is used to satisfy the thermal demands. If the recovered waste heat is not sufficient to satisfy the thermal demands, an auxiliary boiler is needed. If there is an oversupply of recovered waste heat, this heat could be stored, valorised or discarded. Typical methods of valorising the waste heat are either conversion to electricity by organic Rankine cycles or upgrading to higher temperature waste heat by means of heat pumps. The latter is only useful when the temperature of the waste heat is low and there is a higher temperature heat demand present.

2.4.2. Thermal load following

In this operation strategy the PGU generates the amount of heat demanded. If the corresponding electricity generated is not sufficient to meet the electricity demand additional electricity may be imported from the electricity grid. Otherwise, the electricity excess can be stored or send to the grid. If the electricity is stored electricity purchases from the grid may be eliminated.

2.4.3. Base load operation

If the CHP system delivers a constant amount of electricity and heat, additional required electricity or heat can be either purchased from the grid or delivered via an auxiliary boiler.

To take advantage of CHP system, it must be noted however that both a heat demand as an electricity demand should be present simultaneously. If this is not the case, or there is only a limited overlap, a thermal energy system should be assessed, or separate generation should be considered.

3. Cost

3.1. Installation costs

The economics of the CHP applications strongly depend on the installation costs, lifetime of the system, operational and maintenance (O&M) expenses and the value of the electricity and heat produced. An overview of the main economic parameters for each CHP-system can be found in Table A10. 2 [169,171–173]. In this table large scale steam and combustion turbines shows superior economics, while fuel cells show the least favourable economics.

Table A10. 2. Main economic parameters for different CHP types.

Prime mover	ICE	Steam turbines	Combustion turbines	Micro-turbines	Stirling engine	Fuel cell
Life Cycle (Year)	20	25-35	20	10	10	10-20
Installed cost (€/kW)	900-2400	350-1650	800-2700	2000-3500	1000-1650	3750-8200
O&M costs (€/kWh)	0.006-0.021	0.003-0.0082	0.003-0.011	0.006-0.02	N/A	0.026-0.037

No fuel or energy (i.e., heat and electricity) costs are added in the overview as these strongly depends on a country, regional or site specific basis. Moreover, variable pricing schemes are often applied. The economics of CHP units in general are favourable in cases that the fuel prices are low, while the electricity price is high.

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3.2. Operation and maintenance costs

3.2.1. Operation costs

During operation, CHP units consume a type of fuel. Based on the cost of the specific fuel and on the required power output and efficiency of the unit, the operation costs can be calculated.

3.2.2. Maintenance costs

As maintenance of CHP units is typically limited (see section 1.3), the maintenance costs also limited.

3.3. ROI/IRR/Payback period

Cost saving are dependent on the type of fuel used by the CHP and the cost of gas and electricity from the grid. The higher grid costs are, the higher the potential cost savings.

Also, the calculation of the payback period is difficult and case specific. One example was found of a CHP unit installed on a farm, where a payback period of 6 years was possible.

3.4. Funding possibilities

Due to the increased energy efficiency and the reduction in environmental impact, several EU member states introduced support mechanisms to promote CHP systems. Westner and Madlener [174]. summarized the CHP support mechanisms applied in several EU member states. The summary can be found in Fig. A10. 3 [174]. It must be noted that some results might not be representative anymore as the paper was published in 2009.

Country	Feed-in tariff	Certificate scheme	Investment support	Fiscal support
Austria	X		X ^a	
Belgium		X ^b		X
Bulgaria	X ^c			
Cyprus			X ^d	
Czech Rep.	X		X	
Denmark	X ^f			X ^e
Estonia	X ^g			
Finland			X ^d	X
France	X ^h			X
Germany	X		X ⁱ	X
Greece	X ^j			
Hungary	X ^c		X	X
Ireland			X	
Italy		X		X
Latvia	X ^k			
Lithuania	X ^k			
Luxembourg	X ^l		X ^d	
Malta				
Netherlands	X		X	X
Poland		X		
Portugal	X			
Romania				
Slovakia	X ^m			
Slovenia	X ⁿ			X
Spain	X			X ^d
Sweden		X ^d		X
UK				X

^a Only CHP < 2 MW_{el}.
^b Dependent on the region.
^c Only CHP < 50 MW_{el}.
^d Only biomass CHP.
^e Only for micro-CHP.
^f Only micro- and biomass CHP.
^g For replacements < 10 MW_{el}.
^h Only existing non-gas-fueled fossil plants.
ⁱ Only CHP < 50 kW_{el}.
^j Only CHP < 35 MW_{el}.
^k Only district heating.
^l Only CHP < 1.5 MW_{el}.
^m Only industrial CHP.
ⁿ Only industrial CHP and DH.

Fig. A10. 3. Support Mechanisms CHP system in Europe.

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4. Applications

4.1. Existing non-farming applications

CHP is used in many industrial applications where there is a combined heat and power demand. Additionally, some other applications of CHP systems are possible: Trigeneration, Combination with thermal energy storage and district heating systems

4.1.1. Trigeneration

If thermally activated technologies e.g., absorption chillers and adsorption chillers are integrated in the CHP system the thermal energy can be further utilized to provide cooling. A vapour compressor chiller can be used when no thermally activated cooling technologies, but electrically driven cooling technologies are desired. In this way electricity, heating and cooling are both provided from a single source, hence the name trigeneration. Combined cooling, heat and power (CCHP) is also commonly used as alternative name for trigeneration. An illustration of a typical CCHP layout is given in Fig. A10. 4., although conventionally either a thermally activated or an electrically driven cooling technology is used, but not combined.

If the thermal demand is mainly for space heating purposes, the heating demand during summer will be low or there will be no heat demand at all. When cooling however is integrated, a CCHP system will be able to provide cooling during summer. If there is a considerable amount of cooling during summer the system can be more utilized. Hence faster returns on investment are to be expected.

Fig. A10. 4. Overview of a typical CCHP architecture.

4.1.2. Combination with Thermal Energy Storage

Peak boilers are installed in order to overcome the mismatch between heat demand and supply, allowing to decrease the capacity of the CHP. A much more energy efficient method to overcome the energy mismatch between heat supply and demand profiles however is thermal energy storage (TES). Moreover, it allows more electricity to be produced during peak hours when prices are typically high. McDaniel and Kosanovic [175], even state that TES can be used to mitigate the high cost of fuel in winter by charging the TES when the fuel costs are low. In a TES system, heat is stored during moments of heat excess (i.e., non-peak hours) and released during moments of heat shortages (i.e., peak hours). Peak boilers might still be used when a TES system is installed, as they are a reliable back-up, and the energy balance does not always allow the TES to cope with all heat shortages. Moreover, even if the energy balance allows the TES to cope all heat shortages, the economically optimal TES size might not cover all heat shortages.

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4.1.3. District heating systems

In district heating networks, heat is produced by one or multiple centralized producer(s) and is distributed by a heat network in order to meet multiple consumers' residential heat demands. Heat networks are interesting to combine with CHP units, as most units are not straightforward to install in households and economies of scales are often applicable. Two other early justifications for the use of district heating networks in urban areas, according to Reddick et al. [176], were the desire to avoid boiler explosions and to remove the combustion of fuels from densely populated areas. Jamsek et al. [177] also highlighted that larger combustion units typically have more advanced flue gas cleaning than single boiler systems and that in case of combined heat and power generation plants, district heat networks are very energy efficient.

When CHP units are combined with heat networks, the thermal energy produced by the CHP system is distributed by a heat exchanger network, providing heat to buildings in the neighbourhood. This method is particularly popular in northern Europe, in Denmark for example 75% of the district heating energy, taking a considerable share in the total heating energy, is provided by CHP systems [175].

4.2. Existing farming applications

Animal waste contributes to significant environmental problems if not properly processed. The organic feedstock (e.g. manure) however, allows for the production of the renewable energy resource biogas, by anaerobic digestion, also producing fertilizers [178] which can be locally used for soil enrichment. Biogas can be used as a fuel source for several CHP systems, allowing for the production of both heat and electricity, as typically demanded in animal farms. Hamzehkolaei and Amjady [178] analysed the feasibility of a small scale CHP unit with a dual fuel ICE as prime mover for a farm with 3058 dairy cows, producing about 53 910 Nm³ biogas per month. The authors compared the implementation of a 375kWe CHP system to the conventional technology, being importing electricity from the grid and generating heat by use of a diesel fuel boiler. The two cases were compared both from an economic as an environmental point of view. The results showed that the implementation of a CHP unit would lead to an annual cost saving of 73 159 \$ and a payback period of 28.5 months, while reducing the annual CO₂ emissions by 529.65 tons. An illustration of a typical animal farm-based Biogas CHP system can be found in Fig. A10.5.

Fig. A10. 5. Schematic overview of a farm-based biogas CHP System.

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4.3. Status of implementation in Europe

Although CHP units allows for the implementation of more sustainable fuels, most CHP units installed in the EU-27 operate on natural gas and solid fossil fuels (e.g., coal). In 2008 the shares of these fuels were respectively 39% and 35% of the total fuel input [179]. Even though CHP units considerably reduce the fuel usage compared to separate production, preventing huge amount of both GHG and pollutants emissions, it must be taken into account that most CHP plants currently operate on fossil fuels and hence are far from sustainable.

The 1997 Community strategy to promote CHP set an indicative target of 18% for the EU-15 by 2010, doubling the relative electricity production from 1994. Their projections showed that 65 Mt CO₂ per year would be saved by 2010 if the target is reached. However, the contribution of CHP systems in Europe has stalled since then and the target was not reached. Mainly because of less favourable CHP economics caused by rising fuel costs and more favourable electricity costs.

The share of electricity produced in 2009 by CHP units in multiple EU-countries is illustrated in Fig. A1.6. With Denmark taking the largest share of respectively 45%, while Malta has no (reported) CHP plants installed. At a European level around 11% of all electricity is produced by CHP units.

Fig. A10. 6: CHP Share in power generation: EU-27: Eurostat 2009¹⁵.

¹⁵ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/combined-heat-and-power-chp-1/combined-heat-and-power-chp-2>

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Appendix 11: Organic Rankine cycle

1. Technical description

1.1. Working Principle

The Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) machine refers to a device that utilizes low-temperature heat to convert it into useful work, which can itself be converted into electricity, while operating in a cycle. Conceptually, the ORC is similar to a Steam Rankine Cycle, and it is based on the vaporization of a high-pressure liquid, which in turn is expanded to a lower pressure, producing electrical work. The cycle is closed by condensing the low-pressure vapor and pumping it back to the high pressure.

ORC is named for its use of an organic, high molecular mass fluid with a liquid-vapor phase change, or boiling point, occurring at a lower temperature than the water-steam phase-change. The fluid allows Rankine cycle heat recovery from lower temperature sources such as biomass combustion, industrial waste heat, geothermal heat, solar ponds etc., and this is the main application of such cycles.

ORC involves the same components as a conventional steam power plant (a boiler, a work-producing expansion device, a condenser, and a pump). However, the working fluid is an organic compound characterized by a lower boiling temperature than water, allowing power generation from low heat source temperatures [180]. The ideal ORC consists of the following four processes for the selected working medium:

1-2: Isentropic compression of working fluid from low to high pressure (pump)

2-3: Constant pressure heat addition by external heat source (evaporator)

3-4: Isentropic expansion (expander)

4-1: Constant pressure heat rejection (condenser)

The four non-ideal processes in the Rankine cycle, are presented in Fig. A11. 1 and Fig. A11. 2 [181], for a simple and a recuperative ORC, respectively. The states are identified by numbers in the T-s diagram.

Fig. A11. 1. Organic Rankine cycle (left) and typical temperature-entropy diagram (right).

The four processes of the simple Organic Rankine cycle correspond to four main components of the cycle, namely the pump, the evaporator (or boiler), the expander, and the condenser. Often, extra components are suitably coupled with the main equipment in order to make the total assembly more

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efficient (e.g., recuperator) and functional (e.g., control systems). Recuperator is a regenerator (sometimes known as internal heat exchanger) that extracts heat from fluid leaving the expander and uses this to preheat the fluid entering the evaporator.

Fig. A11. 2. Recuperative Organic Rankine cycle with (left) and typical temperature-entropy diagram (right).

The thermal efficiency of an ORC system is influenced by the working fluid's properties, the mass flow rate, the heat that is recovered by the system, the power needed by the system, and the power generated by the system. The objective of an ORC system is to maximize the power recovery of a waste heat stream. ORC thermal efficiency is defined as net power out divided by thermal waste heat in. ORC is considered an energy efficiency technology that saves energy with no considerable gas emissions, but there is the possibility of leakage of a working fluid with high-global warming potential (GWP). In general, the design of an ORC machine is affected by the heat source (e.g., waste heat, biomass, ground, solar), while the components' dimensions, as well as the machine's overall size and architecture, depend on the desired conditions that have to be met. Therefore, the main cycle's components need to address the thermodynamic conditions of the designed cycle.

1.2. Power outputs

As it is presented in Table A11. 1 (based on [182] and [183]), there is a very broad range of power outputs that can be achieved in ORC applications with different types of expanders. The choice of the expansion device strongly depends on the cycle operating conditions, type of working fluid and the range of net power generation.

Table A11. 1. Typical power outputs of different expander types.

Expander type	Power Output [kW _e]	Geoth	Solar	WHR
Scroll	0.25 - 5			Turbine
Screw	* 5 - 1000			Screw
Rotary Vane	** < 1.5			Scroll
Reciprocating piston	*** 5 - 20			Turbine
Radial inflow turbine	30 - 500			Screw
Axial flow turbine	> 50			Scroll
				Turbine
				Screw
				Scroll

* 1.5-1000, ** <2.2, ***<2.0 (in [184])

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1.3. Mechanical construction & classification based on it

The expander can be considered as the most technically advanced component of an ORC system [185], where the largest part of the fluid's energy is converted into electricity, having a critical role in determining the cycle efficiency. Based on the nature of their operation, they are broadly classified as either displacement expanders (or volumetric expanders, i.e., scroll, screw, reciprocating piston, and rotary vane expanders) and turbomachine expanders (or velocity expanders, i.e., axial flow and radial inflow turbines) [181], as shown in Fig. A11. 3.

Fig. A11. 3. Expander types used in ORC systems.

In general, the volumetric expanders are suitable for smaller power output (<50 kWe) and often derived from heating, ventilation, air-conditioning and cooling (HVAC) compressors modified to operate in reverse. Both turbomachines and volumetric expanders have their own advantages and disadvantages along with several types available for each main category. For high power output, turbines are cost-effective and constitute the baseline technology¹⁶. In the medium to low power of less than 400 kW technical constraints pushed to the development of various expansion devices, and screw-Lysholm or scroll expanders are preferred [182]. More recently, some improvements for the expansion process have been proposed, such as the isothermal expander, where the expander is heated to keep constant temperature during expansion, improving the expander's efficiency.

The heat exchangers are the cycle's components (Fig. A11. 4) that recover the wasted energy to heat the refrigerant, and on the other side of the cycle reject the heat to the environment. Therefore, these components have a key role for the cycle performance. Heat exchangers represent a major share of the total module cost; therefore, their optimization should be carefully performed. Key characteristics regarding heat transfers are the effectiveness, the pinch-point and the pressure drop. Each heat exchanger of the cycle is sized according to two key characteristics: the effectiveness and pressure drop. Different types of heat exchangers can be used depending on the application, with shell-tube

¹⁶ In reality, turbines constitute the only choice, since most screw expanders are limited to ~250kWe. Also, turbines are dynamic machines, which means that can vary the operating point during operation.

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being the most common mainly in larger-scale systems, while plate heat exchangers are employed mainly in small-scale systems due to their compactness. The critical heat exchanger is usually the heat exchanger installed on the heat source side (evaporator) since the heat recovery takes place in the high-pressure side. Depending on the cycles operating conditions, this heat exchanger must withstand high temperatures and pressures and has to present suitable design to reduce impact of fouling and/or corrosion. Heat can be recovered by means of two different setups: (1) direct heat exchange between heat source and organic fluid, and (2) an intermediate heat transfer fluid loop that is integrated to transfer heat from the waste heat site to the evaporator, such as thermal oil [186] in order to avoid blockage effects and heat-exchanger degradation because of fouling. The selection of the evaporator depends on the heat source. The heat sources in commercial ORC plants are mainly: biomass, geothermal, waste heat recovery, and solar.

Fig. A11. 4. Plate (left) and shell-tube heat exchanger (right).

The other main component of an ORC is the condenser, consisting of a heat exchanger whose purpose is to return the low-pressure vapor from the expander outlet to liquid state. This requires a cooling media of lower temperature than the organic working fluid. Most common in commercial ORC applications is water-cooled condensers but air-cooled (dry or wet) condensers also exist for small cooling loads. The water-cooled condensers usually employ a cooling tower to bring the water back to its initial temperature. In general, the performance of the condenser depends on the pressure of the working fluid, but also on the heat transfer characteristics of the cooling media, such as the temperature and fluid flowrate. Table A11. 2 presents various heat exchanger types that can be used for an Organic Rankine cycle depending on the application.

Table A11. 2 Types of ORC heat exchangers.

Heat exchangers	Plate heat exchangers	
	Shell-tube heat exchangers	
Condensers	Air-cooled (dry or wet cooling)	
	Water-cooled	
Evaporators (depends on the heat source)	Boilers Plate/Shell-tube heat exchangers	most commonly high temperature

The last main component of an ORC system is the feed pump (Fig. A11. 5), which is responsible for the circulation of the working fluid and thereby its pressurization before it enters the evaporator. Feed pumps are key components, and their design or selection process should be particularly attentive. They should comply with the cycle requirement in terms of controllability, efficiency, tightness and NPSH

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(net pressure suction head) [183]. In general, liquid pumps can be classified as either positive displacement (Rotary or Reciprocating) or centrifugal (Single or Multi-stage).

Fig. A11. 5. Multistage centrifugal pump (Grundfos CRNE).

During the pump's selection, parameters such as flow rate, pressure and thermodynamic condition have to be considered. The evaporation pressure affects mainly the high pressure of the cycle and in turn the pump's selection. Therefore, the pump's operational range depends on the refrigerant selection (because of pressure variation) and the desired power production (flow rate). Moreover, the pumps used in ORC systems have to be sealed efficiently, thus the mechanical coupling is avoided for organic fluids (simple shaft sealing) and magnetic coupling is usually proposed for such applications.

Furthermore, the working fluid of the ORC machine has an important role on the system's performance since its thermodynamic properties strongly affect the components selection and design. The fluid selection process is a trade-off between thermodynamic specifications, safety, environmental and economy aspects. While various refrigerants have been employed for ORC systems, the most studied and used in the previous years are the HFCs R134a, R245fa, R404a, and the new age HFOs R1234ze(E), R1224yd, R1233zd(E)¹⁷.

Today, special attention has been given on the environmental aspect and HFO (HydroFluoroOlefins) refrigerants - also known as 4th generation refrigerants - are getting more and more space in the market. According to the new F-gas regulation of the European Union [187], which applied from January 1st 2015, the total amount of fluorinated refrigerants that can be sold in the EU will be phased down in steps to approximately 33% of 2014 sales by 2030. HFO refrigerants are categorized as having zero ODP (Ozone Depletion Potential) and low GWP and so offer a more environmentally friendly alternative to CFCs (ChloroFluoroCarbons), HCFCs (HydroChloroFluoroCarbons) and HFCs (HydroFluoroCarbons) (Fig. A11. 6), from Mitsubishi Electric¹⁸ and [188]. Among others, studied and used HFO refrigerants are R1234ze(E), R1234yf, R1233zd(E) and R1224yd(Z) presenting a low ODP and ultra-low GWP. Temperature-entropy diagram of water and various typical ORC fluids is shown in Fig. A6. 7, adopted from (1. [186], 2. [189], 3&4: [190]).

¹⁷ Other refrigerants used to as maller extent are: R152a, R227ea, R236fa, R290, R601 (n-Pentane), R600a (Iso-Butane), R717, MDM (Octamethyltrisiloxane).

¹⁸ <https://es.mitsubishielectric.co.uk/the-hub/refrigerants-a-new-focus-on-gwp>

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Fig. A11. 6. Evolution of refrigerants.

Fig. A11. 7. T-s diagram of water and various typical ORC fluids.

1.4. Installation and maintenance

ORC maintenance requirements are low in terms of both time and cost, in comparison with Rankine steam systems. Planned maintenance once a year two man-days allowing for maintenance is normally

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scheduled during other equipment maintenance works¹⁹. The installer/supplier can provide details of each system’s exact maintenance requirements, and also how to optimize its performance.

An example of a completed ORC system is presented in Fig. A11.8²⁰ and Fig. A11.9²¹, where a 3D design presents all the main components and their coupling.

Fig. A11. 8. Main components of an ORC unit from TURBODEN.

Fig. A11. 9. Main components of an ORC unit from Air Squared.

¹⁹ <http://www.inmis-energy.com/3-0-biomass/3-7-technology-comparison/3-7-1-orc-advantages-over-steam>

²⁰ <https://www.turboden.com/>

²¹ <https://airsquared.com/news/spinning-scroll-expander-development-receives-navy-sttr-award/nvorc-phase-1-pr/>

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2. Performance

2.1. Efficiency

The efficiency of current high temperature Organic Rankine Cycles can reach up to 24%. Typical steam Rankine cycles show a thermal efficiency higher than 30%²², but with a more complex cycle architecture (in terms of number of components or size) [186]. At low temperatures (below 100°C), ORC efficiency is usually in the range of 4-6% (up to 10-12% for specific applications), but still there are cases where it can be cost effective, especially for waste heat recovery thus improving the overall process/system energy efficiency [191]. In Table A11. 3 [182], output and performance data of different ORC machines are presented.

Table A11. 3. ORC machines, output, and performance data (from manufacturers' websites and brochures).

Model	Manufacturer	Power output (kW)	Working fluid	Expansion device	Heat source /thermal oil /evaporating temperature (°C)	Cooling/condensing temperature (°C)	Electrical efficiency (%)
IT10	Infinity turbine	10	R134a	Screw	80–120	15–30	–
PureCycle ⁹⁰	Pratt & Whitney Power Systems	280	R245fa	Radial inflow turbine	80–120	–	–
TD4HR	Turboden	418		Turbine	150–275	25–35	18.2
TD12HRS	Turboden	1188		Turbine	206–305	25–35	23.6
TD27HR	Turboden	2740		Turbine	155–285	25–48	19.5
TD7CHP	Turboden	738		Turbine	240–300	60–80	18.4
Green Machine	Electratherm	50	R245fa	Twin screw	80–93	21	12
BEP module	BEP Europe	50	R245fa	Single and Z-screw	80–120	20	12
Triogen module	Tri-o-gen	80–165	Toluene	High speed turbogenerator	> 350	35–50	20–22
Calnetix series S, P, M	Calnetix Power systems	125	R245fa	High speed turbine	121	21	–
AD300 TF-plus	Adoratec	300		Turbine	155/245	60/80	17.03
AD625 TF-plus	Adoratec	625		Turbine	155/245	60/80	17.90
AD2400 TF-plus	Adoratec	2400		Turbine	160/250	60/90	17.35
ENEFCOGEN ^{plus}	Eneftech	5	–	Scroll	160–200	20–50	–
05PLU-01							
PROMETHEUS-25	ENERBasque	20	–	–	80–90	10–25	4–8
EP60-ERS	Exergy	400–650	–	Radial outflow turbine	230–315	–	15–22

2.2. Lifecycle emissions

Life-cycle emission calculations of ORC units take the construction, operation and decommissioning phases into consideration, while they depend strongly on the topology of the system, the available heat source and the working fluid, among others. Therefore, the results vary depending on the application.

For example, the Environmental Impact assessment of an ORC power-plant for waste-heat-recovery (ORCPW) technology [192], concluded that the construction phase is the largest contributor to the total Global Warming Potential (GWP) and Eutrophication Potential (EP). The operation phase is the largest contributor to the total Acidification Potential (AP) and Human Toxicity Potential (HTP) for the ORCPW with R114 and R245fa in the life cycle, while the construction phase is the largest contributor to total AP and HTP with the remaining working fluids (R123, R601a, Pentane, R141b, R113).

For a biomass ORC unit coupled with a biomass boiler, results show that the processes with the largest impact in terms of CO₂ equivalent emissions are these which are related to biomass production and organic fluid leakages, accounting for 71% and 19% of the total CO₂ emissions, respectively [193].

²² At cycle high temperatures of about 250°C

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2.3. Scope of circularity

Circular economy is based on the principles of designing out waste and pollution, keeping products and materials in use, and regenerating natural systems. By-products are extracted to enter other circular systems. The product is then used for as long as possible, and at the end of a product's lifecycle, its constituent components are recycled, to be put back into production again. Nothing goes to waste and natural resources are used in the most efficient way, over and over again.

Circularity is at the core of ORC. ORC applications constitute a reliable technology to efficiently convert low and medium temperature heat sources (by-product) into electricity. Recovering the wasted heat increases the systems' efficiency and also lead to lower fuel consumption and CO₂ production. Even though ORC units have a high material content, by the end of their lives, both their components and working fluids can be recycled.

2.4. Stability/Continuity

In general, the process parameters of the working medium, the physical and chemical characteristics of the working fluid, the continuity of heat supply, and the temperature level of waste heat are necessary conditions that must be considered during design and optimization process [194].

2.5. Operation strategies

The goal of control strategies in ORC applications is to ensure the safe operation of the expander, ensuring superheated vapor at its inlet in order to produce the highest net electrical output power. This is achieved by regulating the optimal evaporating temperature generated by the control strategy, while keeping the superheating at low but still safe values, resulting also in a higher efficiency of the system. Possible degrees-of-freedom in multivariable control strategies, may include the speeds of circulating pump and expander, the mass flow rate and/or temperature of the heat sink, depending of course on the nature of the application [195].

2.6. Practical Lifetime

The average lifetime of an ORC unit has been generally estimated in 20 years [196]. In the case of turbines, some authors suggest that the presence of superheated organic fluid at the end of expansion can allow for an extension of lifetime to 30 years, because of the absence of condensation that reduces the risk of corrosion on the turbine blades [186], [196].

3. Cost

Technical publications on ORC development increasingly include estimation of the costs associated with the system design, but knowledge on actual ORC module and project costs remains scarce [197]. In Fig. A11. 8 (a) [186] and Table A11. 4 [198], some typical ORC module costs, for different applications, are plotted as a function of their size. It has to be noted - also from [186] and [198] - that the provided costs are only indicative and partially collected from a non-exhaustive set of ORC manufacturers and from scientific publications. The scattering in the data is due to different prices for different manufacturers, different market strategies, different integration costs, meaning that individual costs should not be generalized, but are given merely to illustrate the general trend of system prices relative to the output power. Fig. A11. 8. (a) indicates that, for a given target application, the cost tends to decrease when the output power increases.

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The investment cost of an ORC project depends on a set of parameters including size/magnitude of the project, location, cost of land, temperature of the heat source, nature of the heat carrier, cost/size of the ORC unit, labour, cost of material, capital cost, storage/backup system, etc. Fig. A11. 10. (b) [182] would be useful for a quick, qualitatively estimation of an ORC project [182]. Referring to [186], k would be higher for CHP systems and lower for waste heat recovery systems.

Fig. A11. 10. (a) Module (empty dots) and total (plain dots) cost of ORC systems depending on the target application and on the net electrical power, (b) Machine and installation costs vs nominal power output.

Table A11. 4. Key characteristics of ORC applications exploiting different heat sources.

Heat source	Source temperature		Media	Dynamic behavior	Capacity	System Cost	Heat source cost
Industrial processes	80–500 °C, Mostly 200–300 °C		Air, water or steam	Detrimental to the system: stalling or temperature shocks	125 kW - 3 MW; 10 MW for big industry	System total cost 1500–4500 €/kW, Operating cost 5.65€/kWh	None
Power waste heat	ICE	80–100 °C cooling system; 400–900 °C exhaust gas	Water or Air with other gases	Starting and braking moments	95 kW - 6.5 MW	No data	Miniaturization required
	Gas turbines	250–550 °C	Air with other gases	Fluctuates if not monitored	50 kW - 6.5 MW	Micro GT+ORC, 2500–3000 €/kW	None
Geothermal	80–180 °C		Water with brine	Varies a little	0.6 - 27 MW	1000-4000 €/kWe	Drilling and brine pump
Biomass	Around 300 °C		Oil	Fluctuates, uses oil to stabilize	100 - 1500 kW	1600 €/kWe for medium scale 10,000 €/kWe for small scale	Boiler; 1000-1250 €/kW Cost of straw around 9-14 €/kWh
Solar collector	<300 °C		Water or oil	Varies with daily and monthly	< 30 MW	MW system 5000-6000 €/kWe	Collectors; 2/3 of the entire system cost
Solar pond	80–90 °C		Water	Varies with daily and monthly	6 kW - 5 MW	MW system 5000-6000 €/kWe	None

Strzalka [199], provides a comparison of ORC module costs against their gross electrical output. The results show that the investment costs of small-sized ORC modules (<500 kW electric output) are significantly higher compared to the investment costs of larger systems. Fig. A11. 11 [199] shows a steady decline in costs of middle-sized and large ORC plants with increasing electric output. Also, in terms of the financial investment required, the study provides the total costs of ORC plants (including boiler) against their gross electrical output. Fig. A11. 11 shows that there is a clear decrease of cost per kW electrical output installed for small-size plants within the power range of <500 kW. The financial investment required to construct an ORC plant with power output above 500 kW remains almost constant even when the power output increases.

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Fig. A11. 11. ORC module and plant cost in €/kW.

There is still not much published information about the actual costs of ORC systems. A brief review of literature knowledge on the investment costs of ORC modules and ORC projects reveals most are in the 2000 - 4000 €/kW range [197]. Geothermal projects tend to be larger with lower specific investment cost values, solar projects are mostly small and can have very high specific investment costs. Others [200] indicate that for small-scale applications (<100kW), a total investment cost of 10,000 €/kWe is considered as an average in EU. As suggested by [201], the specific cost of small-scale ORC units should not exceed the value of 3,500 €/kW and 2,500 €/kW in the power range of 5 – 10 kW and 10–100 kW, respectively. Indicatively, a commercial ORC unit (ElectraTherm Green Machine 50kW) could cost \$2,530/kW in 2011 [202].

Recently, Air Squared²³ developed a Plug and Play 1kW Micro-ORC at an estimated price of \$3,000 in volume production, and a pay-back period of just under three years, which is expected to bring micro-scale power generation on par with small-scale power generation by cutting the cost per kW installed in half.

3.1. Funding possibilities

The incentives for the ORC market fall under two main categories. Firstly, ORC power plants based on renewable energy sources (RES) such as biomass, biogas, solar thermal or geothermal may benefit from incentives and subsidies to promote the transition towards an increased share of renewable energy in the overall energy mix. The related guidelines and recommendations are described in the DIRECTIVE 2009/28/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL. Secondly, ORC power plants based on waste heat sources are included in the DIRECTIVE 2012/27/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on energy efficiency.

To provide adequate support, support levels might be differentiated, typically between technologies and even within technologies, as differentiation is able to better adapt to the individual requirements of each technology [202]. The European incentive scheme provides Feed-in Tariffs (FiTs), Premium Tariffs (FiP), Green certificates/quota obligations, Investment incentives, Auctions/tenders, Net metering. ORC is not a RES technology per se, but an energy efficiency measure. Therefore, additional funding can be achieved by combining ORC with RES (e.g., solar PVs, Biomass) and integrating it in CHP applications²⁴. Subsidies apply for ORC but depend heavily on the application, size, and national policies.

²³ <https://airsquared.com/news/introducing-plug-play-micro-orc/>

²⁴ General info about EU subsidy programs can be found in <http://www.res-legal.eu/home/> and https://ec.europa.eu/energy/topics/renewable-energy/national-renewable-energy-action-plans-2020_en

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3.2. Return on investment

In ORC applications the economic indicators (e.g., the cost per kW, the Net Present Value, the payback time, etc.) can vary greatly between sources due to differences in the assumed conditions and to the different cost functions available in the literature [198]. At present, ORC is a mature technology in the MW power range. However, its downsizing poses many challenges [201]. The investigation of a reasonable return on investment, has to take into account a broad range of parameters. For all the aforementioned reasons, economic evaluation of an ORC investment is an extremely case-sensitive matter, therefore no safe quantitative conclusions can be drawn at the moment, especially for small-scale applications.

3.3. List of suppliers

According to the recent EU policy for reduced CO₂ emissions and the need for energy efficient systems, the WHR applications presented above, are getting more and more attention. Therefore, many manufacturers have entered the market presenting systems with high reliability and efficiency. Some typical providers of ORC systems components are listed in Table A11. 5 and manufactures/ designers of integrated units are presented in Table A11. 6 [203]. Indicatively, some commercial small-scale ORC units' manufactures are Exergy, Enogia, ElectraTherm, Zuccato Energia, Rank and ICENOVA.

Table A11. 5. Typical providers of ORC systems components.

Components	Providers
Heat exchangers	Swep, Alfa Laval, Kaori
Expanders	Bitzer, Hanbell
Pumps	Grundfos, Edur, Hermetic

Table A11. 6. List of ORC manufacturers/designers, with number of installed units and total installed capacity by 2016.

Manufacturer	ORC units	Total MW	Manufacturer	ORC units	Total MW	Manufacturer	ORC units	Total MW
ABB	2	3.8	Enogia	11	0.26	Orcan	16	0.3
Adoratec	23	16.4	Enreco	1	0.15	ORMAT	1102	1701
BEP – E-rational	20	3.6	Exergy	34	300	Rank	5	0.07
Calnetix / CETY	50	6.3	General Electric	6	101	TAS	17	143
DünCyplan	6	1.2	GMK	18	5.3	TMEIC	1	1
Electratherm	55	3.14	gT – Energy Tech	2	0.7	Triogen	37	5.2
Enerbasque	3	0.13	Johnson Control	1	1.8	Turboden	267	363
Enertime	2	1.6	Kaishan	40	27.2	UTC Power	10	2.8
Enex	1	9.3	Opcon	3	2.0	Zuccato	21	1.7

4. Applications

4.1. Non-farming applications

The ORC technology has many applications, counting more than 2.7 GW of installed capacity, distributed over 705 projects and 1754 ORC units worldwide [203].

Among the possible application waste heat recovery is one of the most important development fields for the ORC. It can be applied to heat and power plants, or to industrial processes, hot exhausts from ovens or furnaces, flue-gas condensation, exhaust gases from vehicles, intercooling of a compressor,

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condenser of a power cycle, etc. The industrial sector is one of the most important energy consumers. The recovery of industrial waste heat represents an opportunity to save energy and improve efficiency with significant energy, environmental and economic benefits.

Also, in maritime, where lowering fuel consumption and pollutant gas emissions is becoming increasingly important, production of electricity using the heat generated by propulsion or auxiliary

Other than waste heat, heat generated by renewable energy sources can also be exploited. Established examples are the coupling of ORC engines with biomass boilers, geothermal power plants, as well as solar thermal systems.

4.2. Current adoption in existing farms or other applications

For small scale applications, ORC unit are frequently used, together with steam engines, gasification systems with the possibility of hot air and Sterling engines [146]. The potential of energy production in different regions, is investigated for both agricultural residues [204] and manure [205]²⁵, depicted in Fig. A11. 12²⁶ and Fig. A11. 13 [206].

Fig. A11. 12. Example of biomass ORC unit.

Fig. A11. 13. Example of on-farm electricity production.

²⁵ See also: <https://www.environltd.co.uk/products/litter-combustion/>

²⁶ Source: <https://www.rank-orc.com/biomass-cogeneration-in-agri-food-industry/>

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Even though agricultural by-products are used as heat source in ORC systems (e.g., solid biomass), the on-farm use is still relatively uncommon. Some well-aimed applications – suitable also for the livestock sector - have been implemented by E-RATIONAL, Inc.²⁷:

In a free-range hen layer farm in Scotland, the 128,000 birds produce enough manure to fire a 750 kWth fluidized bed biomass boiler which feeds an ORC unit. The biomass boiler produces 150 °C of hot water, to provide 750 Wth of heat to be recovered by the ORC. The ORC unit produces power & heat. The average electrical power of 65kWe is used on-site for local consumption. The warm water returning from the ORC is used to heat the chicken sheds of the sites. A distribution system brings the heat to the different henneries. In this way, 100% of the heat generated by the boiler is valorized either as power, or as heat itself, and the boiler ash can be reused as fertilizer because of the nutrients remaining in it.

In an industrial fermentation plant located in Belgium, the produced biogas is converted to electricity through ICE and is fed into the grid. The heat from the motor jacket cooling and the exhaust air is used to heat multiple parts of the plant (e.g., digesters, offices, pasteurization process etc.). To optimize the heat recovery, a small ORC unit, was installed to utilize the remaining unused amount of heat. The remaining 400 kWth is recovered by an ORC unit producing an extra 25 kWe net, which is fed into the grid as well. The digestate of the fermentation process can be also applied as a soil supplement in agriculture and horticulture.

Farm scale applications could integrate ORC units as the one shown in Table A11. ⁷²⁸, with the following technical specifications:

Table A11. 7. Example of biomass ORC unit specifications.

Technical Data		LT1	LT2	LT3	LT4	
	Heat source	Heat transfer fluid	Water	Water	Water	Water
		Inlet temperature (°C)	90-120	90-120	90-120	90-120
		Outlet temperature (°C)	80-110	80-110	80-110	80-110
		Volumetric flow rate (m³/h)	17	37	78	165
		Thermal power (kWt)	125-250	250-500	500-1.000	1.000-2.000
		Connections diameter (PN16)	DN80	DN100	DN150	DN200
		Pressure drop (kPa)	125	125	125	125
		Heat transfer fluid inner volume (L)	20	50	120	250
	Useful heat	Heat transfer fluid	Water	Water	Water	Water
		Inlet temperature (°C)	20-40	20-40	20-40	20-40
		Outlet temperature (°C)	30-50	30-50	30-50	30-50
		Volumetric flow rate (m³/h)	14	30	63	125
		Thermal power (kWt)	100-200	200-400	400-800	800-1.600
		Connections diameter	DN65	DN100	DN150	DN200
		Pressure drop (kPa)	125	125	125	125
Heat transfer fluid inner volume (L)	15	50	120	250		
	Electricity	Gross power (kWe)	8-22	20-45	45-85	80-175
		Net power (kWe)	8-20	15-40	30-80	60-160
		Voltage (V)	3 x 400	3 x 400	3 x 400	3 x 400
		Frequency (Hz)	50	50	50	50
		Intensity (A)	31,5	64	127	250
	Data Connection	RJ45	RJ45	RJ45	RJ45	
Dimensions	A = Length (mm)	3.350	4.850	5.800	8.000	
	B = Wide (mm)	1.550	2.050	2.250	2.250	
	C = High (mm)	2.200	2.500	2.500	2.500	
Weight	kg	5.500	6.500	8.000	10.500	
Container transport (optional)		DC 20'	HC 20'	HC 20'	HC 40'	

DC (dry container), HC (high cube)

²⁷ <https://e-rational.net/applications/biomass-chp.html> and <https://e-rational.net/applications/stationary-engines.html>

²⁸ <https://www.rank-orc.com/rank-lt-2/>

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4.3. Combinations with other technologies

ORC systems can utilize heat from many different sources. These sources might be renewable in origin or waste energy from industrial processes and components. As shown in Fig. A11. 14 [182] , the most usual heat sources are:

- Heat recovery on mechanical equipment and industrial processes
- Waste heat from power generation systems (internal combustion engines and Gas turbines)
- Geothermal
- Biomass
- Solar

Fig. A11. 14. Different ORC applications and total installed capacity of ORC systems per application.

Fig. A11. 15 [181] depicts four different typologies of ORC applications - (1) Waste heat from power generation system, (2) Geothermal, (3) Biomass, (4) Solar. Obviously, the common characteristic of all the applications is the rejected heat, which the ORC recovers.

Fig. A11. 15. ORC heat sources: (1) Waste heat from power generation system, (2) Geothermal, (3) Biomass, (4) Solar.

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Appendix 12: Thermal storage system

1. Technical description

Since energy demands in the commercial, industrial and utility sectors vary on daily, weekly and seasonal bases, demands can be matched with the help of energy storage systems [207]. Several types of energy storage exist, as can be seen in the overview of Fig. A12. 1 [207]. In this document, the thermal energy storage (TES) systems will be discussed.

Fig. A12. 1. Different methods of energy storage.

1.1. Working Principle

TES is a technology that stores thermal energy by heating or cooling a storage medium, so that the stored energy can be used at a later time, e.g. for heating or cooling applications or power generation [208]. As will be explained in more detail later, the general working principle of all types of TES systems is similar: The system is first charged (increasing the energy content), the energy (typically as heat) is then stored, until finally, the system is discharged when the energy is required.

Some advantages of using TES in an energy system include a higher overall efficiency, better reliability, reduction of running and investment costs and reduced emissions [208].

1.2. Classification

As can be seen in Fig. A12. 1, both sensible and latent TES systems exist. In the TES review by Sarbu et al. [208], thermo-chemical storage (TCS) is identified as a third type of TES. The selection of a type of TES, is done based on different characteristics, as for example, but not limited to: temperatures, capacity, power, efficiency, storage period, charge and discharge time and cost.

Both sensible thermal energy storage, where storage is done by raising or lowering a material in temperature, and latent thermal energy storage, where a phase change (e.g., from liquid to vapour) occurs, are discussed below. Regardless of the type of TES, at least three steps are involved in a complete storage process [207]: charging, storing and discharging, as can be seen in the simple storage cycle in Fig. A12. 2 [207], where Q_i are heat losses to the environment which will be positive for cold thermal storage and negative for hot thermal storage.

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Fig. A12. 2. Three processes involved with TES.

1.2.1. Sensible thermal energy storage

As mentioned before, sensible TES is the process where energy is stored by changing the temperature of a storage medium. This medium can be a gas (e.g., air), a liquid (e.g. water or oil) or a solid (e.g. rock beds, bricks or soil). No phase change will occur in sensible TES. The capacity (the amount of energy that can be stored) of a sensible TES, is proportional to the possible temperature difference, the available mass of the storage medium and the specific heat capacity of that medium. The capacity can be expressed with Equation 1, where Q is the stored amount of heat (J), m is the available mass (kg), c_p is the specific heat capacity (J/kgK) and ΔT the available temperature difference ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).

$$Q = m \cdot c_p \cdot \Delta T \quad (1)$$

The properties of some common TES materials can be found in Table A12. 1 [207]. Some others (mainly used at higher temperatures) are thermal oils, molten salts and liquid metals [209]. As can be seen, water has a high volumetric thermal capacity. This heat capacity, in combination with its high availability, the possibility to be used as storage medium and as heat transfer fluid, its non-toxicity and its cost are the causes it is the most commonly used energy storage material at low temperatures [209]. (Stratified) hot water tanks are a cost-effective option for energy saving in water heating systems via solar energy and via co-generation energy supply systems [208]. Unless the system is pressurized, the maximum temperature of TES systems with water is limited by the boiling temperature of the water. Buffer vessels for domestic hot water (DHW) supply are typically in the range of 200 L to several cubic meters (m^3) [208].

Table A12. 1. Thermophysical properties of some common TES materials.

Material	Density (kg/m^3)	Specific heat capacity (J/kgK)	Volumetric thermal capacity ($10^6 \text{J}/\text{m}^3\text{K}$)
Water	988	4182	4.17
Clay	1458	879	1.28
Brick	1800	837	1.51
Sandstone	2200	712	1.57
Wood	700	2390	1.67
Concrete	2000	880	1.76
Glass	2710	837	2.27
Steel	7840	465	3.68

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1.2.2. Latent thermal energy storage

Unlike with sensible thermal energy storage, there is no significant temperature change required for latent thermal energy storage. Instead, the heat is mainly stored in the phase-change process and is linked to the latent heat of the substance [208] Latent TES materials are called phase-change materials (PCM's), which have the property of releasing or absorbing energy with a change in physical state. They allow an increased energy storage density (and hence a reduced volume) and have an isothermal nature. Latent TES has been used since ancient times. E.g. in the nineteenth century, ice stores were a common way in Europe to preserve food [209]. The storage capacity, Q (J), of a latent TES can be calculated with Equation 2, where heating of a medium from a temperature below the melting temperature to a temperature above the melting temperature are considered.

$$Q = m \cdot (c_{ps} \cdot \Delta T_s + f \cdot \Delta q + c_{pl} \cdot \Delta T_l) \quad (2)$$

In this equation, m is the mass of the system (kg), c_{ps} and c_{pl} are the (average) specific heat capacities in the solid and liquid phase (J/kgK), ΔT_s and ΔT_l are the temperature differences in the solid and liquid phase (°C), f is the melt fraction and Δq is the latent heat of fusion (J/kg).

1.3. Typical sizes

The size of a TES system is highly dependent on the application and the selected type of TES system. The greater the required capacity, the larger the system for a certain heat transfer medium will be. This medium be selected by considering the temperatures and the required power. In the publication by Frazzica et al. [209] the following set of typical parameters is given:

Table A12. 2. typical parameters for Sensible and laten thermal energy storage system.

TES system	Capacity (kWh/t)	Power (MW)	Efficiency (%)	Storage period
Sensible (hot water)	10-50	0.001-10	50-90	Days/months
Latent	50-150	0.001-1.	75-90	Hours/months

1.4. Mechanical construction

Since the size and the selected medium are depending on the required characteristics, also the mechanical construction can vary significantly. Two examples with a construction of completely different are given.

Sensible thermal storage vessels with hot water, e.g., in residential buildings, are typically made as a steel vessel (of e.g. 750 l), surrounded with insulation material. On the inside, there can be one or more coils through which a fluid can flow. These coils are often made of steel or copper.

Thermal energy storage is however also done by heating of the soil in summer, in order to use this energy for space heating during winter. In this case, no storage vessels are required. The mechanical construction is rather a set of boreholes and tubes in the soil through which a heat transfer fluid can be circulated.

1.5. Installation and maintenance

Since sensible thermal energy storage with hot water vessels is one of the most common forms of thermal energy storage, this is what this paragraph will be focussed on.

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The installation of such TES systems is typically performed by a plumber. The supply and discharge tubes have to be connected to the suitable ports on the device. It is important that these connections are performed watertight.

TES systems are typically low-maintenance because they have no moving parts [207]. Some water treatment might be necessary, and cleaning of filters and heat exchangers might be required to remove cleaning.

1.6. Selection of the appropriate type

When selecting a TES system, a trade-off is typically made between size, cost and performance. The temperatures at which the system should operate will limit the possible storage media. A further selection can be made by comparing the available space and the specific heat capacities (see Table A12. 1) to the required thermal storage capacity. When multiple options remain, the selection will typically be done on a cost basis.

2. Performance

2.1. Fuel or electricity use

Thermal energy storage systems don't have any moving parts themselves. However, when implemented in a large system (e.g., the heating system of a building), they will impose an additional pressure drop. In order to overcome this pressure, drop, pumps are required which will use electricity (or fuel).

This fuel or electricity use caused by pumps or fans will typically be much lower than the energy that can be saved by using the TES system. Since only a limited fuel or electricity use is required, also the associated emissions will be low.

2.2. Factors affecting performance

In order to obtain a TES system which performance as expected by the characteristics of the system it is implemented in, an appropriate selection needs to be made first.

The efficiency of the selected TES systems is typically determined by charging and discharging efficiency and the losses to the environment. In general, the performance of the TES system can be improved by limiting the losses to the environment, e.g., by adding insulation.

2.3. Practical lifetime

Since TES systems have no moving parts, the lifetime of these installations can be very long. One of the main causes of failures that can be identified for TES systems is corrosion of surfaces. However, with regular inspection, adequate material selection and possibly water treatment (depending on the type of TES system), this risk can be mitigated.

3. Cost

3.1. Installation costs

As already mentioned before, a number of different TES technologies exists, each with significantly different installation costs. According to Frazzica [209], sensible TES systems can be inexpensive,

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because they are mainly made of a simple tank for the storage medium, with some auxiliary equipment. Also, the different storage media (see Table A12. 1) can be purchased relatively cheap. One large cost will be the thermal insulation of the container of the storage medium, required to minimize the losses to the environment. In a report by IRENA [210], some values can be found to estimate the installation cost. Sensible TES with hot water would be between 0.1 and 10 €/kWhth, while latent TES with PCM would be between 10 and 50 €/kWhth.

3.2. Operation and maintenance costs

As elaborated on in section 1.4, TES systems are typically low maintenance. Therefore, it can be assumed that the maintenance costs for such systems will be low. Furthermore, as the only power that is needed to use TES is electricity to run the pumps, also the operation costs will be limited.

3.3. Cost savings

The costs savings possible by the installation of a TES systems are case specific and dependent on the selected technology. Although no general rule for the possible cost saving was found, some examples were encountered:

- One university could reduce the peak demand for cooling with 40%, saving them \$320 000 per year [211].
- Calculations for an air conditions system in an office building in Malaysia show that cold TES can reduce the annual cost for air conditioning with 35% [212].
- The evaluation of TES for a system with PV production and a heat pump reported energy cost reductions up to 41%, depending on the climate conditions [213].

3.4. ROI/IRR/NPV/Payback period

As both the installation costs and the cost saving as case specific and difficult to estimate, it is hard to give estimates on the rate of return on investment or the payback period.

In one publication, TES was considered for a combined heat and power plant in a district heating network. Payback periods were found between 1.67 years and 4.52 years, depending on the capacity of the TES (ranging between 25 MWh and 1000 MWh).

3.5. Funding schemes

No information could be found about funding schemes for thermal energy storage systems.

4. Applications

4.1. Existing non-farming applications

4.1.1. Heating and cooling systems

Producing space heating can be done using electricity, natural gas, propane or fuel oils. TES systems can be used to increase the efficiency of heating systems. Furthermore, if prices of electricity are e.g., lower during the night, TES with water tanks can be used to reduce operating costs. In addition to water tanks, also aquifer or borehole TES systems exists (UTES, underground TES), as well as TES in the construction elements of a building.

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4.1.2. TES in building construction

While water tanks are commonly used, the energy can also be stored in the constructional components of a building. This can be done as a passive system, using the thermal mass of the building to improve comfort (e.g., heavy concrete constructions). To increase capacity, even PCMs can be implemented in the construction of the building. Also, active systems are available, where hot or cold water can be directed through the thermal mass of the building, in a system called thermally activated building structures (TABS).

4.1.3. Solar energy storage

Although solar energy has a large potential as renewable energy source, it is limited by being a cyclic, time-dependent energy resource [207]. By storing excess solar energy with a TES system during the day, energy can be provided when no sun is available. This is illustrated with Fig. A12. 3 [214]. Additionally, one of the main applications of TES with molten salts at high temperature, is in concentrated solar power plants.

Fig. A12. 3. Using thermal energy storage for solar energy applications.

4.2. Existing farming applications

No applications of TES systems specifically designed for livestock farming could be identified. However, some examples of non-farming applications used in a farming environment do exist. For example, TES with borehole systems can be done to reduce the heat costs in winter and cooling costs in summer [214]. Additionally, also the use of a hot water storage vessel to store solar energy in a pig farm in Germany was found [215].

4.3. Status of implementation in Europe

No data was found on the current status of the implementation of TES systems in European farming.

4.4. Best practices/typical combinations with other technologies

TES systems are typically not use individually but combined with other renewable technologies. Some relevant technologies are:

- **Heat pumps:** TES systems could be charged by heat pumps when electricity prices are low. Additionally, they allow to increase the power output.
- **Geothermal energy:** By using borehole TES, the capacity of a geothermal system is used as storage vessel.
- **Solar collector:** The thermal supply by a solar collector will seldomly match the immediate thermal demand. When the supply is larger than the demand, the system can be charged. When there is no sun, the system can be discharged.

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Appendix 13: Electrical storage system

Energy storage is essential for electrical systems that are powered by renewable energy. The important point about renewable energy technologies is that their performance is highly dependent on daily and seasonal weather conditions, and energy production can vary from a few minutes to a few hours during the day. In a situation where it is impossible to generate electricity, if the power storage technology is not provided in the system, another source such as a connection to the electricity grid will be needed to supply the required power. Therefore, with the help of energy storage technologies, the use of renewable energy can be maximized and even if it is possible to connect to the electricity grid due to the difference in the purchase and sale price of electricity can be profitable. By storing electricity generated from renewable sources, it is possible to consume it at the desired time. It is conceivable that shortly, with the increase in renewable energy usage in various sectors and the increase in fossil fuel prices and electricity prices during peak times, the energy storage industry will be more welcomed and experience significant progress. But electricity storage technologies also face many challenges. Because it is not possible to store electricity directly and it must first be converted to other energies and then stored. During the completion of this process, energy loss occurs and requires expensive equipment. Various technologies for local energy storage are differed greatly in terms of performance, cost, components, and features. According to the existing technical needs and limitations, we should select the best option for each project. Fig. A13. 1 to Fig. A13. 3 show the projects implemented using electricity storage technologies in Australia [216], Nigeria [217] and Southern Hemisphere [218] respectively.

Fig. A13. 1. 240 kWh battery bank charge by solar panels on Gippsland Dairy Farm.

Fig. A13. 2. The energy system of Gbamu-Gbamu village in Nigeria.

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Fig. A13. 3. The Li-ion battery bank of Robben Island, one of the largest battery banks in the Southern Hemisphere.

1.2. Classification

1.2.1. Lead–acid batteries

Working principle: The potential difference between pure lead at the negative pole and PbO_2 at the positive pole, plus aqueous sulfuric acid, stores the battery's chemical energy while it is in charge. These batteries are produced in two types, 'deep cycle' and 'starting'. For applications that require a large number of cycles and low energy output, the deep cycle type is used. But starting batteries are designed for applications with higher output power and fewer cycles. A 12V 9AH Lead acid battery dimension is 151 mm x 65 mm x 94 mm. Lead-acid batteries are available in three versions: Wet Cell (flooded), Gel Cell, and Absorbed Glass Mat (AGM). Electrolyte fluid is used in the production of Wet Cell batteries, which can be accessed if necessary. But fluids are not accessible in Valve Regulated Lead-Acid Batteries (VRLA) and they are maintenance-free and sealed. For deep cycle applications, Gel Cells are usually used, which use a silica additive to regulate the electrolyte.

Fig. A13. 4. Working principle of a lead-acid battery.

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Installation & maintenance: Among the factors that should be considered in the installation are the ventilation required for the battery bank, the ground conditions on which the battery is to be placed and the safety of people who may have access to the battery bank. In addition, the ambient temperature must be kept constant under the permitted operating conditions of the battery. Batteries are exposed to freezing at low temperatures and low charge. Also, batteries that are used continuously at high temperatures have a very short lifespan.

In lead-acid batteries, the amount of water must be monitored regularly, because the production and release of hydrogen and oxygen from the battery cause water loss. Usually, other battery components do not need maintenance and the only problem is the battery water control. Continuous control of the battery water level can be costly if the system is installed in a remote location.

1.2.2. Nickel-Cadmium (NiCd) batteries

Working principle: A positive electrode made of nickel (or hydroxide) and a negative electrode made of cadmium hydroxide create the structure of a nickel-cadmium battery. In nickel-cadmium batteries, the positive and negative electrodes undergo oxidation and reduction reactions. These batteries are produced in three forms: pocket-plate, sintered-plate, and sealed. The first two types can be vented and maintained. The pocket-plate Nickel Cadmium batteries have lower energy density and higher cost than lead-acid batteries. But they have a long and reliable life cycle. They require little maintenance and can retain energy well. They also show good resistance to physical and electrical abuse. Because of these benefits, Nickel Cadmium batteries are used in hospital emergency power systems or train emergency braking. Sintered-plate Nickel Cadmium batteries have 50% more energy density and better performance than pocket-plate, but their higher cost is their disadvantage. This type of Nickel Cadmium batteries is used in cases such as starter motor for diesel or aircraft engines that need to be charged in a short time and high peak power. The nominal voltage of nickel–cadmium battery system is 1.2 V/cell.

Fig. A13. 5. Schematic diagram of Ni-Cd battery energy storage system.

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Installation & maintenance: Nickel-cadmium batteries are less sensitive to temperature changes. This is because the electrolyte composition does not change during charging and discharging the battery, making them more resistant to freezing even at low charge levels. These batteries are also less affected at high temperatures. These advantages make the installation conditions of these nickel-cadmium batteries easier.

The need for maintenance in these batteries is far less than that of lead-acid batteries. This is because these batteries produce fewer corrosive elements and also release less gas. As a result, a process such as sulfating the lead-acid battery does not occur and increases battery life.

1.2.3. Nickel–Metal Hydride (NiMH) batteries

Working principle: The chemistry on the positive electrode of Ni-MH batteries is the same as Ni-Cd batteries. Hydrogen in the form of a metal hydride acts as a negative active ingredient. While charging the battery, hydrogen absorption occurs during a thermogenic reaction. The electrolyte in these batteries is aqueous potassium hydroxide. With the help of lithium hydroxide, the evolution of oxygen can be reduced, and the charging efficiency of the positive electrode can be improved. Almost all Ni-MH batteries do not require maintenance and are sealed. Like all batteries that use aqueous electrolytes in their structure, extra care must be taken when charging to avoid overcharging and limit oxygen production. The negative electrode has extra capacity than the positive electrode and can actually handle overcharging and over-discharging. The energy density of these batteries is 1.5 to 2 times higher than Ni-Cd batteries. Endurance against overcharging or discharging, environmental friendliness, safety and high-power capacity are some of the advantages of this type of battery. But compared to Li-ion batteries, they have a lower energy density. The nominal cell voltage of Ni-MH batteries is 1.2V.

Fig. A13. 6. Schematic of Ni-MH cell.

Installation & maintenance: Almost all Ni-MH batteries do not require maintenance and are sealed. Like all batteries that use aqueous electrolytes in their structure, extra care must be taken when charging to avoid overcharging and limit oxygen production. Because the chemical products of overcharge can recombine in the cell, they do not cause any chemical degradation or change for moderate charge rates.

These technologies can be installed in harsh environmental conditions and require minimal electronic battery control systems. Because of their durability in extreme temperatures can be installed in applications where safe operation and long life are essential.

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1.2.4. Lithium-ion batteries

Working principle: These batteries use the exchange of lithium ions between the positive and negative electrodes throughout their life cycle (Fig. A13. 7 [219]). Different chemicals are used in the production of lithium-ion batteries, each with different properties and characteristics.

Fig. A13. 7. Main components and operating principle of a lithium-ion cell.

Perhaps the most promising technology for storage energy is lithium-ion batteries that can be used on a small and large scale to generate electricity. Although they have a significant share of the smartphone and laptop market and perform better than other technologies, they need further development in the power generation industry. In this family of rechargeable batteries, discharge is done by transferring lithium ions through a non-aqueous electrolyte from the anode to the cathode. Materials, chemistry, performance, cost, and safety characteristics vary considerably in the family. The cathode can be produced using various compounds such as lithium cobalt oxide (LiCoO_2), lithium-iron phosphate (polyanion), or lithium manganese oxide (spinel). Usually, carbon (graphite or special carbon material) is the constituent of the anode. The electrolyte is also often composed of a lithium salt (LiPF_6 , LiBF_4 , or LiClO_4) which is soluble in an organic solvent (ethylene-, dimethyl-, and diethyl-carbonate). A lithium-ion battery cell nominal voltage is 3.7V.

Installation & maintenance: Lithium-ion batteries typically do not require maintenance, but their performance can be affected by the installation location. Most lithium batteries have a battery management system (BMS) responsible for controlling the temperature, charge status, cycle life, and other aspects of each battery cell. As long as the storage system is installed at the right altitude and in the eligible temperature range, it will not need maintenance. Avoiding extreme temperatures is strongly recommended to ensure the performance of lithium-ion batteries.

1.2.5. Flow batteries

Working principle: There are two fluid electrolyte reservoirs inside the structure of these batteries, which are flowed through an electrochemical cell. Zinc / Bromide and Vanadium Redox are commonly used as electrolytes in these batteries (Fig. A13. 8). The advantages of these batteries are environmentally friendly and the use of low-cost materials, high charging speed, good energy density, and good energy efficiency. The main disadvantage of these energy storage systems is the use of pumps and control systems, which increase costs. Although these batteries have a low energy density, we can use them in local energy storage applications. Flow battery cell voltage ranges from 1.0 to 2.43 volts.

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Fig. A13. 8. Schematic of Vanadium Redox Flow Cell.

Installation & maintenance: Compared to all available batteries, flow batteries have the longest lifespan and the least maintenance. The electrolyte in these batteries is not degenerate during use and can be used for many years without replacement, and finally can be recycled and reused. Furthermore, the electrodes in these batteries do not undergo chemical changes during operation. Any of the battery components can be replaced during the process or at the end of life. Since this technology requires space for installation, it is not suitable for small applications and the most significant focus is on using this technology in fixed and large applications.

1.2.6. Pumped storage hydroelectricity

This system uses the gravitational potential energy of water to store energy. By pumping water from a low-altitude source to a higher-altitude reservoir, energy is stored. In times of need to generate energy by releasing the water stored in the upper tank to the lower tank, the turbine placed in the path is rotated and produces electrical energy. In this technology, there must be a high-capacity tank with high height to generate electricity. For this reason, the use of this system is largely dependent on the topography of the project area and requires a lot of infrastructures (Fig. A13. 9), which makes it practically possible to use it only in very limited places.

Fig. A13. 9. Schematic diagram of pumped hydro storage.

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1.3. Selection of appropriate technology

To choose the best possible option among the available technologies, we should consider various factors such as total costs (initial, installation, maintenance, replacement, and disposal), longevity with proper performance, safety and reliability, and finally the environmental impacts. It is also important to consider the energy density and power available, fast charging capability and operating range according to the project. The use of lead-acid batteries is more common than other options due to their high reliability, low discharge, and low total cost to store the produced energy by photovoltaic panels. However, due to the short lifetime of these batteries due to continuous loadings and discharges and their few life cycles, they do not meet all expectations. They are predicted to be replaced by lithium-ion batteries shortly. On the other hand, lithium-ion batteries have advantages such as high energy efficiency and density, long life cycle, and partial self-discharge, which are very important. Moreover, they are not made of toxic materials from an environmental point of view, and with continuous and proper control of these batteries, we can achieve the required reliability. The biggest drawback of these batteries is their relatively high cost, which is two or three times more expensive than lead-acid batteries. Of course, with the improvements made in their production process, it is predicted that their cost reduction process will continue, and they will be able to compete with other options in terms of cost. Given the above, both lead-acid and lithium-ion battery technologies can be a good option for storing the energy produced by photovoltaic panels. But to make the final choice needs to be examined more carefully according to the requirements and conditions of the project.

2. Performance

2.1. Lead–acid batteries

Low energy density and long recharge time are some of the disadvantages of lead-acid batteries. Electrolyte levels in unsealed batteries should be constantly checked and desulphation of electrodes. If lead-acid batteries are over discharged or left standing in the discharged state for prolonged periods hardened lead sulphate coats the electrodes and will not be removed during recharging. Such build-ups reduce the efficiency and life of batteries. Over charging can cause electrolyte to escape as gases. Conventional lead-acid batteries have 500 cycles, which can extend to 2000 cycles with special design and settings. Residential or farm work cycles can reduce battery life and should be disposed of as hazardous waste at the end of the battery life. In general, lead-acid batteries are not recommended for energy storage at home or on the farm due to their low energy density.

Lifecycle Emissions: Attempts have been made to replace lead-acid batteries with other available technologies due to improper disposal, lead smelting operations and other environmental concerns. The two main components of these batteries are lead and sulfuric acid, which can contaminate solid and groundwater in case of improper disposal. Lead is highly harmful to human health, and sulfuric acid is a highly corrosive substance. However, if these batteries are properly collected and recycled, the overall environmental impact of this product can be reduced. Lead has a high recycling rate among common metals. This means that the environmental effects associated with the extraction and smelting of lead ore are minimized.

2.2. Nickel Cadmium (NiCd) batteries

These batteries have to work on a range from 0 to 45 °C, during charging, and from -20 to 60 °C, during discharging. It is not possible to vent or maintain Nickel Cadmium sealed batteries. Out of these ranges,

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they are dangerous and could explode. The memory effect reduces the performance of Nickel-Cadmium batteries, which occurs as a result of repeated shallow discharge cycles and reduces battery capacity. This effect can be neutralized by completely discharging the battery and recharging. If maintained properly, these batteries can last between 500 and 1,500 cycles and they have an efficiency of 70-75%. Nickel Cadmium batteries can be used on farms or at home but are less popular than lead-acid batteries due to the high environmental burdens caused by cadmium and the higher cost.

Lifecycle Emissions: These batteries contain 6 to 18 percent cadmium, a heavy metal that is highly toxic. For this reason, special disposal care is required at the end of battery life. In the United States, the cost of disposing of a battery at the end of the life cycle is added to the purchase price of the battery. Besides, according to the "batteries directive", the use of this technology is limited to specific applications in the European Union Within the European Union (for replacement purposes or for certain types of new equipment such as medical devices), and manufacturers of nickel-cadmium batteries are required to collect them at the end of their life and recycle them in dedicated facilities.

2.3. Nickel–Metal Hydride (NiMH) batteries

These batteries have advantages such as safety (resistant against leaking and explosion), life cycle, high energy density, and abuse resistance. The efficiency of a NiMH battery is usually between 600 and 1200 cycles and up to 80% capacity. Due to their high energy density and lower environmental impact, they are actually a good alternative to Nickel Cadmium batteries. Under the influence of few cycles, the capacity of these batteries is significantly reduced, but in contrast, the capacity of Nickel Cadmium batteries is almost constant throughout their life. In local storage systems, cost and longevity are more important than energy density. This consideration is why the lithium-ion batteries are more desirable than these batteries.

Lifecycle Emissions: Based on the information available on these types of batteries, these batteries' raw materials and wastes are not classified as toxic materials. Ignitability, corrosivity and reactivity are considered potential hazards in the life cycle of these batteries.

2.4. Lithium-ion batteries

Durability and long-life cycle, low discharge speed and high power and energy density are the most obvious advantages of lithium-ion batteries. Also, these batteries do not need maintenance and have sealed cells. However, the thermal problems of LIBs remain intractable due to the flammability, volatility and corrosiveness of organic liquid electrolytes. To ultimately solve the thermal problem, all-solid-state LIBs (ASSLIBs) are considered to be the most promising technology. The capacity of these batteries decreases over time, and they typically have a life cycle of about 1000 cycles. For example, "Thunder Sky" Lithium Iron Phosphate battery can provide 80% of the initial capacity in 3,000 cycles and 70% of the initial capacity in 4,000 cycles. The initial cost of these batteries is moderate, and they need protective circuits to prevent overcharging and discharging too much, which is one of their disadvantages. The cells are protected from possible damage by a protective circuit. Lithium-ion batteries are very suitable for storing energy in farms and homes due to their high capacity and longevity. We should only consider the economic aspect of using these batteries. They have the best energy density (125-250 Wh/kg, up to 250-630 Wh/l), cycle efficiency (90%), and durability (400-1200 cycles), with high power density (230–340 W/kg, up to 1,500 W/kg), the lowest rate of self-discharge (5–8% per month at 21°C, 15% at 40°C, 31% at 60°C). Lithium-ion batteries are capable of operating in a wide range of temperatures. However, to expand lithium-ion batteries in power generation, it is

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necessary to reduce costs and operate more safely. Extensive efforts have been made today to use these batteries in electric vehicles and generate electricity by improving capacity, reliability, safety, and power size. Lithium-ion batteries generate an unusual amount of heat due to overcharging due to their high energy density. Also, the heat generated at the anode and the oxygen produced at the cathode, and the possibility of short circuits due to lithium deposition poses risks. In this regard, one of the most basic issues is the safety of these batteries.

Lifecycle Emissions: Lithium extraction can lead to surface and groundwater pollution, respiratory problems, ecosystem degradation and damage to the landscape. Water pollution from lithium extraction can be deadly to aquatic life. Also, to extract each ton of lithium, an average of 1.9 million litres of water is required, which significantly impacts water resources depletion. By-products of lithium extraction include significant amounts of magnesium and lime waste. On the other hand, 67 megajoule (MJ) of energy are used to produce one kilogram of lithium-ion battery. The energy source used during the extraction and production of lithium-ion batteries dramatically affects the global warming potential. These adverse environmental effects can be significantly reduced by effectively collecting and recycling these batteries.

2.5. Flow batteries

For Vanadium redox flow cells or (VRB) batteries, we can expect 65 - 80% storage performance, short-term response to electricity demand, and a lifetime of about 12,000 cycles over 10 years. VRB batteries require very little maintenance, unlike other rechargeable batteries. One of the disadvantages of these systems is their high complexity. The low energy density of these batteries is between 20-40 Wh/l, which is 40-80 Wh/l for lead-acid batteries and 140-210 Wh/l for Li-ion batteries, which is a disadvantage.

Lifecycle Emissions: Flow batteries do not use toxic metals such as lead, cadmium, zinc, and nickel, which can pollute the environment throughout the battery life cycle. That is why flow batteries are much greener than other batteries. In addition, vanadium is a substance that is found in abundance and is readily available. It is also possible to prepare and recover vanadium from chemical wastes and various combustion streams. Vanadium electrolyte is almost 100% recyclable and reusable and can be used in another project without any waste.

2.6. Pumped storage hydroelectricity

The efficiency of pumped hydro systems (i.e., output energy to energy absorbed for pumping) is between 70 and 80%. This efficiency is 92% for pumps and turbines, 98% for engines and generators and 93% energy efficiency (7% energy loss). Pumped hydro systems require very large water tanks and high elevation differences between lower and upper tanks to increase relatively low energy density. The lifetime of these systems is typically estimated at 50,000 cycles (over 30 years).

2.7. Battery Bank sizing

To calculate the approximate size of the required battery system, the daily energy consumption and type of battery must be specified.

For example, if a livestock farm has an electricity demand of 170MWh, it is preliminarily possible to assess a peak daily demand as the double of the daily average consumption, as follows

$$170000\text{kWh}/365=465.75 \text{ kWh}$$

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$465.75 \times 2 = 931.5$ kWh daily power consumption

Then, the storage size can be assessed for different technologies:

Lead Acid Sizing

$931.5 \text{ kWh} \times 2$ (for 50% depth of discharge) $\times 1.2$ (inefficiency factor) = 2235.6 kWh

Lithium Sizing

$931.5 \text{ kWh} \times 1.2$ (for 80% depth of discharge) $\times 1.05$ (inefficiency factor) = 1173.69 kWh

3. Cost

3.1. Lead–acid batteries

The rate of self-discharge in lead acid batteries is lower than other batteries and it is between 0.09% and 0.4% per day. This amount is slightly higher than lithium-ion batteries. They also have 50 Wh/L to 100 Wh/L energy density. Significant changes in the rate of self-discharge and energy density of these batteries are not expected until 2030. On the other hand, lead acid batteries on the market have a cycle life of between 250 and 2500 full-cycles and between 3 and 15 years of calendar life. According to possible developments, by 2030, the cycle life of these batteries is expected to increase to 540 to 5375 full cycles (i.e., more than double). Currently, the cost of lead acid batteries in 2016 is estimated at USD 105 to USD 475/kWh. Given the projected improvements in the production process, it can be expected to reduce costs to compete with other technologies. These costs could be reduced to USD 50 to 240/kWh by 2030 [219].

3.2. Nickel Cadmium (NiCd) batteries

The cell structure of nickel-cadmium batteries is more expensive than lead-acid batteries, which is why they cost more than lead-acid batteries. Despite the high performance and efficiency of nickel cadmium batteries, due to the high cost of these batteries, they are not very popular compared to lead-acid batteries. At present, the cost of using this technology is around USD 1000/kWh, which is about 4 times more than the cost of lead-acid batteries. We should bear in mind that due to the use of toxic substances in the structure of these batteries, which are extremely harmful to the environment, they should be disposed of correctly at the end of life by the manufacturer or by an approved organization, which in its kind can add to the cost of this technology. But due to the lack of an alternative technology with similar performance and features, there is still no alternative on the large and industrial scale, and they are used.

3.3. Nickel–Metal Hydride (NiMH) batteries

Given current hydride technology, the cost of a NiMH battery is estimated at about USD 170 - 640/kWh, which is relatively high [220]. This factor has prevented the expansion of these batteries' use as a power supply in various applications. The battery producing cost and the battery materials cost formed the cost of a battery. In terms of battery producing costs, production volume and technology used in the production process are influential. By increasing the production volume and improving the manufacturing technology, it is possible to reduce the cost of these batteries in the future. On the other hand, among the components of these batteries, negative electrodes with about 45% have the largest share in the total cost of materials. As a result, the design and use of inexpensive electrodes can reduce the cost of this technology. Reducing cobalt consumption in the manufacture of electrodes seems to be the most achievable option. It is expected to reduce USD 50/kWh of the cost.

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3.4. Lithium-ion batteries

In recent years, huge investments have been made to develop lithium-ion batteries due to their diverse and wide range of applications. At best, the energy density between 200 and 735 Wh/L can be considered for lithium-ion battery technology. The discharge depth of these batteries varies between 80 and 100% for different chemistries. Also, the cost of lithium-ion batteries for various chemistries is estimated at around USD 200 to USD 1260/kWh. Typically, as system size increases, cell components account for a smaller share of the cost. Because the power electronics and perimeter costs are higher for larger systems. Therefore, the cost of these systems depends on the size of the system. Due to the young technology of Li-ion batteries, we can reduce the cost of these systems in the future with the help of various drivers. Increased production capacity, wider supply chains, improved performance and design, improved materials, and the benefits of more operational experience are among the technical factors that can seriously reduce the costs of this technology. With the improvement of the mentioned factors, we can expect the costs related to the installation and commissioning of Li-ion batteries to be reduced from USD 200 to USD 1260/kWh in 2016 to USD 77 to USD 574/kWh in 2030. This forecast means that we will see a 54 to 61 percent reduction in the cost of this technology in the near future [219].

3.5. Flow batteries

The two properties of scalability and suitability for large-scale applications have put flow batteries in the spotlight and research, which has led to increased production experience. Currently, flow batteries have an energy density between 15 Wh/L to 70 Wh/L. Due to this technology's special chemistries and designs, it is not predicted that by 2030, there will be major changes in their energy density. It is hoped that the round-trip efficiencies of these batteries will increase from 60 to 80 percent in 2016 to 67 to 95 percent in 2030. Also, the cost of flow batteries in 2016 is estimated between USD 315 and USD 1680/kWh, which is estimated to be reduced by two-thirds in 2030 (i.e., USD 108 to USD 576/kWh) [219]. Although using these systems requires more initial investment than other technologies, but flow batteries with a long lifetime (usually more than 10,000 full cycles), they can compensate for the difference in the long run. The electrolyte in these systems is the main factor in this long-term stability. To become a cost-effective solution for matching of intermittent renewable energy supply to demand, these flow batteries should retain most of their capacity over decadal time scales.

3.6. Pumped storage hydroelectricity

On a large scale, Pumped hydro can be the cheapest option available. Currently, between USD 2,000 and 4,000/kW are needed to invest in Pumped hydroelectricity technology²⁹. 15% of this capital is spent on pump-turbine devices, 60% is spent on civil infrastructure or dams and 25% is spent on other system components. Pumped hydro is a mature technology and has been used for many years. As a result, major advances in technology in terms of cost, structure, or efficiency in the coming years are far from expected. Even as environmental standards for electricity and energy production become stricter, costs may increase. As mentioned, due to the special nature of these systems, their costs are the site sensitive. Costs related to the design and construction of reservoirs, the purchase of required pumps, and other construction costs can vary in different projects. One way to use this technology at a lower cost is to upgrade existing dams by adding electric generators, which can store energy at the cost of less than USD 100 to 300/kW. The exploitation of abandoned mines, which are also less

²⁹ [IEA-ETSAP | Energy Systems Analysis](#)

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environmentally sensitive, can also help reduce costs. Generally, USD 50 to USD 150 per MWh is considered energy storage cost by using pumped hydroelectricity technology [221].

3.7. List of battery manufacturers

The following is a list of the largest and most popular battery manufacturers with the largest market share for solar energy storage.

Table A13. 1. List of battery manufacturers.

Battery manufacturer	Country of origin
CALB	China
Alpha ESS	China
Ampetus	China
BYD	China
Pylontech	China
GNB	Germany
Sony	Japan
NGK Insulators	Japan
Toshiba	Japan
Kokam	Korea
LG Chem	Korea
Samsung	Korea
Tesla	USA
EcoUlt	USA
Aquion	USA
Redflow	USA
SimpliPhi Power	USA
NEC Energy Solutions	USA
EnerDel	USA

4. Applications

4.1. Lead–acid batteries

Among the various kinds of energy technologies, the Lead-acid battery (LAB) system is considered a promising energy storage system because of certain major advantages such as low manufacturing cost, well-established technology, reasonable specific energy, high operational safety, reliability, long cycle life, easy to maintain, and possibilities of the higher amount of recyclability. Based on the numerous advantageous, LAB system has served as an essential energy storage system for various applications such as automobiles, hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs), stationary, industrial, aircraft and as an energy storage and release system for renewable energy systems like Photovoltaic (PV) applications.

The installation of photovoltaic systems in livestock production buildings is one of the sector’s efforts to make these installations sustainable. In this viewpoint, the LAB systems have considerable solution for storage the energy generated during the day. However, LAB systems can be found in other electrical devices that contribute to the operation and safety of these building, like emergency light and alarms systems.

Among the most internationally recognized use case for applications of Photovoltaic Systems, a dairy farm located at the region of SEBDOU south of Tlemcen, northwest of Algeria can be included. According to the relevant report, the photovoltaic system mounted was able to cover entirely the electricity consumption at the dairy farm using the electricity grid as storage element to be supplied in

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periods without solar energy. That is why the dairy farm energy profit decreased from 29.8 to 9.6 MWh/year. In addition, along the PV system life cycle the dairy farm makes a transition from an electricity consumer with a cost of 27017 € to an electricity producer with profit of 29633 €.

4.2. Nickel Cadmium (NiCd) batteries

The energy storage technologies can be used in a variety of applications ranging from short-term storage to long-term storage, along with low to high temperature applications. It is well known that the performance of a Nickel-Cadmium battery is based on the complex chemical and electrochemical phenomena involved in the battery.

Although, the high performance of Lead-acid batteries, sometimes is needed take into account other aspects of the system, such as maintenance costs, system reliability and useful battery life that makes NiCd batteries a suitable solution for use in remote control of game cars, photography equipment, and home power tools which need a lot of power quickly. In addition, large capacities and high discharge rates of the NiCd batteries, have allowed to use them on industrial applications for emergency backup power for aircraft avionics systems, nuclear power plants, and mass transit equipment. However, nickel cadmium batteries offer some advantages like their cycling ability, durability, long life, and reliability; that contribute to making them ideal too for photovoltaic applications.

4.3. Nickel–Metal Hydride (NiMH) batteries

The nickel metal hydride (NiMH) battery technology is well positioned to power the next generation of electronic devices. This battery provides a near-term answer to the demand for portable, rechargeable power sources which are lighter and smaller than nickel cadmium batteries. Commercially available NiMH batteries can substitute for nickel cadmium (Ni-Cd) batteries cell for cell, with almost: indistinguishable voltage characteristics, but provide 25 - 40 percent more energy and are free of environmentally undesirable cadmium.

NiMH cells are commercially available in cylindrical AA, 415 A, A, and 4/3 A sizes, as well as various small prismatic configurations and large prismatic cells for high-energy applications such as electric and hybrid vehicles, as well as spacecraft power. Besides, NiMH battery packs are finding immediate use in portable electronic applications such as laptop, notebook, and computers, cellular communication and consumer electronic devices such as camcorders.

4.4. Lithium-ion batteries

Energy storage technologies are promising tools to achieve a low-carbon future. Specifically, they allow for the decoupling of energy supply and demand, which can provide a valuable resource to electricity system operators. Currently, lithium-ion battery technology offer power solutions across the spectrum for energy storage solutions to portable energy solutions. Some of the most common applications are power backups of uninterruptible power supply (UPS), mobile, laptops and other used consumer electronic devices. At this last group beyond the majority Internet of Things devices used in advanced agronomic practices and the management of livestock buildings. Thus, there are sensors nodes for measuring environmental variables and productive parameters, and gateway node for connecting internet-based services.

On the other hand, the use of lithium-ion battery power for electric mobility constitutes another applications context among which are agricultural vehicles and machinery that promises to

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revolutionise the agricultural industry by lowering costs and improving production. From battery powered large tractors to autonomous small electric robots, battery and solar power are changing the face of agriculture.

4.5. Flow Batteries

Rapid and continuous exhaustion of the non-renewable resources has prompted researchers to focus on developing renewable energy resources to meet the increasing energy demand and to reduce the carbon footprint of electricity generation. However, the renewable energy sources are intermittent, and their use can create fluctuation in electricity generation, making them non-dispatchable. Energy storage systems are thus required to match the supply and demand. Flow batteries exhibits several desirable characteristics associated with an electrical energy storage system; these include good electrochemical reversibility, large storage capacity (multi-MWh/MW), deep discharge, high round-trip efficiency, active thermal management, and long cycle life when compared to other technologies. It can be recharged either conventionally or with mechanical refuelling at a suitable refuelling station, making it attractive for electric vehicles applications.

4.6. Pumped storage hydroelectricity

Pumped Storage Hydropower (PSH) is an energy storage technology of storing and producing electricity to supply high peak demands by moving water between reservoirs at different elevations. PSH systems represent over 99% of the total global installed capacity of energy storage technologies, with approximately 140 GW of installed capacity worldwide. The proper utilization of the locally available renewable energy (RE) sources in remote areas can be a cost-effective solution for a desirable clean, inexhaustible and environmentally friendly energy supply option.

PSH systems has been reported by the scientific community as a promising storage technology for RE-based power systems, which can supply power to remote areas economically, reliably, with environmentally friendly way. There are some success applications like the work of Bhattacharjee S, Nayak PK., where throughout the used oh PV/PHS configuration for hydroelectric power station was possible supply loss power and reduce the load fraction from 11% to 4.4%.

Generally, farmers store a large quantity of water in a reservoir for drip irrigation purpose. This large quantity of water has a high potential to produce electricity employing PHS system. The upper reservoir of the PHS is connected to the water source from where water is lifted, and the lower reservoir is connected to the irrigation system for supplying water to the cultivation land. Water is pumped to upper reservoir from the natural water channels and rivers during an off-peak hour at a low price. The system thus delivers irrigation water as well as electricity at a low price. Djelailia et al [222] proved the effectiveness of PHS use in the case of irrigation and electrical power supply to reduce fuel consumption and CO₂ emission in Algeria's remote areas.

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Part II: Energy efficiency solutions

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Appendix 14: Farming practices

1. Overview

Livestock buildings are energy consumers and despite the fact that energy consumption represents a small percentage of the production cost, it increases together with the automation and mechanization of the various processes [223], [224]. High energy efficiency on livestock farms means that simple efficiency measures can yield significant savings, especially in older buildings. Beginning from the identification of how much, where and when the energy is used, targeted measures can be taken towards an efficient energy consumption. This report, however, skips any structural (building) and most of equipment (heating, lighting, ventilation, etc.) improvements, and focuses onto energy efficient farming practices.

According to the proceedings of the European Forum on Livestock housing for the future [223], farming practices that promote the animal welfare promote the increase in production as well. Typical examples consist the increase in milk production when cows' cubicles are equipped with mattresses [225], the reduction of bulls' growth rates when they are hosted on too small spaces [226] and the reduction of veterinary costs if animals' health problems are more infrequent [227]. Apart from the quantity, the quality of products, essentially meat, can also be affected by stressful conditions on the farm and during transport to slaughter (e.g. veal meat) [228]. The quality of the produced products can also be affected by the housing as by altering the frequency of contacts between humans and animals or by facilitating or impeding the handling of them: e.g. a lack of loading facilities in the farm can increase the stress of bulls transported to slaughter and therefore, reduce the decline of meat pH [229]. In general, it can be observed that improvements in animal welfare are accompanied by improvements of performances, but such improvements increase the overall farm profits only when the benefits are higher than the costs. Representative examples are the mattresses for cows [230] and the appropriate handling of calves [231]. However, in the case of enlargement of space allowances, the benefits may not balance the costs, at least not when they are studied only from an economic point of view. More specifically, when improvements are made from a very poor situation to an average one, then it's more likely that costs are largely paid by benefits; whereas when improvements are made from an average to an excellent situation, the difference between benefits and costs may be lessened (Fig. A14. 1 [223]). However, this has to be supported by more empirical data.

Fig. A14. 1. Hypothetical relation between welfare improvements and resulting benefits or costs.

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An identification of the main energy efficient farming practices per type of farm has been carried out, and the selected practices are briefly presented in this document. The typical classification per type of farm is being followed, with the expected overlapping where practices do not differ.

2. Energy efficient farming practices per type of farm

2.1. Swine farms

The size of a husbandry unit affects the energy consumption as larger units tend to be associated with higher energy consumption per unit (per sow and/or pig produced). According to literature, this is partly justified by the level of automation and equipment used [223].

Heating

As explained in [232], heat must be provided to the younger pigs on a pig unit with the general principle to achieve a farrowing room temperature of 24 °C, once the first piglet is born in the room. When the youngest piglet in the farrowing room is over 2 days old, this should be reduced to a maximum of 20 °C. Uncontrolled heat loss should be minimised in order to save money and improve output. Pig heating pads can be utilized to supplement the heat source at farrowing rather than an infra-red bulb. Poor temperature control can lead to unnecessary overheating of pads, and this could result in wasted heating and ventilation energy, especially in the first two weeks after farrowing.

First stage weaners (i.e., approximately 7 kg to 17 kg live weight) also require a source of heat. Newly weaned pigs should initially be kept at 28 – 29 °C, with a reduction of approximately 2 °C in each week thereafter (room temperature). Key areas in weaners constitute the accurate control of heat pads and lamps and the enclosure of creeps to accurately control temperature, prevent heat loss and reduce heating requirements. Equipment wise, portable temperature/RH sensors and data loggers are a cheap but effective way of recording variations within the building. If a more accurate measurement of heat losses is pursued, then a thermal imaging survey is suggested [232].

Ventilation

Heating and ventilation efficiency are closely related. Pig houses are ventilated to control the levels of gases (e.g., carbon dioxide, ammonia, methane, hydrogen sulphide) and airborne pathogens in the pigs' environment and therefore achieve good performance in terms of growth rates and feed conversion efficiencies. It is mandatory that airflow can be properly controlled without being influenced from draughts or leaks.

In the weaner and finisher section of pig farms the main energy consumers are ventilation and feeding systems. The feeding system consumes more energy if it's a liquid one and the ventilation system chosen is Automatically Controlled Natural Ventilation (ACNV). On the other hand, if the feeding system is an augured wet/dry system and the ventilation system is fan-powered with restricted inlets, then the consumption pattern may be reversed [232].

Environment quality

As stated in [233], the quality of the environment in farms is a significant factor because animal welfare, productivity and, therefore, economic performance, depend on it. Certain environmental parameters in farms are usually controlled methodically and regularly (e.g., temperature, humidity) but others, like the concentration of gases like environmental ammonia, are not. Gases must be present in the environment in concentrations that do not compromise animal health and ammonia is

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particularly important. Nowadays, the high density of animals leading to difficulties in generating adequate ventilation in combination with the high protein diets causes ammonia (NH₃), being accumulated and generating problems.

Ammonia originates from the decomposition of organic matter such as urine and faeces and is one of the most harmful gases found in farms causing significant economic losses. It is highly soluble, and it evaporates quickly decreasing the air quality. Its dispersion is favoured by high humidity and temperature. It is an irritant gas, which means it damages the respiratory tract of animals. Its effect on the tracheal mucosal surface ranges from paralysis to total loss of the cilia of the epithelial cells, including necrosis of the mucosal epithelium. The type and degree of the lesions depends on the concentration of ammonia in the environment and the exposure time. In swine farms, apart from respiratory diseases, death of new-borns, pneumonia and more, it can also increase the stress of the animals leading to immunosuppression and the consequent economic loss [233].

Creep areas

Enclosing creep areas allow thermal environment to be better regulated and will reduce heat loss. Besides saving energy, enclosed creeps improve piglet comfort and help reducing the heating effect of lamps on the sows. Cooler sows have higher feed intakes and thus increased milk production. Different approaches range from fully sealed and insulated boxes to open-sided areas with a cover which incorporates a small tip, helping retain the heat while ensuring visibility to the piglets. Creep areas typically use 8 kWh per pig produced, enclosing creeps can reduce this in half [234], [235].

Feed and nutrition

There are numerous studies about animal feed in the literature. Feed cost represents around two thirds of the production costs for fattening pigs [236] and 15 – 17% of the production costs for sows and their litters until weaning [237]. Consequently, nutrition is a major mechanism for improving the sustainability of pig production. Reducing the use of feed would reduce feed cost, and consequently nutrient excretion. It can also influence product quality: lean-to-fat ratio, fat quality, and the homogeneity of products. Currently most of fattening pigs are group-housed and fed based on the average pig requirements of the room or the pen, resulting in some pigs being overfed and other underfed [238]. Sows are usually fed two diets, one restrictively during gestation and the other during lactation [237] both based on an average sow's requirements [239].

Precision feeding is one way to better consider individual variability in nutrient requirements within a group. It involves using technology to provide the right amount of feed, with the right composition and at the right time, to a group of animals or to individuals [236]. Precision feeding aims to improve characterization of individuals (feed intake, growth potential, body condition, physical activity, health, etc.) or small groups to better adapt the quantity, quality and timing of feed supplied to them. It also aims to improve efficiency by reducing farm costs, reducing excretion, and monitoring quality (Fig. A14. 2 [239]). Applying precision feeding and doing so accurately requires assessing the nutritional potential of feed ingredients and nutrient requirements of each animal to formulate balanced diets accurately to minimize nutrient deficiency or excess [236,239].

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Fig. A14. 2. Principles of precision feeding.

As highlighted, precision feeding would improve feed and nutrient efficiency³⁰. Improving feed efficiency is a major objective to enhance pig production sustainability in terms of economy and environment [240]. The main environmental impacts of pig production originate from feed production [241] and from manure excretion and emissions during pig farming [242,243]. Strategies to improve feed efficiency include genomic selection and intestinal microbiota manipulation, removal of external stressors (e.g. climate stress) and guarantee of adequate nutrient supply (via empirical or factorial estimation of animals' requirements) [239]. Also in correlation to the paragraph about Environment quality, it should be mentioned particularly for the climate stress that in a dirty environment measured through air quality (amount of ammonia, CO₂ and dust), pigs' feed intake has been found to decrease of 100 g/kg compared to a cleaner environment, especially for individually housed pigs [239,244,245].

As for the distribution of the feed, it is responsible for varying levels of energy consumption in livestock units. Distributing feed in the form of a mash is associated, on average, with a higher level of energy consumption than dry feed (1,111 kWh and 938 kWh per sow per year, respectively). This is due to the fact that mash requires more powerful motors to be distributed and also, higher volumes must be moved in comparison to dry feed. Additionally, the number of distributions also has an impact on the energy consumption of feeding systems. Distributing feed in the form of a mash is often associated with a higher number of daily distributions [223]. It should be noted that fitting variable speed pumps to wet feed but also waste equipment can cut feed distribution costs by 30-50% [232].

2.2. Dairy farms

Dairy farms typically require more energy for day-to-day operations than other livestock facilities, especially daily kWh of electricity for milking, cooling and storing the milk. In general, the results of dairy farm energy assessments show that operations with large herd sizes typically have greater energy needs and greater energy savings potential than smaller dairies. However, like all farms, the specific energy demands of each dairy are unique. In particular, the configuration of the milking system impacts energy consumption; number of milking units in the parlour and level of vacuum needed to operate and clean them. Three key areas for improving energy efficiency during the daily milking routine are milk cooling, water heating, and vacuum pumps. When combined, these three factors account for

³⁰ Feed efficiency (FE) is the ratio of mean daily weight gain to mean daily feed consumption over a given period [345].

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approximately half of the energy consumption on dairy farms [246] or for 20 – 30% of the electricity consumption on a typical farm according to [247].

Milking process (Choosing energy efficient equipment)

The milking process consists of harvesting milk from the dairy cow and transporting the milk to a bulk tank for storage. This process can take place one or two or more times per day and most dairies schedule their lactations for a continuous milk supply throughout the year. On average, milking utilizes 18% of the electrical energy use on a dairy farm [248].

The vacuum pump operates during milking and equipment washing and is often the primary electrical energy user. Vacuum pumps become less efficient as the vacuum level increases [249]. Therefore, operating the vacuum pump at lower vacuum levels conserves energy. Sizing the vacuum pump to meet the needs of the milking and washing system can reduce capital costs for equipment, reduce energy operating costs during the life cycle of the pump and ensure that the pump is performing properly. The size of the vacuum pump is dependent on all of the components of the system that admit air during operation. Pumps are generally sized by accounting for the amount of air admitted into the milking system during the milk harvest plus a 50% reserve to account for accidental air admittance and the wear and tear of parts [250].

A variable frequency drive (VFD), also referred to as a variable-speed drive (VSD) or adjustable-speed drive, gauges the amount of vacuum suction needed in the parlour and adjusts the speed of the pump motor to deliver only the amount of suction needed. The energy savings comes from the reduced demand of the vacuum pump (by eliminating the amount of air that would be admitted through a regulator, the motor uses less horsepower). A VFD can reduce vacuum pump electric use by 50 to 60%, assuming a power requirement of 0.25 HP per milking unit during milking. In addition, lowering the vacuum pump's RPMs can extend its life as there will be less wear and maintenance costs [249], [251].

Milk cooling

Cooling milk accounts for most of the electrical energy consumption on a dairy farm. Milk needs to be cooled from its harvested temperature of 35 - 37 °C, to 3 °C to maintain high milk quality and low bacterial count [252], [253]. Heat exchangers cooled by well water, variable-speed drives on the milk pump, refrigeration heat recovery units and scroll compressors are all energy conservation technologies that can reduce the energy consumed in the cooling system.

Installing a properly sized precooler can reduce refrigeration energy consumption by about 60% [254]. A properly sized well water heat exchanger can reduce milk temperatures to within 5 to 10 degrees of the groundwater temperature. Higher efficiency for precooling can be achieved with a 1-1 ratio of coolant to milk flow and by using the largest water lines possible in order to maximize the coolant flow. Other factors that determine the energy and economic savings of a precooler include herd size, number and size of compressors, type of coolant used and the age of the bulk tank. An added benefit of using water for precooling is that it can afterwards be used for livestock drinking water. Cows depend on drinking water to produce milk and prefer warm water to cold. The warm water can also be used to perform other tasks, such as washing and heating.

A variable-speed milk transfer pump can reduce energy use by slowing the flow rate of milk through the heat exchanger. A lower and more continuous milk flow rate through the heat exchanger increases

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the coolant-to-milk ratio and results in greater milk cooling. Milk can be cooled by an additional 15 to 20 °C by installing a variable-speed milk transfer pump [255], [251].

During the process of cooling milk, heat is rejected from the condenser coil of the refrigeration system. It is possible to recover this by passing the hot refrigeration gas through a heat exchange system which is immersed in water. A water temperature of over 50 °C can be achieved by using this technique. The water heating system needs to be carefully configured so that the heat recovery can deliver the maximum benefit without compromising the operation of the milk cooling system. Depending on the number of cows being milked, the water storage tank should be sized to provide enough hot water for one milking [235], [252].

The function of a compressor is to compress the cold, low-pressure refrigerant gas from the evaporator to a high-pressure, high-temperature state for condensing. The three types of refrigeration compressors used for milk cooling on dairy farms are the reciprocating, scroll and discus. The reciprocating compressor is the most common and can be either open type, hermetic or accessible hermetic. The scroll and discus compressors are newer and more efficient than reciprocating compressors. Research has shown that replacing a failed reciprocating compressor with a new scroll compressor can reduce milk cooling costs by 20% because of a reduction in the electrical demand [249], [251], [253], [256].

Water heating

As presented in [252], hot water is essential for producing high-quality milk on dairy farms and is primarily used for cleaning milking systems. The amount of hot water required varies from farm to farm and depends on the size of the milking herd and the type and size of the milking system.

Hot water is generally produced by water heaters that use either fuel oil, natural or propane gas, solar energy or electricity. There are several ways to reduce the amount of energy used for heating water. Whether using a direct or indirect water heater, overall efficiency is determined by the combustion efficiency of the fuel source and the amount of heat loss from the storage tank, known as standby loss. A direct water heater combines the water storage tank and the heating element. The storage tank in an indirect water heater contains a heat exchanger that is connected to a separate boiler unit. Insulating the storage tank and connecting pipes can reduce standby losses for both types of water heaters. The sides and top of an electric water heater and the sides of gas and oil water heaters can be insulated.

Proper water temperatures are essential for cleaning milking equipment. Using warm or cold water when possible, can help reduce energy costs.

Finally, using a control device for electric water heaters can reduce electricity use during periods of expected increases in demand above the average supply level, also known as peak demand. Time clocks provide a simple and cost-effective way to control water heaters. Shifting electrical loads to off-peak or low demand hours and off-peak utility rates not only ensures farmers of having hot water at a reasonable cost, but also benefits the utility provider by allowing direct control of the energy demand on their system [252].

Manure management

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Manure management affects hygiene, animal welfare, work organization and costs on dairy farms [257,258]. Using recycled separated manure solids (RSMS) as bedding for loose housed dairy cows is considered cost-effective because it avoids the purchase of bedding material. This practice is adopted by several dairy farms in USA and by a few modern dairy farms in Italy, although there are some objections from farm advisors and veterinarians. The objections regard the high bacterial populations in bedding material that would in their turn influence the level of bacterial counts on udder surface, particularly on teat ends, and increase the risk of mastitis [223].

As concluded in [223], the main advantage of RSMS for bedding is the low material cost which is zero if free available on farm. In this case, the estimation of cost savings is about 43.6 € cow⁻¹year⁻¹ with reference to labour, machine and material average costs in Emilia Romagna. The drawback of this practice, however, is the high capital spending on the mechanical separator. This is why the purchase of a liquid manure separator for producing manure solids as bedding material is only worthwhile for relatively large farms or for collective use.

Feed

As in pigs, there are numerous studies regarding cows' feeding and nutrition. In general, there are two ways to improve feed efficiency (FE). One is to increase milk yield with the same dry matter intake, and the other is to decrease dry matter intake and maintain the same milk yield. Many diet modifications that increase milk yield will also increase feed efficiency. As the cow produces more milk, the proportion of nutrients used for maintenance becomes smaller. In other words, the fixed costs of the animal are spread out over more pounds of milk, making the animal more cost and energy efficient. Once the fixed costs are achieved in a dairy cow, producing additional milk takes less energy and protein.

An added benefit to increasing cows' feed efficiency is that fewer nutrients will be excreted in manure, so feed efficiency affects both economic and environmental efficiency. This is of considerable importance to dairy farms struggling with manure application management.

However, as dry matter intake increases there is a decrease in feed digestibility, and the cow becomes somewhat less efficient at extracting energy from the ration. This decrease in digestibility grows larger as intake increases and becomes a real issue in high producing dairy cows with high intakes. Therefore, it is important to optimize rather than maximize dry matter intake (DMI) in the cow. In many situations getting more dry matter intake in a high producing dairy cow is an economically sound practice. However, in some circumstances the cost of having a more energy dense or digestible diet may be more expensive than the return from increased milk. This would result in a lower income over feed cost and would not be advised [259].

The key factors to improve dairy feed efficiency vary from study to study but the following general principles are identified [259–261]:

- Higher FE values can be achieved by reducing days in milk as cows direct more nutrients to milk production at the expense of growth and weight gain. Cows losing body condition or body reserves will have high FE values as these nutrients can be captured as higher milk yield.
- Lower FE values can be caused by the age or lactation number (first lactation cows) as young cows divert nutrients to growth in mid and late lactation. Expected FE values for young cows are 0.1 to 0.2 units lower than mature cows.

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- Pregnancy reduces FE values as the foetus' requirements increase during late gestation. This impact, however, is small.
- Fresh cows (less than 21 days in milk) may have FE values below 1.2 if cows achieve higher DMI (desirable) relative to milk yield. If FE values are over 1.4, cows could be mobilizing excessive body condition (undesirable) which also will be reflected in high milk fat test (undesirable).
- Lower FE values are observed in cows that gain body weight as nutrients are stored as body condition or fat. This decline in FE must occur if cows lose body weight in early lactation. Lower FE values in late lactation can be desirable. Future FE values can be adjusted if average daily gains are available (daily weights).
- Based on Journal of Dairy Science data (2002 to 2004), as NDF (Neutral Detergent Fibre) percent in the ration's dry matter increased, FE declined from 1.8 to 1.4. FE values remained constant at 35% NDF and above.
- FE values will be increased by higher digestible forages (higher forage quality) as more nutrients are available for productive functions. Dry matter digestibility (DMD) and NDF digestibility (NDFD) tests will be useful benchmarks that will impact FE.
- Stimulating rumen fermentation while stabilizing the rumen environment will improve nutrient and fibre digestibility. Rumen acidosis will reduce FE values because digestibility has been reduced.
- FE values will be reduced by excessive heat and cold stress and walking distances as more nutrients are needed for maintenance requirements.
- FE values can be improved by feed additives such as rumen buffers, ionophores, yeast cultures, and fermentation/digestion aids; and silage inoculants as they can improve digestion and/or nutrient availability.
- FE values can be improved by injecting bST (Bovine somatotropin) as cows divert more nutrients to milk production.

Overall cow comfort

Cow comfort depends almost entirely on the barn environment, including clean and soft stalls, comfortable footing, as cows walk on their toes, fresh air, clean water, and good visibility. In terms of energy consumption, cow comfort depends on proper ventilation, livestock watering and good lighting [253].

2.3. Poultry farms

Poultry production is an important sector within the animal production industry, and energy use in this sector has increased with the population and standard of living. These factors have encouraged an increase in energy inputs to maximize growth, feed efficiency and profitability, to minimize labour-intensive practices, or both [262].

Feed

The highest energy input in poultry farms is the animal feed. Feed should be provided according to optimal consumption rates and should be composed of a low-protein formula. Although there is a difference between layer and broiler production in terms of the feed formula, in both types it must contain sufficient energy, minerals, protein, vitamins and water to supply vital functions and egg or meat production. The amount of energy contained in feed is generally expressed in units of energy per

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kg of feed that can be metabolised (e.g. kJ kg^{-1}) [263], [264]. However, the research for the nutritional requirements of poultry is an ongoing effort. A majority of scientific articles on poultry research focuses on improving the understanding of bird nutrition, both for fundamental knowledge of nutrition and for direct application to the industry [265].

Equipment

In some poultry production systems processes such as the supply of feed and water to the animals have been systematized through equipment and machinery for these tasks. On one side this machinery (feeders and feed distribution system) has partly increased the energy consumption of the units but on the other, it has allowed an exact management in the quantities of feed supplied, thus avoiding its waste or possible deficiencies at a certain time. Likewise, the management of water through automatic mechanical systems avoids wasting it and reduces the problems associated with beds with excess humidity (which favour the appearance of diseases). Another process that can be systematized in a similar way is the collection of eggs through an automatic conveyor belt, making egg collection faster and safer. Therefore, while the aforementioned technologies require energy to operate, they greatly contribute to the optimization of the processes.

Another energy efficient measure, equipment wise, is the utilization of brooding curtains. Brooding curtains allow chicks to stay warm while restricting them to a smaller area of the house, without the expense of heating the entire house. To perform efficiently they should form a tight seal along the ceiling, walls and floor [266].

Environment quality

Significant energy efficiency measures constitute also (a) the reduction of the amount of ammonia in the litter and (b) the avoidance of water losses through damaged pipes or other sources, which increase the relative humidity and alter the stability of the environment. As in swine farms, high ammonia levels can increase the susceptibility of animals mainly to respiratory, but also to non-respiratory diseases [233]. Additionally, high concentrations of ammonia increase the animal stress which can lead to immunosuppression and therefore, higher risk of suffering from infections with the consequent economic loss.

2.4. General

Even if it does not consist a farming practice as defined in the beginning of this report, regular cleaning, checks and good equipment maintenance will heavily contribute to optimising the energy performance on all the aforementioned types of livestock farms [223].

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Appendix 15: Barn monitoring and advanced control strategies

1. Technical description

The equipment needed for the smart control system are the following:

- (1) General environmental sensing equipments collect environmental data in order to (i) be able to use it in (near) real-time or near real-time and develop a smart control system to optimize the microclimate, in terms of indoor air quality and thermal environment, and (ii) collect baseline data that will then be compared with the environmental conditions inside the livestock buildings after the adoption of the smart control system and RES installations, to evaluate, assess and compare the “before” and “after” conditions.
- (2) Energy consumption equipment measure and monitor energy consumption of livestock buildings.
- (3) Weather stations collect weather data in order to be able to forecast the local microclimate and better assess the actions that need to be performed in order to maximize the self-consumption of the local RES, by forecasting for example the power generated by the PVs and PVTs.
- (4) Gateway and consumables ingest all real-time data to the cloud platform for users to remotely monitor and produce useful analytics to assist in their everyday operations and farm management.

1.1. Working principle

The working principles for each equipment type is described below:

1.1.1. General environmental sensing

The monitoring devices that retrieve various environmental data are using different sensing technologies that are described below. The concept of the sensors could be simplified into 3 main categories:

Variable resistance load sensors have a variable resistance and measure the electric current or electric load to calculate the different values for the sensing value according to the ohmic value of the resistor that is changing according to the sensing value.

Electrochemical sensors have the same working principles as the resistive load ones, but the variable resistance is changing its ohmic value according to a chemical component that is very sensitive to the desired measured value. The sensor has a membrane on top of the sensor housing and the desired Gas finds its way into the outlet and by means of gas diffusion an electrochemical reaction occurs when the gas reaches the working electrode. The type of reaction is either oxidation (e.g., Metal oxide) or a reduction according to the gas type.

The Optical sensing devices are based on converting the light rays into electronic signals; these sensors measure the quantity of light and translate it into a readable form. The sensor acts as a photoelectric trigger when a change occurs and it either increases or decreases the electrical output.

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1.1.2. Energy consumption

For electric energy consumption, simple energy consumption meters and energy analyzers are the 2 options. We investigated 2 verticals:

- a) **Inline energy monitoring equipment:** a vast number of models can be used, will be selected according to the maximum energy consumption per line.
- b) **Non – intrusive monitoring equipment** utilizes Current transformers (CT) to acquire the energy readings. The accuracy class needed is above class B meaning an accuracy of +-5%.

We may enable energy monitoring of different devices working at a stable state in a non- stop mode, using hour counters, while integrations of already installed energy and gas monitoring systems may also be possible utilizing non-intrusive optical flow meter sensors.

1.1.3. Consumables and Gateway

The Gateway utilises various communication protocols and enables high security features for its communication with the IoT platform that will offer the data to the users. The Gateway hardware we selected is lightweight, cost-effective and is utilising as its based on the Raspberry Pi platform that has adequate processing power and memory to meet the arisen requirements.

1.1.4. Weather station

The IP65 rated Libelium weather station contain multiple sensors that could measure the atmospheric conditions (wind speed, wind direction, solar radiation, air temperature, humidity and pressure, precipitation and ect.) spontaneously and transmit them at predefined frequency.

1.2. Selection

More details about the selection of the sensors will be found in D3.3

1.2.1. General environmental sensing

General specification for the environmental sensing includes specifications in order to ensure that the installed sensors will endure the harsh environment according to the different attributes, livestock type and sensing values. Some sensors need to be mounted close to the ground level of the livestock facility, meaning that it is required to have a protective casing that can endure water pressure washing, oxidation etc. Additionally, all sensors must be CE (Conformité Européene') compliant and have a warranty of more than 6 months. All sensors will work with the Modbus TCP / RTU protocol.

1.2.2. Energy Consumption

In order to be able to evaluate the penetration of the different RES units and the benefits of each technology, there is the need to monitor the energy consumption in terms of electric energy and gas consumption within the farm to cover daily needs.

1.2.3. Gateway and Consumables

The most important requirement regarding the Gateway is to be IoT ready, meaning that it is able to interact though remote services. Meanwhile, it should be able to utilise different communication protocols seamlessly, is versatile and can be expanded accordingly.

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1.2.4. Weather Station

The weather station will retrieve measurements regarding the different environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, pressure, wind speed, solar radiation etc. The pilots are distributed in sparse and very different environmental zones; therefore, the requirements to select the different units has to do that the equipment must be able to withstand the cold environmental conditions of -40 °C in Germany and the warm environmental conditions of +35 °C in Greece.

1.3. Installation and maintenance

Regarding the different equipment categories and the respective installation actions and maintenance needs:

1.3.1. General environmental sensing

Regarding the installation of the various environmental sensors that will operate using the Modbus protocol, a single twisted pair UTP (Cat 5e or above) cable will be used for the RS-485 communication line that needs to run along all spots where we will connect the EVIKON Modbus sensors. In each installation spot there is the need for a stable power supply, preferably a new powerline for the sensor network should be created and connected directly to the power supply of the sensors, thus avoid having actual plugs. The sensors must not be powered on until the monitoring is ready to initiate, as the degradation will be faster. Then, PLEGMA technical personnel will strip the RS-485 wires and make the appropriate connections to the sensors, as we need to follow the daisy chain wiring scheme in order to verify the network robustness.

In order to enable the different sensors to be present for the whole project duration, we chose (wherever possible) to utilise metal oxide-based sensors due to their increased lifetime (approx. 5 years) and not electrochemical ones that would last for approx. 6-12 months and would need to be replaced or calibrated using a specialized procedure that heavily increases the costs. More specifically, the various sensors have different needs and specifications in terms of maintenance and calibration intervals. Digital sensors do not need any calibration. Optical (NDIR) sensors need a calibration after 5 years. Metal oxide semiconductor sensors need calibration after 12-24 months, whereas electrochemical sensors which measure specific gases such as oxygen and hydrogen sulphide, may need calibration every 6-12 months. In order to perform the calibration of the sensors, a representative of the specific company that has provided the sensors must visit on-site and perform the calibration.

1.3.2. Energy Consumption

The energy consumption equipment installation procedure depends on the type of the equipment that will be selected. In any case, it is a quite straightforward procedure that may be performed by an electrician, and no maintenance is required after the installation. Then, in order to collect the data, PLEGMA personnel will handle all the communication of the sensor with the gateway.

1.3.3. Consumables and Gateway

The gateway installation includes the software installation that will be led and supported by PLEGMA, and the actual installation of the gateway unit in the facility. The installation spot should provide also a monitor as the gateway will also act as a human machine interface, and it should be performed in a place that may provide power and internet availability. In case the installation spot is exposed to

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extreme conditions (dust, high/low temperatures), then the gateway must be protected by being installed in a circuit breaker, or another facility room. No planned maintenance is required.

1.3.4. Weather Station

The selected Libelium weather stations must be installed in spaces where there is internet availability. No power is required as the weather stations will operate using a battery and a small solar panel. No planned maintenance actions are required.

2. Performance

2.1. Factors affecting performance

A few environmental factors (temperature, humidity or liquid, corrosive gases) can affect the sensors' power operation, sensing operations and radio communication. Meanwhile, the distance from sensor-to-sensor and the wireless gateway could affect the data transmission.

2.2. Stability / continuity

The local climate does not have a direct impact on the sensors, as they have been selected to withstand the climate conditions of all 4 pilot locations.

2.3. Operation strategies

Open-Loop Control is the simplest, as it is the easiest to implement (just perform an action and hope it works) leading to minimal computational cost. On the downside, it does not include feedback to improve performance, leading to reduced control performance, while also not being robust.

Proportional, Integral, Derivative (PID) Control is the most popular controller in industry, as it is easy to implement and robust. The PID control uses error rejection. Each time the PID is evaluated, it checks the difference (error) between the set point value and the true value. Then, the controller changes the input (control action) to get the true value to as close to the set point as possible. PID control is easy to implement, requires low computational costs, is robust and corrects the errors through feedback. On the other hand, it does not optimize the process, is difficult to achieve optimal parameterization, needs often tuning and one controller can only be applied to a single control action.

Model Predictive Control (MPC) is a more advanced one, being very popular in industry, as it is the best control achievable with high optimization levels if the model used during implementation is highly accurate. In order for the MPC to be used, the process must be modelled, include a cost function, and sometimes include various constraint functions. During evaluation, the MPC essentially looks into the future and identifies all possible combinations of inputs and their cost of implementation. Then, it picks the combination with the lowest cost and recommends that as the most effective plan to reach the set point. In case constraints are provided, the controller ensures that they are not violated. The accuracy of the forecasting model is extremely important because MPC looks into the future and makes control actions based on it. The users can easily understand the reasons why the controllers recommend certain actions by analysing the models, which is a significant advantage over any Artificial Intelligence (AI) powered control. On the other hand, MPC requires high level of engineering expertise to implement, identification of highly accurate models which will be adapted and updated due to change of operating conditions (e.g., Different seasons).

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Reinforcement Learning (RL) Control is very similar to MPC. Its main difference is that it continually learns as time goes on so there is no need to update its decision-making criteria manually. First, a simulation is performed to train the RL controller by showing it what happens when certain actions are performed during certain scenarios and afterwards the RL is ready for operation, where it will continue to learn and adapt. The model identification is relatively easier than using MPC providing near-optimal control, but there is no understandability of the control selection, there is the need for historical data or simulation for training before implementation, and direct controls using RL may be too risky. RL is often acting as a supervisory role, advising the operators the best possible actions³¹.

2.5. Practical lifetime

Depend on selection, the practical lifetime of sensors could be up to 5 years, with the exception of sensors that might need replacement after 2-3 years.

3. Cost

3.1. Installation costs

The purchase costs vary depending on the manufacturer and specifications. The installation costs include common materials as well as the cost of the technician who will visit the farm and perform any necessary operations such as hole drilling, cables expansion etc.

3.2. Operation and maintenance costs

It is possible that at some time we might need to upgrade the gateway, e.g., installing an extra communication layer or additional processing power / RAM / storage. The sensors' operational costs are minimal as most of the sensors need a power consumption lower than 2 Watts.

As far as it concerns maintenance, different sensors have different needs and specifications in terms of maintenance and calibration intervals. Sensors for energy consumption, weather station and gateway do not need any maintenance or calibration. General Environmental Sensing need some calibration depending on their type. In order to perform the calibration of the sensors, a representative of the specific company that has provided the sensors must visit on-site and perform the calibration. The cost is around 200 € / sensor, but it varies from country to country and also on the number of sensors that need to be calibrated.

3.3. ROI/IRR/NPV/Payback Period

Return on investment cannot be defined as the above-mentioned equipment are considered as consumables.

3.4. List of brands/supplier

Bases on the technology requirements, varieties of supplier were approached. Such as Scientific Enterprises, EVIKON, Automation Technique, NESA SRL and UTECO for environmental sensors. For weather station, Libelium, Youshiko, Bresser and Scientific Enterprises are available. For energy meters, schneider, fludia, langyang, lovato were among the distributors assessed. Additional information and details will be found in D3.3.

³¹ <https://medium.com/@ruinian/controls-comparison-between-4-popular-control-strategies-d1f3a3b61eb1>

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4. Application

4.1. Existing non-farming applications

The concept of indoor environmental monitoring is widely applied in the commercial and industrial buildings to allow actions regarding the ventilation, optimal indoor condition as well as smart control of the different heating and cooling systems. In order to allow the smart control to take the wheel and increase efficiency in respect to reducing costs the area utilizes smart sensors to monitor the different environmental parameters. According to the case, the occupancy and other characteristics the IoT is enabling smart control towards heating and cooling.

Microclimate and nature-based solutions are tightly coupled as the conditions might affect the area and create floods, block roads from broken trees and other actions. Smart city monitoring aside from smart parking, traffic control is focused on weather monitoring to allow early detection of potential flooding, loss of property as well as sewage system problems. All of the previously mentioned use a set of sensors to monitor different values and through analysis and decision support for the maintenance and planning groups of the city as well as early information to the citizens.

4.2. Existing farming applications

Agriculture 4.0 is the new approach towards farm management and precision agriculture. The ability to harness the technology advancements from other industries, such as commercial building, IoT computer science etc. allowed the Agro sector to evaluate and adopt them. Agro 4.0 is utilizing low - cost sensors, actuators, microprocessors, nanotechnology, high-bandwidth cellular communication, cloud computing and artificial intelligence (AI).

Adoption of IoT solutions for agriculture is constantly growing. Cellular companies are seeking business opportunities in farm IoT applications. They are developing integrated systems that combine sensors and communication systems. IoT sensors and cloud computing will drastically improve the quality of data flow, which will, in turn, help farmers make better decisions.

The Agro4.0 applications are numerous and focused around different sectors of the Agro domain livestock, crops and heavy machinery is updated and enrich with new technologies and new applications using CPS and IoT. Some examples is continuous soil analysis to enable better crops and minimize investments on fertilizers and pesticides. New types of food and new types of monitoring devices are used in the livestock farming ranging from VR headsets to allow comfort to the livestock up to wearables and tracking technology to increase the livestock healthier upbringing. Environmental monitoring and microclimate analysis allows the farmers to take targeted actions towards data driven decisions regarding the optimum time for plantation, irrigation and harvesting of different crop and vegetables. Based on sensor data the farmers can plan and adapt to the new climate conditions to shift to alternative more profitable plants

4.3. Applications in Pilot farms

The installation plans of sensors in RES4LIVE pilot farms are shown in the below figures.

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Fig. A15. 1. Environmental sensors installation locations in LVAT farm.

Fig. A15. 2. General environment sensor (T&RH, NH3 and CO2) installed in ILVO farm.

Fig. A15. 3. Environmental sensors installation locations in AUA farm.

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Fig. A15. 4. Energy consumption and weather sensors installed in GOLI farm.

4.4. Best practices/typical combinations with other technologies

Advanced technologies are integrated thanks to the evolution of IoT into existing farming and livestock management practices to increase production efficiency and quality of agricultural products. These smart technologies have proven to increase the quality of crop yield and reduce the environmental footprint from the agricultural sector [267].

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Appendix 16: Smart ventilation

1. Technical description

Traditionally, the pig houses are designed as long and narrow buildings and are mechanically ventilated. In order to develop a more sustainable pig production buildings, a new building type of pig houses installed with hybrid ventilation system, which combines mechanical and natural ventilations, has been proposed by a Danish company, AgriFarm Innovation A/S. This innovative design includes saving the energy consumed by fans via natural ventilation, saving the labour work and increasing daylighting via an innovative design of the building configurations.

1.1. Working principle

The hybrid ventilation combines mechanical and natural ventilation, which can run individually at different period of the year or run parallel. We take cattle building as an example to illustrate the principle of hybrid ventilation. In Fig. A16. 1 (b), the windows on the side walls, on the roof and ridge are auto controlled and they are one of the most important parts of natural ventilation by supplying or exhausting the air to or out of the building. In Fig. A16. 1 (c), there are air channels, named as partial pit ventilation system (PPV), under the crate (where cattle rest) to collect the highly concentrated pollutant air. These channels (shown in Fig. A16. 1. (a) 2, 3) are connected to the central channel (shown in Fig. A16. 1 (a) 4), which finally meets at the acid air cleaner as shown in Fig. A16 (a). 1. Experimental tests conducted in winter and summer have shown that 64% ammonia emissions can be collected by PPV system in this tested cattle building. More detailed can be found in reference [268].

(a) A photo to show the cattle building inside, 1 – acid cleaner, 2, 3 – exhaust air channels to draw air from the slurry pit, 4 – central exhaust air channel connecting the acid cleaner and the exhaust air channels such as 2 and 3.

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(b) A photo to show the cattle building with automatically controlled windows

(c) Front view of a cattle building with hybrid ventilation, the area marked in red ellipse is the fresh air supplied to the slurry pit and the area marked in blue ellipse is the exhaust channels to draw air out of the building and deliver the air to the cleaner

Fig. A16. 1. Principle of hybrid ventilation system installed in a cattle building.

The PPV exhausting air system can also be combined with mechanical air supply system to the slurry pit, as shown in Fig. A16. 2. The supplied fresh air form an air layer between the slatted floor and the slurry surface to avoid concentrated pollutant air flowing upward. Although cattle barns are generally ventilated by natural ventilation, it is expected that the hybrid ventilation is probably adopted more frequently in the future in order to reach the goal of CO₂ neutral by 2050 in Europe by collecting ammonia and methane emissions.

It is probably noticed that the building design is very different from the traditional cattle barn which is usually long and narrow. The proposed cattle barn with hybrid ventilation system is more squared (wider) compared to the traditional cattle barns. This design, first, saves the labours in terms of route followed by cattle to the milking station, supply more daylighting to the barns with windows installed on the ridge and roof and ensure the hybrid ventilation system performing in a better way too.

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Fig. A16. 2. Illustration of the airflow patterns via the supplied and exhausted air channels (patented).

The hybrid ventilation systems have been installed in a few fattening pig production buildings (length in 50.0 m, width of each section in 22.0 m and height in 11.0 m) in Denmark and Sweden. One example of the building structure and hybrid ventilation system installed in a fattening pig production building in Denmark is shown in Fig. A16. 3 [269]. The air of natural ventilation is supplied or exhausted via auto-controlled windows (shown in Fig. A16. 3 (a)), which is similar to the cattle barn presented above.

(a) A photo of a confined fattening pig building with automatically controlled windows

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(b) A 3-D illustration of the fattening pig building with four sections and each section is independent.

(c) Side view of the confined fattening pig building for one section

Fig. A16. 3. Schemes of a fattening pig building installed hybrid ventilation system.

The PPV is installed below the solid floor at each pen, as shown in Fig. A16. 3 (b), to collect the concentrated pollutant air. This amount of air will enter into the air cleaner (two cylinders shown in Fig. A16. 3 (b)), which has been one of the products listed on the best available technologies in Denmark regarding the abatement of emissions from livestock productions.

This type of design including the building configuration and ventilation system can also be used in other type of animal buildings, e.g., piglets/ sows' buildings

1.2. Selection

Not applicable to this subsection.

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1.3. Installation and maintenance

Comparing to the traditional cattle barn with natural ventilation, there are some required installations and maintenances. The PPV systems are required to be installed below the crates where cattle rest and the fans to exhaust air from PPV channels are also needed. In order to automatically control the openings of hybrid ventilation system, the windows and motors are needed. The maintenance for the mechanical parts might be needed but those components are quite robust.

Comparing to the traditional fattening pigs, the number of fans with large capacity has been significantly reduced. The air supply inlets have been replaced by operable windows controlled by motors automatically.

2. Performance

2.1. Environmental impact

The hybrid ventilation system used in cattle barns has collected around 64% of ammonia emissions annually by PPV in the tested barn and around 20% of methane in summer. The ammonia emission and odour emission were collected by PPV in 74% and 75% respectively [270], which was obtained from experimental test conducted in a pig barn with the innovative building design and hybrid ventilation system.

2.2. Factors affecting performance

The hybrid ventilation system consists of natural and mechanical ventilation system. Due to the natural ventilation, the performance of hybrid ventilation system highly depends on the outdoor climate. In order to provide the proper indoor thermal environment in winter, it is important that the control system can control the openings appropriately, so that the animals will not suffer from cold stress. However, in summer it is also important to control the opening sizes to avoid the barns to be over ventilated so that the emissions can be collected by PPV more efficiently. The performance with current control strategies have been monitored for the last 10 years in cattle barn and 5 years in fattening pig barn by the company AgriFarm Innovation A/S, who has developed this system. Some analysis of outdoor climate parameters on the system performance can be found in the publication by [271].

2.3. Stability/continuity

The animal buildings installed with hybrid ventilation system generally requires a period of three to six months to minor adjust the control system so that the performance of the ventilation system can be ensured.

2.4. Operation strategies

The entire ventilation system is auto controlled by Intellifarm developed by Agrifarm Innovation A/S.

2.5. Practical lifetime

The components used in the hybrid ventilation system depend on the individuals provided by different companies, e.g., windows, motors, fans, concrete air channels. According to the experience of AgriFarm A/S, the windows have generally 15 – 20 years lifetime. It is not easy to give a number of how long the fans can last because they depend on the running frequency and hours as well as the maintenance.

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3. Cost

Overall, the vision of the innovative building design of the animal barns and the hybrid ventilation system is to decrease the energy cost in pig production by 60%, while achieve up to 50% gains in production profitability. Considering the reduction of ammonia emissions by 70% and odour emissions by 40% compared to traditional barn, the benefit brought by the system to society is invaluable.

3.1. Installation costs

Compared to the more traditional stable types, the additional cost of construction is the equivalent of DKK 130 – 150 per square meter. The increased construction price is caused by the establishment of PPV system below the solid floor.

3.2. Operation and maintenance costs

The hybrid ventilation system with Intellifarm control concept can save the operating costs of ventilation system significantly, where 1 or 2 fans are required comparing to 10 fans in traditional stables. This is equivalent to the reduced cost of ventilation by 1.50 - 2 kWh per produced pig. The price of electricity is different worldwide, but at 0.8kr per kWh, the cost is reduced by DKK 1.20 – 1.60 per slaughtering pig. The budget saved by ventilation system purely is limited but with the same manpower, more pigs can be produced at one time, which brings the interest to the farmers.

3.3. Cost savings

See above or it is difficult to provide the savings.

3.4. ROI/IRR/NPV/Payback Period

By installing hybrid ventilation system and the innovative building design, the number of footpaths per stable in Denmark can reach 25% ~ 50% without increasing the climate and environmental impact.

3.5. Funding schemes

The AgriFarm Innovation A/S has a close collaboration with many partners e.g., Aarhus University, Agrobusiness park, SEGES and has been involved in many large research projects supported by Innovation Fund, GUDP fund in Denmark. The AgriFarm Innovation A/S also received a project granted by EU horizontal 2020 (more details about the project can be found in this website <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/673453>).

3.6. List of brands/suppliers

AgriFarm Innovation A/S, Denmark.

4. Application

4.1. Existing farming applications

The hybrid ventilation system has been installed in a cattle building in Ringkøbing Denmark and four fattening pig production buildings in Denmark. It has also been installed in a few fattening pig production buildings in Sweden. More projects can be found on the website <https://agrifarm.dk/en/projects/>

4.2. Existing non-farming applications

Not applicable.

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4.3. Potential farming applications

There is a large potential to apply hybrid ventilation system in different type of animal buildings in a temperate climate. It can also be applied in warm climate if proper design of cooling systems can be implemented, and its control is combined into the Intellifarm system.

4.4. Status implementation in Europe

It is foreseen that the advantages of this system will be recognized and valued by more farmers in Europe. Currently, a few fattening pig production buildings adopted the innovative building design and hybrid ventilation system in Denmark and Sweden. In north Germany, there are also farmers who are willing to construct this type of pig production buildings. The size of the Agrifarm A/S is increasing, and this could be a good sign that the business is on track and more buildings with hybrid ventilation system and intellifarm control system can be constructed. The projects having been finished by Agrifarm Innovation A/S can be found at <https://agrifarm.dk/en/projects/>.

4.5. Best practices/typical combinations with other technologies

In warm/hot climate, the system is generally combined with high pressure cooling system if cooling is needed to mitigate the heat stress in animal barns. The cooling system has been used in the pig production buildings with the innovative building concept and the hybrid ventilation system.

Acknowledgement

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Appendix 17: Heating and cooling distribution systems

1. Technical description

1.1. Working principle

To guarantee proper indoor environmental conditions for animals in livestock buildings, heating/cooling is needed in some situations and is supplied via heating/cooling distribution systems. There are two common distribution systems, which are the air distribution system and the liquid distribution system.

1.1.1. Air distribution system

In many buildings, air is heated/cooled centrally to produce a desired temperature and humidity and then the heated/cooled air is distributed to the zones [272]. The air is typically conditioned in air handling unit (AHU). As shown in Fig. A17. 1 [273], common components in an AHU are dampers to control the exhausted and supplied air flows, a mixing chamber, one or more fans and heating or cooling coils. After the AHU, the air stream can be distributed to the different rooms. Since AHU is typically large, it is often located in a separate room, near the zones that are supplied with conditioned air.

Fig. A17. 1. Layout of a simple AHU.

Several aspects need to be considered when designing an air distribution system:

- Supplying air flow rate to different zones can be different due to the diverse thermal loads.
- The flow rates should be high enough to provide adequate mixing in the zone, but drafts should be avoided especially in cool outdoor climate.
- Fan power and noise need to be minimized.

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- Ducts are typically insulated to avoid losses. Additionally, this prevents condensation that can occur on the external surfaces of cold ducts.

1.1.2. Liquid distribution systems

In addition to air distribution system, liquid distribution system (sometimes called water distribution system or hydronic system) are available in industry. The liquid distribution system consists of a piping network through which liquid (e.g. water) is pumped to various locations [272]. The heated or cooled liquid is distributed via end-user components (e.g. underfloor heating, radiators, heating or cooling coils) to heat/cool the zones. In addition to the piping network and end-user components, pump is present and control valves are normally needed to regulate the flow.

Although water is the most common liquid, natural gas or fuel oil networks can also be installed in buildings to distribute the fuel to furnaces or boilers. Finally, refrigerants or steam can be circulated in buildings too for supplying heating and/or cooling. Different liquid distribution systems can be categorized based on the operating temperature, flow generation, pressurization, piping arrangement and pumping arrangement. A basic schematic of a hydronic heating system is shown in Fig. A17. 2 [273] as an example.

Fig. A17. 2. Schematic overview of a basic hydronic system.

1.2. Selection

To design and install a heating/cooling system, the designer has to consider several constraints. For example, the dimensions of heating/cooling system should fit the (limited) space allocated for the

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installation, and the diverse heating/cooling loads in different zones need to be provided. To select an air distribution system or a liquid distribution system will therefore depend on many parameters.

1.3. Installation and maintenance

To guarantee efficient operation of the heating/cooling system, maintenance is required. Valves and heat exchangers need to be cleaned regularly; filters should be replaced according to the user manual, and the quality of the fluids (e.g., refrigerant) might need to be monitored.

2. Performance

2.1. Environmental impact

Heating/cooling distribution systems themselves are not energy efficiency technologies. They should be applied in combination with other technologies. For example, the local heating/cooling can be used with a heat pump, which can utilize the heat from manure. This heat can warm the water, which is circulated in a heating distribution system to supply local heating for e.g., small pigs in cool outdoor climate. Another example of using the 'waste' heat is to transfer the captured heat from large size pigs to the area where piglets are reared via heating distribution system. To utilize the waste heat has a positive environmental impact.

To provide heating/cooling to different zones, some fluids need to be displaced. For this displacement, a pressure drop has to be overcome by fans or pumps where electrical energy consumption occurs. How the pressure drop can be determined in different types of distribution systems is described below.

2.1.1. Air distribution systems

As mentioned earlier, the flow rate supplied to a zone depends on the thermal load of that zone. However, higher flow rate leads to higher pressure drop. Therefore, larger duct sizes could be selected, but this leads to higher installation costs and generally are hindered by the limited installation space. A trade-off exists among pressure drop (considering energy savings), installation cost and limited installation space.

Pressure drop due to the viscous effect in a duct is calculated by Eq. (1), and the pressure drop to overcome the minor loss is calculated by Eq. (2).

$$\Delta p = f \frac{L}{D_H} \frac{\rho \dot{V}^2}{2} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta p = K_L \frac{\rho \dot{V}^2}{2} \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the air density (kg m^{-3}) and \dot{V} is the volumetric flow rate ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$). f , L and D_H in Eq. (1) represent the friction factor, the duct length (m) and the hydraulic diameter (m). Finally, in Eq. (2), K_L is a loss coefficient that depends on the type of fitting.

An overview of representative loss coefficients K_L can be found in Table A17.1. [273]. The pressure drops on Fig. A17. 3. are determined for a medium smooth tube. With increased roughness of the tube, also the pressure drop will rise. Therefore, an overview of typical tube roughness can be found in Table A17. 2 [272]. Finally, recommended design velocities (for industrial buildings) for air distribution systems are summarized in Table A17. 3.

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Table A17. 1. Loss coefficients for different types of fittings.

Type of fitting	K_L range
Circular duct, 90° smooth bend	0.1-0.2
Circular duct, 90° pleated bend	0.25-0.5
Rectangular duct, 90° bend	0.1-0.2
Bellmouth entrance to plenum	0.03-0.5
Expansion to plenum	0.05-0.3

Since the calculation of the friction factor in equation is not straightforward, the friction loss can be determined with pressure drop charts, e.g. shown in Fig. A17. 3 [273].

Fig. A17. 3. Friction loss as a function of volume flow rate.

Table A17. 2. Roughness heights for commercial air ducts.

Category	Duct material	Roughness (mm)
Smooth	Aluminium, uncoated carbon steel, PVC	0.03
Medium smooth	Galvanized steel with 1.2 to 3.6 m joints	0.09
Average	Galvanized steel with 0.76 m joints	0.15
Medium rough	Fibrous glass ducts or liners	0.9
Rough	Flexible ducts, coated liners	3.0

Table A17. 3. Recommended velocities for industrial buildings.

Component	Velocity (m/s)
Main ducts	6-9
Branch ducts	4-5
Branch risers	4
Fan outlets	8-12
Coils	3
Outdoor intakes	2.5

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To overcome the pressure drop when supply the air, one or more fans are installed in the system. The fans used in HVAC systems are typically either axial or centrifugal units [272]. An axial fan, as shown in Fig. A17. 4, has multiple propeller-shaped blades mounted on a hub. As the hub rotate, the air is propelled axially by the blades.

Fig. A17. 4. Schematic representation of an axial fan.

In Fig. A17. 5, a centrifugal fan can be seen. The flow enters axially at the centre of the impeller and is accelerate radially by the rotating blades.

Fig. A17. 5. Schematic representation of a centrifugal fan.

The electrical power used by the fan can be calculated by Eq. (3). In this equation, η_f and η_m are the efficiency of the fan and the motor respectively.

$$\dot{W}_{elec} = \frac{\dot{V}\Delta p}{\eta_f \eta_m} \quad (3)$$

In practice, the flow rate a fan can deliver (at a certain rotational speed) depends on the pressure drop it needs to overcome. Therefore, when selecting a fan for a specific application, it is necessary to find a fan whose characteristics match those of the system for the operating point [274]. This is illustrated in Fig. A17. 6 [274].

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Fig. A17. 6. Fan and system characteristics.

2.1.2. Liquid distribution system

The liquid distribution system is to supply the required liquid flow to each heat exchanger with optimized pressure drop and pumping power.

Eqs. (4), (5) and (6) are used to calculate the head loss (a term used in hydronic system instead of pressure drop) for water distribution system. Eq. (4) calculates the head loss due to viscous friction on the wall, with the friction factor given in equation 5. The head loss due to fittings is denoted by Eq. (6).

$$h_L = f \frac{L}{D_H} \frac{\rho \dot{V}^2}{2} \quad (4)$$

$$f^{-0.5} = 1.14 + 2 \log\left(\frac{D_H}{\varepsilon}\right) - 2 \log\left(1 + \frac{9.3}{Re\left(\frac{\varepsilon}{D_H}\right) f^{0.5}}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$h_L = K_L \frac{\rho \dot{V}^2}{2} \quad (6)$$

In Eq. (5), ε is the surface roughness of the walls (see Table A17. 4) and Re is the Reynolds number of the water. Using a representative friction factor of 0.02 to 0.03 is in practice usually sufficiently accurate to estimate head loss [Mitchell]. Several typical loss coefficients K_L can be found in Table A17. 5 [273].

Table A17. 4. Representative roughness values for different pipe materials.

Pipe material	Roughness (mm)
Smooth brass, lead, copper or plastic pipe	0.0015-0.03
Steel and wrought iron	0.04
Galvanized steel and iron	0.1-0.15
Cast iron	0.25
Fibrous glass product	1-3

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Table A17. 5. Representative loss coefficients for piping systems.

Type of fitting	K_L threaded	K_L flanged
Standard elbow	0.7-2.5	0.24-0.4
Tee (straight line)	0.9	0.08-0.26
Tee (branch line)	1.1-2.7	0.5-1.0
Gate valve	0.12-0.4	0.0-0.34

Similar to the discussion on fans in air distribution system, pumps are an essential component in liquid distribution system to overcome the pressure drop in the system. A pump needs to be selected to achieve the desired flow rate and pressure with optimal pumping power [272]. Pumps can be classified in three broad categories [273]: reciprocating, rotary and centrifugal pumps. Reciprocating and rotary pumps are positive displacement pumps, while a centrifugal pump is a turbomachine. In HVAC systems, the centrifugal pumps are most used. A schematic representation of a centrifugal pump is shown in Fig. A17. 7. This is very similar to the design of the centrifugal fan from Fig. A17. 5.

Fig. A17. 7. Schematic representation of a centrifugal pump.

When selecting a pump, one needs to match the characteristics of the pump to those of the system for the desired operating point, as can be seen in Fig. A17. 8 [273].

Fig. A17. 8. Balancing of pump and system characteristics in water distribution systems.

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2.2. Factors affecting performance

The outdoor climate has a strong impact on the heating or cooling loads. In colder outdoor weather, the system needs to deliver higher heating loads. Maintenance is another key factor impacting the performance of the heating/cooling distribution system. Additionally, matching the capacity of pumps/fans with the desired flow rate at the operating point is significant to ensure the performance of the entire distribution system.

2.3. Stability/continuity

The stability of heating/cooling distribution system mainly depends on the stability of heat source. The heating/cooling distribution system consists of pumps, fans and/or valves that need to be regulated according to the required capacity.

2.4. Operation strategies

The control of the indoor air climate in the different zones of a building is typically performed by a climate controller. For simple systems, this can be only a thermostat, but for more complex buildings, a climate computer will be used. In addition to the heating or cooling systems (e.g., gas boiler or heat pump) and other active components in the building (e.g., automatic opening of windows), the climate computer will also control the heating and cooling distribution system.

The different operation strategies used by these controllers are typically confidential to the suppliers.

2.5. Practical lifetime

No information on the practical lifetime of heating and cooling distribution systems could be found.

3. Cost

3.1. Installation costs

The installation costs of heating and cooling distribution systems highly depends on the dimensions of the system and should be estimated for individual applications.

3.2. Operation and maintenance costs

Heat and cooling distribution systems do not incorporate the combustion of any fuel as this is consumed by the heat supply sources. The components such as valves, fans and pumps consume some electricity that leads to operation costs. The operation cost of valves is small, the cost for operating fans and pumps might be more significant. These can be calculated based on the pressure drop at given flow rates (see section 2.1).

As heating and cooling distribution systems require some maintenance, maintenance costs can contribute to the costs too.

3.3. Cost saving / ROI / Payback period

The calculation of ROI or payback period is also case dependent.

3.4. Funding schemes

No funding schemes for heating and cooling distribution systems could be found.

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3.5. List of brands/suppliers

In each country, many suppliers of heating and cooling distribution systems can be found. Therefore, a complete list is out of the scope of this report.

4. Applications

4.1. Existing applications

Many applications of heating/cooling distribution systems can be found in human occupied buildings and industrial buildings. In Denmark, applying local heating/cooling system via water circulation has been investigated in a few research projects, e.g., **GreenLive** project. In a hybrid ventilated (combination of natural ventilation and partial pit mechanical ventilation) pig building, a local cooling system was installed in part of the section, where pipes to circulate water was embedded in the solid floor where pigs rest on. The results showed that pigs intended to lie the cooled floor more and the respiration rate was likely lower than the zones where cooling was not provided.

4.2. Best practices/typical combinations with other technologies

Heating and cooling distribution systems are what connects the heat (or cold) source with the rooms of which the indoor climate is controlled. Therefore, they can be combined with each type of heat source (e.g., condensing gas boilers or heat pumps).

Furthermore, other energy efficiency technologies can be implemented in the heating and cooling distribution system. A smart ventilation system can be used to control fans and valves, or heat recovery can be performed on waste heat streams.

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Appendix 18: Heat recovery

1. General description

1.1. Working principle

With heat recovery, thermal energy in waste streams can be transferred to a different medium. This process will reduce the heating or cooling loads and consequently the operational costs of a farm. Furthermore, since the loads are reduced, also the investment costs of a heating or cooling system will be lower. Four heat sources for heat recovery are identified and will be discussed later in this report [275]. These are: ventilation air, air washers, manure, and milk cooling.

1.2. Selection

The selection for the type of heat recovery to be performed in industry or on a farm will always be dependent on the presence and energy potential of the waste heat streams at the considered farm. Although this is case specific, some general considerations apply. Heat recovery from ventilation air is only possible in mechanically ventilated stables and on the difference between the barn inside temperature and the outside temperature. Air washers can only be used for heat recovery when local regulations require the presence of air washers on the exhaust air. Whether manure cooling for heat recovery is possible will depend on the manure management system. Finally, milk cooling and heat recovery can only be combined on farms where dairy cows are kept.

1.3. Installation and maintenance

In the previous section, various possibilities for waste heat recovery were discussed. This waste heat can be upgraded to a higher temperature by a heat pump, or be used directly (e.g., for preheating the air). In any case, a heat exchanger is required to transfer the thermal energy from the heat source to the other fluid. In this section, a brief overview of heat exchanger technologies will be given.

Heat exchangers are devices used to transfer thermal energy from one fluid to another fluid at a lower temperature. Heat exchangers are used in a wide variety of applications, such as power production, process, chemical and food industries, electronics, environmental engineering, waste heat recovery, manufacturing industry, air-conditioning, refrigeration, space applications, etc. [276].

Two types of heat exchangers exist: recuperators and regenerators. Regenerators are a storage-type heat exchanger, where the same flow passage (or matrix) is alternately occupied by one of both fluids. The hot fluid stores the heat in the matrix, while the cold fluids is heated by this matrix is at a later time. More conventional are recuperators, where the heat transfer between both fluids occurs through a separating wall. Both concepts are shown in Fig.A18. 1.

Most heat exchangers for farming applications will be of the recuperators type. Again, multiple typologies of recuperators type heat exchangers exist. Most common in industry are the shell-and-tube heat exchanger, the gasketed plated heat exchanger, the plate-fin heat exchanger and the tube-fin heat exchanger [276]. Some illustrations of these types of heat exchangers can be found in Fig. A18. 1 to Fig. A18. 5.

When the fluid can be controlled adequately, heat exchangers are typically low in maintenance. Regular cleaning can be required to avoid a reduction in efficiency.

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Fig. A18. 1. Schematic representation of recuperators and regenerator type heat exchangers.

1.3.1. Shell-and-tube heat exchanger

Shell-and-tube heat exchangers are often used in process industry and power generation. They are able to transfer high thermal powers and the tubular shape allows it to withstand high pressures and temperatures. These devices are reliable and easy to maintain.

As can be seen in Fig. A18. 2 [276], a shell-and-tube heat exchanger consists of a bundle of tube mounted in a cylindrical shell. One fluid will flow inside the tubes, while the other fluid flows in the shell, over the tubes.

Fig. A18. 2. Schematic representation of a shell-and-tube heat exchanger.

1.3.2. Gasketed plate heat exchanger

Gasketed plate heat exchangers are often used in food industry because they can easily be opened for cleaning. Although they can withstand lower pressures than a shell-and-tube heat exchanger, they also can deliver a high thermal power and can achieve a very high effectiveness.

The main components of a gasketed plate heat exchanger are the corrugated plates over which the fluids will flow and the gaskets that determine the different flow paths. The plates are mounted together with the gaskets on a frame and the connection ports are connected to the rest of the installation. A schematic overview of a gasketed plate heat exchanger can be seen in Fig. A18. 3 [276].

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Fig. A18. 3. Schematic representation of a gasketed plate heat exchanger.

1.3.3. Plate fin heat exchangers

With this type of heat exchangers, channels are created by the stacking of parallel plates, shown in Fig. A18. 4 [276]. These channels are separated by fins (often corrugated plates) that are attached (brazed, soldered or welded) to the plates. These fins increase structural strength and improve heat transfer. Plate fin heat exchangers are typically used for gas-gas or gas-liquid applications.

Fig. A18. 4. Schematic representation of a plate-fine heat exchanger.

1.3.4. Tube fin heat exchangers

For gas-liquid applications, tube fin heat exchangers (see Fig. A18. 5) are often used, where the liquid is flowing inside the tubes and the gas on the outside. These tubes are finned on the outside to improve the heat transfer between the gas and the tubes. Although these heat exchangers can withstand higher pressures than plate fin heat exchangers, they are also less compact.

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Fig. A18. 5. Schematic representation of a tube-fin heat exchanger.

2. Performance

2.1. Environmental impact

With heat recovery, the energy demand for heating or cooling can greatly be reduced. This efficiency improvement reduces the amount of fuel that needs to be burned or electricity that needs to be taken from the grid. Both will decrease the emissions associated with the targeted process and will improve the local air quality around the farm.

Although some examples can be given, the exact environmental impact is case specific. As will be mentioned later, heat recovery from ventilation air has been shown to reduce the heating load with 55.5% [277].

2.2. Factors affecting performance

The extent to which heat recovery can be used will in some cases depend on environmental conditions. For manure heat recovery and milk cooling, no impact of the local climate could be identified. However, for heat recovery from the ventilation air or from the air washers, the potential for heat recovery will be depending on the temperature difference between the waste streams and the outside air.

3. Cost

3.1. Installation costs

No figures could be found on the installation costs of heat recovery systems in farming applications.

3.2. Operation and maintenance costs

Maintenance costs for heat recovery systems will typically be low, because maintenance is limited. Some cleaning of heat exchangers might be required to guarantee efficient operation.

In general, operation costs will also be low. Heat exchangers do however introduce an additional pressure drop in the system. This pressure drop has to be overcome by an electric fan or pump. The higher this pressure drop, the higher the operational costs will be. For a well-designed system, the costs for running the fan or pump will however be significantly smaller than the costs that can be saved.

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When recovered energy needs to be brought to a higher temperature, a heat pump will be installed. This heat pump will also use electricity, and thus present an operational cost.

3.3. Cost savings

Only limited information on the potential costs saving by heat recovery in farming applications could be found. Therefore, it is also difficult to estimate ROI or payback periods.

4. Applications

4.1. Existing non-farming applications

4.1.1. Heat recovery ventilation

Heat recovery ventilation (HRV) is a mechanical ventilation system for residential buildings. By recovering the residual heat in the exhaust gas, the fresh air is preconditioned. This effectively lower the heating or cooling demand of a building. A schematic representation of HRV is shown in Fig. A18.6 [278].

Fig. A18.6. Heat recovery ventilation in residential buildings.

4.1.2. Flue gas waste heat recovery

In many industrial processes, hot flue gasses are released into the atmosphere. When no heat recovery is performed, the thermal energy in this hot gas is expelled and wasted. By installing a heat recovery system (e.g. a heat exchanger), the efficiency of the plant can be increased. The recovered energy can either directly be used in the process of the plant again, or be employed e.g. to supply heat to the offices [279].

4.2. Existing farming applications

4.2.1. Ventilation air

In most livestock farms, a minimal ventilation rate is required to keep the air inside the stable healthy. This means that also during winter, this minimal ventilation is active while the barn is being heated.

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Consequently, some of this heat is lost to the environment. These losses can account for 65% of the yearly energy input for heating [280].

Some of this heat can be recuperated by installing a heat exchanger between the fresh air and the exhaust air. No direct contact between the incoming and outgoing air is allowed, as this would pollute the incoming air. An example of how a ventilation air heat recovery systems could work is shown in Fig. A18. 7 [281].

Fig. A18. 7. Example of a ventilation air heat recovery system.

Several successful implementations can be found in literature. Han et al. [277] were able to reduce the energy used for heating with 55.5% for one month, with the system shown in Fig. A18. 8 [277]. Another example is the case of Alberti et al. [282], where an air-to-air heat exchanger was used to increase the overall efficiency of a heat pump system. The recuperated heat accounted for 34% of the total delivered heat. Some other examples of implementation of such systems can be found in references [283,284].

Fig. A18. 8. Ventilation air heat recovery system.

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There are however also some difficulties or disadvantages. The main issues are the relatively small temperature differences, the corrosive environment and the accumulation of moisture and dust. Furthermore, since the convective heat transfer coefficients with air are typically low, a large heat exchanger will be required. Finally, it should also be mentioned that these heat exchangers introduce an additional pressure drop and consequently result in a higher operational cost.

4.2.2. Air washer

An air washer is a device used in livestock farms to treat the exhaust air before it is released to the environment. The goal of this treatment is e.g., to reduce the ammonia content of the exhaust air or to remove dust and unpleasant smells. A schematic representation of an air washer can be seen in Fig. A18. 9.

Fig. A18. 9. Schematic representation of an air washer.

The water used in an air washer is heated by this process. The heat in the waste flow can be recuperated as a source for a heat pump system [285]. The temperature of this water is rather constant throughout the year, which is beneficial for the COP of the heat pump. The amount of heat in the waste stream is however limited.

4.2.3. Manure

Although manure is typically associated with methane or nitrous oxide emissions, it also presents an opportunity as an energy source. There are two possibilities: anaerobic digestion and slurry heat recuperation.

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With anaerobic digestion of manure, biogas and digestate are produced. This biogas can be used as a fuel, while the digestate is a useful fertilizer. This anaerobic digestion is however outside the scope of this report.

The second option is slurry heat recovery. This manure slurry is a waste product with a liquid consistency, being a mixture of solid and liquid animal faeces with the addition of process water used for flushing [286]. This slurry is typically at a temperature higher than the ambient temperature, so heat can be extracted. As it remains at a rather constant temperature throughout the year, it is a suitable heat source for e.g., a heat pump. Furthermore, it slows down putrefaction, reducing the greenhouse gas emissions. One disadvantage of slurry heat recovery, is that there is only a limited amount of heat available [285].

One example of a manure heat recovery system can be found in the publication by [286]. In this system, the manure serves as a heat source for a heat pump that is used for providing domestic hot water for the breeder pigs. The authors claim that the system is technically possible, financially profitable and beneficial for the environment. A schematic representation of their installation can be seen in Fig. A18. 10 [286].

Fig. A18. 10. Installation diagram for preparing domestic hot water with a heat pump and manure heat exchanger.

4.2.4. Milk cooling

Bulk milk coolers are used to chill the milk from its harvest temperature of 35 °C to 4 °C to stop bacterial growth and maintain the quality of the harvested milk [287]. This is an energy-intensive process, so to reduce the costs, the heat that would be dissipated to the atmosphere can be recovered. This will contribute to increasing the energy efficiency of the plant.

This energy recovery is investigated by Sapali et al. [287]. In their case, the heat recovery system was used to heat the water for cleaning the milk processing equipment. A schematic representation of their system is shown in Fig. A18. 11 [287]. The COP of the heat pump used to cool the milk was increased from 3 to 4.8 by implementing the heat recovery. Other publications discussing milk cooling heat recovery can be found in references [288–290].

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Fig. A18. 11. Schematic diagram of the milk cooling heat recovery system investigated.

4.3. Status of implementation in Europe

No information on the status of the implementation of heat recovery systems in farms in Europe could be found.

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Appendix 19: Local heating and cooling

1. Technical description

1.1. Local cooling

To reduce the heat stress in livestock buildings, several adaption measures were proposed to modify the local environment of the individual animal by modifying the conductive, evaporative, radiative and convective heat release mechanism of the animals, in combination or alone.

1.1.1. Forced air velocity

By the use of additional fans, the air velocity close to the animal surface can be increased to raise the convective heat release. However, the fan-driven systems could not guarantee sufficient cooling benefit to animals. Mondaca and Choi [291] proposed a “polytube ventilation system” to distribute fresh air drawn from the outside through a series of perforations discharging aimed jets onto the cows, shown in Fig. A19. 1 [291]. With the consideration of increasing reclining time of cow, Wang et al [292] proposed “precision air supply system” which was based on the concept of providing precise amounts of fresh air to each cow in the stall, shown in Fig. A19. 2 [292].

Fig. A19. 1. Schematic of the polytube ventilation system.

Fig. A19. 2. Schematic of the precision air supply system to cool cows (a) in head-to-head stalls and (b) in both reclining and standing postures.

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1.1.2. Fogging and misting system

These cooling systems produce water droplets, which cool the air by evaporation as they disperse. In general, the evaporation process depends on the droplet diameter, sedimentation velocity and the relative humidity of the ambient air. The droplet diameter has a major impact on the velocity and duration of the evaporation. The fogging system employs high pressure to generate mean droplet diameters between 10 μm and 30 μm , shown in Fig. A19. 3 [293]. The misting system employs low-pressure to generate mean droplet diameters around 60 μm . Haeussermann et al [293] indicated that fogging system could reduce the energy consumption of the ventilation fans by 25% in a mechanically ventilated experimental pig building during a hot summer in southern Germany.

Fig. A19. 3. Schematic of the facility for fattening pigs with fogging system.

1.1.3. Floor cooling

Floor cooling may lead to improved comfort of animals during hot periods. The developing of a floor cooling system using underground water was used both in open-type and closed pig facilities, shown in Fig. A19. 4 [294]. The floor cooling system consists of five elements: underground or cold water, pump, external pipe, polyvinyl chloride (PVC) pipeline (loops of heat pipe), controllers including valves and thermostat. A PVC pipeline was placed under the sleeping area. Cold water could then flow from the pipeline inlet and be discharged to the drainage system. The inlet valve could be automatically controlled according to the temperature. A few extra external pipes are installed for circulating the water. The energy demand of the floor cooling system is limited to pumping the underground water.

Fig. A19. 4. Schematic of floor cooling systems with underground water in pig farm.

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1.2. Local heating

Localized supplemental heat can be categorized into two types: infrared heat (heat lamp), and conductive surface heating (heated floors and heated mats).

1.2.1. Infrared heating

Infrared heating allows creating a local heating zone for small animals e.g., piglets. Installing infrared heating makes it possible to maintain a higher temperature zone locally and therefore reduce the energy consumption if the entire building should be heated to the same level of temperature. Thermal energy released by infrared heaters is not absorbed by air but reaching biological objects via radiation with negligible heat loss. The use of infrared heating provides a 40% energy saving as reported in [296].

Li et al [297] developed an intelligent carbon fiber heater (ICFH) for piglet, shown in Fig. A19. 5 [296]. The intelligent control unit adjusts the heating level based on comparison of the ambient temperature around the piglets and the design temperature. They compared the performance and electricity usage of heating devices (ICFH, ICFHL, and IHL³²), shown in Fig. A19. 6 [297]. Results indicated that ICFH helped to reduce the piglet crushing rate and saved 40.6% of electricity usage compared to IHL, which is the current heating system for piglets in China.

Fig. A19. 5. Illustration of intelligent carbon fiber heater (ICFH): (a) exploded view of ICFH assembly, (b) photo of installed ICFH assembly, (c) photo of shell with temperature detection unit, and (d) location of temperature sensor on temperature detection unit.

Fig. A19. 6. Photos of (a) ICFH treatment, (b) ICFH+light treatment, and (c) Incandescent heat lamp (IHL) treatment.

³² ICFHL is short for ICFH+light. IHL is short for Incandescent heat lamp

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1.2.2. Floor heating

The floor heating could be achieved by using electricity and hot water. Electric-heated appeared to be better than the water-heated when considering installation costs and stability of systems [298]. While the advantage of water-heated is that it could be achieved by using renewable energy sources, geothermal heat pump [163,299], solar energy [300,301] or both [302].

Tikhomirov et al [303] developed an energy saving installation for local heating of piglets using Peltier thermoelectric elements, shown in Fig. A19. 7 [303]. The system consists of a thermoelectric assembly, which in turn included the estimated number of Peltier elements (3), the air cooler of cold circuit (1) with an exhaust fan (2) installed in the bypass of a pig house ventilation system, the water cooler of hot junction (4) connected by direct and return pipes (inlet/ outlet) (8) through a circulation pump (9) with a heated panel (6). Thermal power of the thermoelectric assembly is regulated by changing the current strength flowing through the thermocouples. Power, control, and management of the circuit is carried out by the block (5). The experimental results indicated that the thermoelectricity could reduce energy consumption up to 30% for heating young animals compared to the existing direct heating plant. The estimated payback period for local heaters of young animals (1.0 to 1.4 m²), based on Peltier thermoelectric elements, was about 3.5 years.

Fig. A19. 7. Functional-technological scheme of the installation of local floor-mounted heating of piglets using thermoelectricity. 1 is air cooler of cold circuit; 2 is fan; 3 are Peltier elements; 4 is water cooler of hot junction; 5 is power and control unit; 6 is heat panel; 7 are temperature sensors; 8 is pipe; 9 is pump.

Blázquez et al [304] have investigated the potential of recovering thermal energy from slurry for floor heating in pig farm, shown in Fig. A19. 8 [304]. The geothermal heat pump is the center of the entire slurry technology. As shown in Fig. A19. 8 (b), the slurry cooling circuit is the working fluid of the heat exchanger that is pumped around a closed-loop cooling circuit returning to the evaporator. The heat recovered from the thermal energy of the slurry is used to raise the temperature of the liquid refrigerant of the geothermal heat pump, the cooled working fluid is then circulated back to cool the slurry, shown in Fig. A19. 8 (a). The working fluid of the heat exchanger around the condenser of the

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geothermal heat pump is used to heat the ceramic heating plate where the piglets were resting. The advantages of the slurry technology are twofold, cooling the slurry to reduce ammonia emission and heating the floor with renewable energy.

Fig. A19. 8. Scheme of (a) working principle of the slurry technology and (b) heat pump operation to recover heat from slurry and generate hot water.

1.3. Installation and maintenance

Similar to heating and cooling distribution system, the key components for local cooling and heating are fan, tube, heat exchanger and pump. Tube, valves and heat exchangers need to be cleaned and checked and the quality of the working fluids need to be monitored regularly.

2. Performance

2.1. Environmental impact

The local heating system could be driven by heat recovery from waste heat (e.g., slurry) and thermal energy generated by renewable energy sources (e.g., geothermal energy). Meanwhile, the electricity consumption by pumps and fans could be compensated by other renewable energy. Hence, the local heating and cooling system could be carbon neutral if integrated design processes are followed comprehensively. Meanwhile, local heating and cooling strategies could improve energy efficiency and therefore reduce greenhouse gas emission indirectly.

2.2. Factors affecting performance

The maintenance of system and stability of power source, heat/cool source and insulation of the piping system could affect the performance.

2.3. Stability/continuity

Similar to heating and cooling distribution system, the stability relies on the stability of power source, heating/cooling source.

2.4. Operation strategies

The local heating and cooling system could be combined and driven by renewable energy.

2.5. Practical lifetime

No information on the practical lifetime of local heating and cooling systems could be found. It can be estimated based on the available information for lifetime of pipes, heat pump, etc.

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3. Cost

3.1. Example of investment cost and return on investment

The detailed cost and return on investment should be discussed with specific heating/cooling demand and system design. The budget of floor heating by recovering heat from slurry introduced in section 1.2.2 is listed below.

Currently, the slurry technology is being tested in a pig farm contains 1500 breeding pigs and 2500 transition pigs (from weaning to 23 kg). The pig farm locates in the region of Toledo (Spain). The total initial investment value and the price of each single component were summarized in Table A19. 2. It is estimated that the initial investment could be amortized in 4 years. Meanwhile, the slurry technology is expected to reduce CO₂ and CH₄ emission by 74% and 80% respectively.

Table A19. 2. Global initial investment of slurry technology in the investigated farm.

	Unitary price	Units	Total price (EUR)
Heat pump system	16,245.00 EUR/u	1 u	16,245.00
Geothermal heat exchangers	1 EUR/m	3830.52 m	3830.52
Reinforced concrete cover	16.26 EUR/m ²	1915.26	31,142.13
Recirculation pumps	911.00 EUR/u	6 u	5466.00
Working fluid	4.08 EUR/l	770.07 l	3141.89
Total initial investment			59,825.54

3.2. List of brands/suppliers

In each country, many suppliers of heating and cooling distribution systems can be found. Therefore, a complete list is out of the scope of this report.

4. Applications

4.1. Existing applications

Some of applications has been introduced in the above technical description. In Denmark and Holland, the local heating/cooling system has also been tested by using water flowing from the pipe installed in the pens with larger size of pigs to pens with smaller size of pigs. The application of combining local cooling system with heat pump has also been tested in a pig barn with hybrid ventilation system in **GreenLive** project, funded by GUDP in Denmark. The applications, which utilizes the waste heat from slurry via heat pump to supply warm water into the pipes installed in the solid floor to heat the resting area of pigs, can be found in a few Danish pig farms. The entire design concept of pig houses, ventilation system and inteli-controller as well as polluted air purifier are provided by AgriFarm A/S in Denmark.

4.2. Best practices/typical combinations with other technologies

The local heating and cooling could be designed and optimized with heating and cooling distribution systems. Meanwhile, the combination with renewable energy and energy recovery from waste heat could largely improve the energy efficiency and reduce the cost.

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Appendix 20: Energy efficient lighting

1. Technical description

1.1. Types of lamps

The basic components of light system are lamp, luminaire and control unit. The lamps available for agriculture lighting are:

Incandescent lamp generates light through filament heating. With low manufacturing costs and function equally well on both alternating current and direct current, incandescent lamp were used extensively before.

Halogen lamp is one type of incandescent lamp that consists of a tungsten filament sealed in a compact transparent envelope filled with halogen gas. The combination of the halogen gas and tungsten filament triggers a halogen-cycle chemical reaction, The filament in halogen lamp could be operated at a higher temperature therefore have higher luminous efficacy and colour temperature.

LED lamp: produces light by using light-emitting diodes (LEDs). LED lamps are significantly more energy-efficient than equivalent incandescent lamps. Commercial LED lamps have a lifespan many times longer than incandescent lamps.

Fluorescent lamp generates light via fluorescence. It is a low-pressure mercury-vapour gas-discharge lamp. When supplied with electric current, the gas excites mercury vapour to produce short-wave ultraviolet light that thereafter causes a phosphor coating on the inside of the lamp to glow

Compact fluorescent lamp is one type of fluorescent lamp designed to replace the incandescent lamp. This lamp uses a tube which is curved or folded to fit into the space of an incandescent bulb, and a compact electronic ballast in the base of the lamp.

Metal halide lamp produces light by an electric arc through a gaseous mixture of vaporized mercury and metal halides. This lamp is 3 to 5 times as efficient as incandescent lamp and have higher colour temperature which is suitable for high intensity applications outdoor.

High-pressure sodium: is a gas-discharge lamp that uses sodium in an excited state to produce light at a characteristic wavelength near 589 nm. High-pressure sodium lamps emit a broader spectrum of light, but they still have poorer colour rendering than other types of lamps.

1.1.2. LED lighting

LED generally has higher efficacy and lifespan than the other types of lamp as indicated in Table A20. 1 [305]. LED also tend to require less amount of energy during the total lifecycle (Fig. A20. 1 [306]). Therefore, LED is considered as the energy efficient lighting option. Nowadays, the costs of LED packages have decreased to the point where LED lighting products can be competitive with conventional lighting products on a first cost basis, while offering significantly lower initial cost and electricity cost during its lifecycle. Besides, LED lighting has key features as spectral control, intensity control and optical distribution control [307].

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Table A20. 1. General characteristics of light source.

Lamp Type	Lamp Power (W)	CRI ³³	Efficacy (lm/W) ³⁴	Typical Lamp life (hrs)
Incandescent	34-200	100	11-20	750-2,000
Halogen	50-150	100	18-25	2,000-3,000
White LED	1-200	70-90	50-100	25,000-100,000
Fluorescent	32-100	70-95	75-98	15,000-20,000
Compact Fluorescent	5-50	80-90	50-80	10,000
Metal halide	70-1,000	60-80	60-94	7,500-20,000
High-pressure sodium	35-1,000	20-80	63-125	15,000-24,000

Fig. A20. 1. Comparison of total lifecycle energy consumption of Incandescent, CFL and LED bulbs.

1.1.3. Solar light pipe

Compared to artificial lights, solar light pipe has the advantage of providing natural light and therefore saving energy. Light pipe can capture natural daylight into deep indoor space without inducing excessive heat gains and glare patches. The light pipe consists of three components: a collector, a reflective pipe and a diffuser, as shown in Fig. A20. 2 [308]. The collector is a transparent element, which is installed at the external aperture of the pipe. Its main functions are to collect daylight and protect the light pipe from the impact of weather and soiling. It is usually made flat or dome-shaped from a highly transmitting material. The reflective pipe is a passive component consisting of either a simple reflective interior coating or a light conducting fiber optic bundle. The diffuser is installed in the

³³ CRI: Color Rendering Index

³⁴ Lumen (lm) is the unit of the time rate of flow of light (luminous energy) equal to the energy emitted through a unit solid angle (one steradian) from a uniform point source of one candela.

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ceiling of the room, admits the daylight into interior spaces and distributes the available light energy evenly.

Fig. A20. 2. Layout of the light pipe with (a) flat collector and (b) dome collector.

1.2. Selection

1.2.1. Quantity of illumination

Lighting has significant impacts on the animal behaviour and production. Therefore, lighting system should fulfil the requirement of each livestock type. The detailed recommended illuminance levels for dairy, swine, poultry and equine could be found in ASABE standard EP344.4 [305]. Table A20. 2 presents the range of recommended luminance most appropriate for carrying out agricultural tasks [309].

Table A20. 2. Range of recommended luminance for agricultural tasks.

Task by level of visual challenge (with examples)	Range of luminance
Simple: Cleaning barn, feeding animals, loading/unloading material, refueling, hay mows, storage areas	30-100 lumens (2.8-9.3 foot-candles)
Moderate: 'Rough' shop work, farm office work, cleaning	300-1,000 lumens (28-93 foot-candles)
Demanding: 'Detailed' shop work, machinery repair/maintenance, operating power tools, sorting, inspecting, milking, care of animals	3,000-10,000 lumen (279-929 foot-candles)

1.2.2. Quality of illumination

Uniformity: Lighting system should provide uniform illumination to guarantee that each object can receive illumination from more than one direction to minimize the denseness of shadows. For difficult seeing task in poultry house and dairy house, the satisfactory uniformity ratio should be in the range of 1.5 to 2 [310] and 1.5 to 1 [311] respectively. In general, better uniformity of illumination could be achieved with greater mounting heights and closer spacing of luminaires.

Glare: For certain lighting system, glare should be minimized to objectionable level by covering the luminaires with sufficient shielding. It is suggested to mounted luminaires as far above normal line of

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sight as possible and limit both the luminance and quantity of light emitted within the 45° to 85° zone [310].

Colour: The psychological effects induced by lighting colour should be considered when selecting light sources to obtain quality lighting.

Environment: The quality of illumination also affected by the indoor environment. The ceilings, walls and floors can reflect light and therefore increase the utilization of the light within the room. Excessive brightness ratios should be prevented by room surface which have matte finishes of high reflectance. Using luminaires to direct light upward toward ceiling with relatively high reflectance could generate a more comfortable visual environment [310].

1.3. Installation and maintenance

The wiring and power distribution for lighting system should be designed and installed by licensed professional engineers. As suggested in EP344.4, the maintenance of lighting system should be performed once every three months. Regularly observe the condition of automatic control equipment and electrical cords to ensure it is functioning properly. It is not suggested to keep the lights on during daylight periods. Faulty lamps should be replaced, and dirty lamps should be cleaned.

2. Performance

2.1. Environmental impact

Fig. A20. 1 shows that LED lighting have lowest total life-cycle energy consumption, which also means lower carbon footprint. Base on the 2012 technical data, LED lamps offered a 76% reduction of CO₂ emission compared with incandescent lamp [312]. The detailed life-cycle environmental impact of LED lighting could be found in reference [312], which was estimated based on the 2012 technical data. The energy efficiency of LED lighting is deemed increased greatly and significantly reduce its negative impacts on environment. Meanwhile, the life-cycle of LED is free of mercury.

2.2. Factors affecting performance

LED lighting is mostly used indoor, the factors (e.g., geographical location, climatic conditions, orientation, inclination, latitude and etc.) would not affect its performance. The indoor temperature could affect the LED's light output, as energy conversion efficiency drops with increasing temperature.

2.3. Stability/continuity

The stability of LED lighting is primary depend on the input power (current and voltage).

2.4. Operation strategies

The operation of LED lighting is the same as traditional lighting. Light on/off bases on the current luminance and recommended luminance.

2.5. Practical lifetime

LEDs have general lifetime of 25,000-50,000 hours. Top-quality LEDs have lifetimes up to 100,000 hours. The heat generated by LED chip and its own quality are the main factors affecting their lifetime and performance.

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3. Cost

The cost and saving vary from country to country. Hence, this section is discussed based on the several existing farm applications. Please note that the calculation of projected cost and saving should be consulted with local electrical companies.

3.1. Installation costs

Clarke and Ward [313] have projected the cost and saving of retrofitting a barn with 60 W incandescent bulbs with 10W LED lamps or 18 W LEDs tube. Table A20. 3 [313] shows that the initial investment of installing LED lighting is still very high, especially the LED tube.

Table A20. 3. Comparison of the cost to retrofit incandescent bulks with LED bulbs or LED tube.

	Incandescent 60 W (Dimmed to 30 W)	LED lamp 10 W (Dimmed to 5 W)	LED tube 17 W (Dimmed to 9 W)
Average rated life (hr)	1000	30000	36000
Number of lamps	54	54	54
Typical cost per lamp	\$1	\$18	\$200
Total cost of lamps	\$54	\$970	\$5400
Annual cost of electricity	\$1600	\$260	\$500
Electricity for 2 years	\$3200	\$520	\$1000
Total cost over 2 years	\$3700	\$1500	\$6400
Savings over 2 years	N/A	\$2200	-\$2700
Total cost by year 7	\$13000	\$3800	\$8600
Savings by year 7	N/A	\$9200	\$4400

(\$:Canada dollar)

3.2. Operation and maintenance costs

The main cost for operation and maintenance of LEDs lighting come from the electricity consumption, which is based on the amount of lamps and local electricity price.

3.3. Cost savings

The costing saving of LED lighting comes from reduction in electricity consumption. Table A20. 3 shows that LED lighting could reduce electricity consumption significantly and compensate its drawback of higher initial investment.

3.4. ROI/IRR/NPV/Payback Period

The Farm Energy and Agri-Processing (FEAP) grant program in Canada has retrofitted a pig barn with LED lighting [314]. The annual energy consumption of pig barn was reduced from 136.4 MWh to 58.5 MWh when replaced fluorescent with LED. With the granted funding (35% of the cost), the payback period was estimated as 0.71 year.

3.5. Funding schemes

No EU funding was found yet to support the application of LED lighting in livestock buildings.

3.6. List of brands/suppliers

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Table A20. 4. List of LED lighting suppliers and solar light.

Manufacturer	Country	Products
Helio LED Lighting	Canada	Channel light, Flood Light, Round Light Fixture
OSRAM	Germany	LED bulk, control system, solution and etc.
Norka	Germany	LED tube, LED bulb, Flood Light, solution and etc.
Philips Lighting	Netherlands	LED tube, LED bulb, Ledinaire and etc.
Aruna Lighting	Netherlands	Poultry LED system
HATO Lighting	Netherlands	Lighting solutions
LED Livestock ApS	Denmark	Lighting solutions
Velux	America	Solar light system
Solatube	America	Solar light system

4. Application

4.1. Existing farming applications

Nowadays, farms have retrofitted exiting incandescent/CFL lighting with LED lighting throughout the barns, mechanics shop, outdoor yard and etc. [313,314].

Wachenfelt et al [308] installed and measured the performances of solar light pipe in the pig house locates in Odarslöv Sweden. Flat collector and dome collector were reported achieving 48% and 55% of daylight autonomy respectively based on the annual climate data in Sweden.

Besides using more efficiency LED lighting, another possibility of sustainable lighting system is to make best of natural light. In the introduction of Smart Ventilation (Appendix 16), combining natural and pit mechanical ventilation system, the integrated design process has been implemented by modifying the geometrical configuration, utilizing daylighting as much as possible to save the electrical energy consumption and ventilate the building by natural driving force. This is a good example for integrated design for livestock production buildings.

4.2. Existing non-farming applications

In 2021, LEDs took up approximate 50% of lighting markets in buildings sector worldwide. Meanwhile, numerous countries worked on phasing out incandescent lamps more than ten years ago, many are now beginning to replace fluorescent lighting with LEDs lighting. It is estimated that LED would be the only option in all countries by 2025 and fulfil the Net Zero Emissions by 2050 Scenario [315].

4.3. Potential farming applications

LED lighting could be installed in both indoor and outdoor of the livestock buildings.

4.4. Status implementation in Europe

EU decided to phase out inefficient lamps on 17 April 2015. With lower prices and better performance, the market share of LED lighting keeps increasing.

4.5. Best practices/typical combinations with other technologies

LED lighting could be combined with solar light to guarantee the requirement of daylight. LED lighting is driven by electricity, therefore renewable energy e.g., wind turbine, biogas etc. could be selected as the power source.

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Appendix 21: Building envelope

1. Technical description

1.1. Working principle

Thermal insulation of the building envelope is fundamental for an effective control of the indoor microclimate in livestock farm buildings. This technology is therefore necessary to assure general animal health, more comfortable working condition, with direct consequences on the farm productivity. The high fuel costs has promoted to improve the energy use efficiency of livestock housing and to minimize energy consumption. A livestock house (Fig. A21. 1) is an open system that exchanges energy and mass between the indoor and outdoor environments and the animals that occupy the internal volume.

Fig. A21. 1. Envelope in livestock buildings.

The building walls, floor, and roof represent the control surfaces and enclose the control volume of the thermodynamic system, represented by the livestock house, and its internal surfaces, such as animals, interior walls, and equipment. With the aim to analysis of the thermal behaviour of a livestock house, is needed to obtain the energy balance of a livestock as follows [316]:

$$\Phi_a + \Phi_{tr} + \Phi_H + \Phi_{sol} + \Phi_V = 0 \quad (1)$$

where Φ_a = heat flow from the animals inside the enclosure (W)

Φ_{tr} = heat flow due to transmission through the control surfaces (W)

Φ_H = heat flow due to supplemental heating system (W)

Φ_{sol} = heat flow due to solar radiation (W)

Φ_V = heat flow due to ventilation (W)

Further, the Fig. A21. 2 [317] represents the location of the variables involved in the energy balance of a typically livestock building in cold condition requiring supplemental heating Φ_H .

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Fig. A21. 2. Heat balance of a generic livestock house.

Another way to increase the energy efficiency, is through the use of constructive technologies of wall and roof insulation, ventilated roof, shading curtains, and others. The scientific community of this sector has worked on the development of technologies available for harnessing renewable energy source in the normal operation of livestock buildings.

1.2. Selection

1.2.1. Wall and roof insulation

Thermal energy storage in walls, ceilings and floors of buildings may be enhanced by embedding PCM within these construction elements. Increasing the thermal storage capacity of a building can decrease the internal temperature oscillations. Significant representative technological solutions for wall and roof insulation are reported as follows.

Thermal insulating panel in expanded granular glass contains more than 66% of glass deriving from the recycling of car windshields, neon tubes, window glass and quartz sand. The product is completely free of harmful agents, so it is particularly ecological, and its inorganic origin makes it totally incombustible. The material also has a constant thermal conductivity value. The structure of the material is made up of millions of closed and hermetic glass cells that ensure an efficient vapor barrier. This insulation is impermeable to water and vapor-tight, does not absorb moisture, and has good resistance to compression. The product is manufactured in the form of slabs that are used in floors or roofs, and in the form of panels for dry walls and floors. Both the sheets and the panels are particularly easy to install.

Mineral wool or rock wool is obtained from the fusion and spinning of natural rocks. The raw material is dosed in the oven and melted at a temperature of about 1600 °C. The thermo-chemical characteristics of natural rocks are essential to obtain a fiber that is unassailable by acids, rot-proof and with a high resistance to temperature, which are used as raw material to produce bio-soluble rock wool. Bio-soluble rock wool, which is also known as mineral wool or feldspar wool, is chemically neutral, does not contain dangerous components and does not contain asbestos.

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Polyethylene-based foam obtained by extrusion of a mixture of polymeric components and agents is characterized by high practicality and ease of use, as well as by dynamic stiffness, compressive strength, and high resistance to humidity. The material lasts a long time and keeps its performance constant. Excellent water resistance, fire resistance and low thermal conductivity. Specific application for cavity walls.

Polyester fiber is a latest generation insulating panel, for use in construction, it is used both in the cavity of walls and above false ceilings. It is particularly appreciated for its lightness, self-supporting capacity, and deformability. The product has excellent thermal and acoustic performance, it also has an excellent reaction to fire and, more importantly, it does not emit opaque or toxic fumes.

Insulating panel in sintered expanded polystyrene (EPS) is obtained from a closed cell, flame retardant block (Euroclass E). The panels are decidedly versatile and easy to handle, they combine the advantages of perfect sintering with those characteristics of the product: high insulating power, unchanged over time. The product has excellent performance permeable to water vapor, but impermeable to water (no water absorption by capillarity); unassailable by molds and bacteria; it is light and cheap and has a high density. The sintered expanded polystyrene is devoid of nutritional values capable of supporting the growth of fungi, bacteria, or other microorganisms, so it does not rot or mold. Due to its chemical and biological stability, EPS does not pose a danger to environmental hygiene and groundwater. The EPS installed in building insulation does not present any health hazard factors, as it does not release toxic gases. Handling and any mechanical processing are also absolutely harmless and there is no danger of inhaling particles or allergic manifestations. It combines high performance with minimal environmental impact; the PSE has an extraordinary cost / benefit ratio: every kg of oil used for its production saves 150 kg of heating fuel in 50 years of the minimum useful life of a building. Using objective calculation methodologies, such as the LCA method, which analyzes the entire life cycle of a material (energy and water consumption during production and transport, energy savings during its useful life, energy recovery in case of recycling or energy consumption in case of disposal) it shows how sintered expanded polystyrene satisfies the strictest ecological standards.

Phase change capsules (Phase Change Material – PCM) have the characteristic of being “latent heat accumulators”. By inserting wax capsules, for example, in the plaster, a stabilizing effect on the temperature of the environment is obtained, which remains cool in summer and warm in winter. The temperature is, in fact, regulated by the melting and solidification of the wax. Inside the capsules is stored wax whose melting point is between 22 and 26 ° C. When the wax melts, energy is consumed and ensures that the temperature in the room does not increase. During this “phase change” cycle, the temperature of the wax remains unchanged. In cold conditions, the wax capsules contained in the plaster keep the internal temperature constant: as the temperature decreases, the wax solidifies and releases heat. During the melting of the wax, the heat is absorbed to be released again when the wax solidifies. In order to actually mix the latent heat accumulators in the plaster, they must be protected. The liquid wax is inserted in capsules with a plastic casing, the so-called microcapsules. The capsules are produced in the form of an aqueous dispersion or powder. Thanks to this process, PCM microcapsules can be introduced into building materials.

1.2.2. Ventilated roof

The roofs protect buildings from external actions, ensuring high performance of water impermeability, wind resistance and thermal insulation to reduce the energy dispersion.

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In order to have adequate thermal comfort and energy saving, it is necessary to provide insulation but also to create a time shift of the thermal wave peak in the transition, from the external to the internal layers of the roof by acting on the mass and properties of the materials.

Each roof has a certain number of elements according to the different type of operation of the roof. Such functional layers can generally lead to four types of roofing:

Non-insulated non-ventilated roof is a type of roof where neither thermal insulation elements nor ventilation layers are provided. Given the lack of insulation that this coverage ensures, it is used in limited cases where thermal insulation of the system is not required (such as the roofs of agricultural buildings).

Non-insulated ventilated roof is the same as the previous one but with an additional layer of ventilation under the sealing element, with the aim of improving the behavior of the roof in summer as the ventilation reduces the effects of heating due to radiation. solar. This solution is also generally adopted in agricultural construction.

Insulated non-ventilated roof (warm roof) is provided with a thermal insulation layer but does not have a ventilation layer. A roof of this kind therefore consists of the following layers: load-bearing element or roofing support (cast-in-situ concrete or mixed masonry, prefabricated concrete panels, wood panels, metal sheets, etc.); vapor barrier; thermal insulation; waterproof mantle; ancillary works.

Insulated ventilated roof (cold roof) has a composition similar to that of the warm roof but a ventilation space is inserted in the stratigraphy, which separates the layers, interposed between the insulation and the over-roof.

In the warm roof, the waterproof covering is almost always applied directly to the thermal insulation, which constitutes its support, while in the cold roof the waterproof covering is laid on the over-roof which is almost always made of wood. Generally, the type of warm roof is more widespread, especially in industrial buildings, while the cold roof, or ventilated roof, is made above all in the case of wooden roofs, pitched roofs and for residential buildings.

1.2.3. Doors and windows

Building envelopes play a crucial role in the energy balance of buildings and on this matter windows and doors have a significant importance.

Doors

Entrance and exit, or internal doors generally serve as building entrances for building operations personnel and animals. They typically serve double duty as emergency egress. Industrial doors typically used in barn and stables also provide access for material handling in buildings. Doors are typically rolling or coiled gates, or sliding security grilles, that can open large apertures in a building wall to allow unloading and loading trucks that back up to an elevated dock, or to allow building access for vehicles and tractors. Common door types include:

- Swing doors, generally serving Entrance/Exit functions.
- Revolving doors, generally serving Entrance/Exit functions.
- Industrial (e.g., overhead) doors, serving material handling and security functions.

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Commonly used door materials include aluminum, steel, wood and glass. Doors that are integrated with commercial storefronts are typically aluminum frames with glass in-fills, or all glass. Steel-clad doors are generally utilized for service entrance/exit functions. Wood doors are most commonly employed in low density residential construction; therefore, they are beyond the scope of this chapter. Industrial doors are used for material handling, not for pedestrian access. Their main function is to provide security. They are, therefore, frequently not designed for building envelope performance. Security grates or doors are typically installed over more conventional storefront systems. Typical materials for exterior applications are steel, aluminum, and stainless steel. The doors also frequently incorporate glass in-fill panels. There are different type of doors depending on the application context, such as:

Framed doors include a frame around the outer edge of the door held together at the corners with mortise and tendon joints. The framed door can be further improved by rabbeting the edge of the frame rails and setting the panels into the grooves 10 mm to 20 mm. The door can be hung on strap or tee hinges, but since there is an outer frame, the door can also be hung on butt hinges with hidden screws. If the inner panel is made up of several boards' braces are needed, but if the one or two panels are made of plywood, no braces will be required. Large barn or garage doors will need the bracing regardless of the construction of the center panels.

Flush Doors consist of a skeleton frame clad with a sheet facing such as plywood. No bracing is necessary, and the plain surface is easy to finish and keep clean. Flush panel doors are easily insulated during construction if that is necessary.

Double Doors can better serve the large door openings. If hinged doors are used, the smaller double doors are not as likely to sag and bend and they are much less likely to be affected by wind. Usually opening one of the double doors will allow a person to pass through.

Rolling Doors typically consist of a steel frame that is anchored to the perimeter construction to resist wind and operating loads, structural guides for the door edges, and a hood that contains the rolled up "curtain" when the door is in the open position. Larger industrial doors are motorized; smaller units can be operated by manual push-up, chain hoists, or cranks. Motorized doors are often opened and closed with automatic gate operators.

Windows

The windows are one of the most important parts of the barn building envelope. The windows will protect animals from unsuitable air velocity and water leaks and help keep them at a comfortable temperature and humidity values, still guaranteeing suitable air exchange ratios. Windows have long been used in buildings for daylighting and ventilation. Many studies have even shown that health, comfort, and productivity in barns and facilities are improved due to well-ventilated indoor environments and access to natural light. However, windows also represent a major source of unwanted heat loss, discomfort, and condensation problems. Modern windows and vents can be made from a variety of materials, including wood, PVC, composite, aluminum, and fiberglass. For example, in cold regions buildings for livestock can be equipped with aluminum windows in order to prevent frost. Vinyl windows are not a good choice for barn because they are too flexible. Aluminum windows are sturdier and more and more secure. Aluminum windows are also frequently chosen for barns because of the window joints, or joinery. The two joints on the frame are screwed together, and foam gaskets are used to prevent air from leaking in through the windows. The thermal break is an important

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part of aluminum windows. It separates the interior and exterior aluminum to prevent the transfer of cold air through the window. This can help prevent frost. Polyurethane is used for a thermal break in aluminum windows.

1.2.4. Shading curtains

The curtains in barns (Fig. A21. 3) are a cost-effective solution for easy access and temperature control to hog, dairy, or livestock operations. In fact, these devices not only are a way to control the incident radiation, affecting the indoor environment (mainly the temperature level), but also they allow to mitigate strong wind, rain, incoming dust and, if necessary, snow. The temperature, the humidity and the air velocity inside a barn play a key role in the animal comfort and consequently in the production. The curtains allow on one hand to mitigate strong wind and then, to protect animals from cold during the rigid seasons or climate; on the other hand, allow to limit the effect of solar radiation, which has a strong contribution in rising indoor temperature and, then to the heat stress of animals.

Another important aspect is their positive effect in the prevention of diseases and bacterial infection to farm animals. For example, they allow to contrast the harmful presence of insects, such as house flies, *Musca domestica L.*, becoming a physical barrier to their passage.

However, an easy management and control of these devices is important for the farmer and for the everyday running life of the farm. In fact, these devices should work interdependently with barn environmental conditions, which may change throughout the day or during a specific period. They could be activated and then taken place after reaching the threshold value of some parameters, such as temperature or external wind speed. In fact, the choice of this technology depends on the main parameters, which have to be controlled, and on the environmental condition of the barn location.

1.3. Installation and maintenance

In the design installation processes, it is necessary to comply with the national and local standards and building codes. Maintenance requirements are provided by manufacturers, in order to assure safety and performance standards over time.

As *shading curtains* represent a typology of building envelope with several mechanical moving components, a focus on its maintenance requirements is provided.

Fig. A21. 3. Mechanical shading curtains.

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With the aim to maximize livestock productivity, it is important take into account the importance of light, ventilation, and overall climate control. Suitable environmental conditions can lead to better yield which means increased profits. An automatic Barn Curtains work in roll-up and drop-down systems powered by motors, that typically receives the command of sensors that measure the main environmental parameters that govern the comfort of livestock buildings. With the aim of integrating the creation of automated systems with the existing sustainable development policies, it is possible to use the development of existing technological advances in the area of Information and Communication Technologies, as well as the Embedded Circuits free and open-source such as Arduino, NodeMCU, Teensy, Launchpad and PocketBeagle. These devices have an intuitive programming interface that enable the implementation of repetitive tasks. For the specific case of motor control, it is possible to install communication interfaces that guarantee the safe operation of external devices.

The system (Fig. A21. 4) consists of a powerful 380-volt electric drive turns the top bar which winds a wire roller attached to a tube at the top of the curtain, moving it up or down.

Fig. A21. 4. Architecture of automatic shading curtains.

2. Performance

2.1. Environmental impact

Following the traditional roles of insulation and shading systems, they are used to increase thermal and visual comfort and provide privacy by reducing overheating and glare. In the last decades the European Community has developed an energetic strategy that more and more takes into account the indissoluble link between energetic politics, environmental changes and environment's protection. In this context should be considered the potentiality of livestock buildings for the implementation of eco-fiend's technologies. The scientific community has proven it is possible to reduce the energy consumption of the heat gain or cooling systems by 55%.

Life Cycle Assessment is needed to quantify the environmental footprint of the various technological solutions available. Materials with different level of embodied emissions and sustainability are available on the market.

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2.2. Factors affecting performance

The building envelope mainly performs in static conditions and the main requirement to assure the performances defined is the integrity of the building structure and the envelope itself. Then, the thermal performances are obviously affected by environmental and weather conditions, which have to be accounted for in the design phase.

2.3. Stability / continuity

There are many benefits associated with use of barn curtains in agricultural buildings. Shading curtains provide a high degree of ventilation, insulation, and lighting materials like wood or metal. They are excellent tools for managing dust, methane and ammonia, moisture and mould, and airborne diseases, all of which can represent respiratory health risks to the livestock.

2.4. Operation strategies

Indoor lighting, temperature and air flow for farm facilities is critical to safe and efficient production. Those of systems should be designed to meet the most energy efficient and economical manner. In this sense there are some items that is needed taking into account for guarantee adequate environmental parameters.

Comfort

Light and fresh air is needed to make the dairy farm design layout in such a way that every morning the cows in the barn get the sunrise and the fresh air. Which is really healthy and people can work comfortably in the morning.

Temperature

One criterion for preventing stress in animals is to maintain their thermoneutral zone over which the total heat production is approximately constant for a given energy intake. The zone of acceptable temperature is usually characterized by air temperature between the lower and upper critical temperatures. However, the thermoneutral zone is very dependent on many factors, e.g. feeding level, floor type, air speed and numbers of animals in the group.

Humidity

Humidity is a critical factor in the ability of animals to lose heat. As humidity increases the effectiveness of evaporative cooling decreases. As the ambient temperature approaches body temperature, sensible cooling becomes less effective, and the animal relies increasingly on evaporative cooling. Thus, the worst conditions for heat loss occur at high temperatures and high humidities.

Ventilation

A proper dairy housing climate is one of the pre-conditions for maintaining an excellent environment within the various housing systems. Then, it has a great effect on the well-being and health status of animals, and overall performance. Conditions must be created to enhance the animal's inherent ability to control its temperature. So, ventilation is essential for the supply of fresh air, with the emphasis on maintaining a suitable air quality under any weather condition over a long period. Also, adequate ventilation is required for the removal of harmful gases, avoidance of moisture accumulation, and the removal of heat produced by dairy animals.

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2.5. Practical lifetime

Solutions for wall and roof insulation, including ventilated ones have lifetime corresponding to buildings ones, which is generally set at 50 years for residential and production buildings, but can vary depending on the expected duration of the economic activities to be carried out in the buildings.

Shadings curtains systems deserve specific considerations, as they need to be monitored on regular basis for better management of the farm. It should be kept safe in order to assure a proper operation of the system. Any damage to the shadings curtains systems must be repaired as soon as possible with the aim to prevent safety for all the cows and the people who are working in the farm. The steel and the members like the cubicle partition posts and the structure needs to be protected from lengthy exposure to water, cow urine and all other possible threats.

3. Cost

3.1. Installation cost

Item		Unitary cost
Wall and roof insulation	Thermal acoustic insulation of terraces and roofs, consisting of rigid panels in glass fibers treated with special thermosetting resins, 1,20x1,00 m with the following characteristics: density 110 kg / m, thickness 30 mm, coating on one band with a bituminous glass veil and bituminous Kraft paper, reborded on two parallel sides. Installed with a layer of oxidized bitumen 85/40 given at the rate of 1,200 kg / m ²	€ 20.42 / m ²
	Thermal insulation on the extrados under ballast in roofs defined as cold or inverted roofs, made with panels in extruded polystyrene foam with a density of 33-35 kg / m ³ ; compressive strength up to 300 kPa laid dry, 10 cm thick	€ 16.69 / m ²
	"Coating" thermal insulation achieved through the use of panels anchored to the facade surfaces by applying glue paste and mechanical fixing with special plastic nail plugs. The insulating panels will be coated on site with a layer of reinforced plaster consisting of suitable smoothing mortar, in which a treated glass wire mesh will be embedded. After the laying of the net, a further leveling of sufficient thickness to cover the net itself must be carried out. The finish will consist of a continuous layer of wall covering based on continuous plastic plaster of the spatulated type, finished thickness approx. 2 mm applied with a spatula; in polyurethane / polystyrene panels, 10 + 1 cm thick	€ 55.20 / m ²
Ventilated roof		€20 to 70 / m ²
Doors and windows ³⁵		€80 to 200 / m ²
Shading curtains	Only curtains settles	€2.8 to 4 / m ²
	Entire system	€ 100 / m ²

³⁵ https://territorio.regione.emilia-romagna.it/osservatorio/Elenco-regionale-prezzi/prezzario-er-2019_completo.xls/view

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3.2. List of brands and suppliers

Item	Supplier	Website
Wall and roof insulation	PITTSBURGH CORNING ITALY	www.foamglas.it
	TERVOL	www.tervol.it
	BASF	www.basf-italia.it
	FORTLAN S.p.A.	www.fortlan.it
	DI-BI	www.di-bi.it
Ventilated roof	CELENIT	https://www.celenit.com
	mazonetto	https://www.mazonettometalli.it
	AERcoppo	https://www.aertetto.it/#gref
Doors and window	Primoss	https://www.primoss.it/
	Hörmann	https://www.hormann.it
	Campisa	https://campisa.co.uk/
Shading curtains	Agrisystemsrl	https://agrisystemsrl.com/
	Carretta Tessitura	https://www.carrettatessitura.com/zootecnia/
	Erilon	http://erilon.it/en/shading-curtains/

4. Application

4.1. Existing farming applications

4.1.1. Ventilated roofs

As above mentioned, the ventilated roof is a common solution in farm buildings overall in the Mediterranean area, where the summer often brings severe thermal conditions. For its nature, the application of this technology in livestock buildings must be carefully evaluated. In closed structures, such as pig sheds or old cow barns, the ventilation can provide an important contribution to reduce the overheating due to the direct solar gain in summer. On the contrary, in open structures, such as cow barns (that are often built without external walls and the roof has a limited slope), the ventilated roof may show a very low efficiency.

4.1.2. Doors and windows

Doors are frequently problematic components of a building's thermal envelope. Typical issues include heat loss from air movement during operation, heat loss from air movement through the perimeter detail, and radiant heat loss through the door materials themselves. Door frames that do not

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incorporate adequate thermal insulation create thermal bridges that tend to lead to wintertime condensation. Overall door thermal performance is a function of the type of operation (e.g. swing, sliding, revolving), the glazing (if applicable), the frame and perimeter details, the sash and sash weather-stripping, and the door materials. Aluminum-framed doors that are part of curtain wall or storefront assemblies sometimes have thermally broken frames and insulating glass units, which provide improved thermal performance. Opaque entrance doors or loading dock doors often have foamed-in-place insulation between their exterior and interior metal skins, which typically provides better thermal performance than insulating glass. These insulated doors must have internal stiffeners to stiffen the face skins and provide adequate structural performance. Heat loss from air leakage is the most significant challenge to thermal performance for heavily used entrance and exit doors. In colder climates, air curtains provide a barrier of fast-moving warm air that limits penetration of cold exterior air while the door is open. The warm air may also be used to raise the surface temperature of the doors, which limits condensation. Entrance vestibules, with separate inner and outer doors, provide improved energy performance over a single entrance door, mainly by limiting loss of conditioned air during door operation.

As for window performances, in recent years, windows have undergone a technological revolution. High-performance, energy-efficient window and glazing systems are now available that can dramatically cut energy consumption and pollution sources: they have lower heat loss, less air leakage, and warmer window surfaces that improve comfort and minimize condensation. These high-performance windows feature double or triple glazing, specialized transparent coatings, insulating gas sandwiched between panes, and improved frames. All of these features reduce heat transfer, thereby cutting the energy lost through windows. In several cases grids are adopted instead of the glass for windows guesting animals. Orientable grids and vents can be open or close as a function of the internal micro-climate conditions. Moreover, grids closures are simpler to clean than glass panels and tend to have a longer life than glass panels. Window and glazing choices should be considered holistically. Window glazing refers to the glass panels in the windows. It is advisable to always choose sealed, double-paned insulating glass. The windows should be sealed with an approved cellular foam tape that has a silicone cap-bead to seal the glass onto the frame. Ultimately, the optimum choice of window and glazing systems will depend on many factors including the building use type, the local climate, utility rates, and building orientation. Once the design team and owner agree on the design problem, window and glazing options can be evaluated. Issues to consider include: heat gains and losses, visual requirements, shading and sun control, thermal comfort, condensation control, ultraviolet control, acoustic control, daylighting and energy requirements. Finally, the color chosen for barn windows can also affect their maintenance and longevity. White is the color that is the least likely to fade. A painted window will fade over time after being exposed to the sun.

4.1.3. Shading curtains

Nowadays, curtains are a huge part of a barn’s functionality and the success of the animals residing there. The market presents a wide variety of products of this type, depending on the opening sizes, different prices based on the level of technological advancement. Practically, there are options that fit any livestock operation needs and budget. The farmer usually has to make the best decisions for the business to be profitable in the future.

In specific, the curtains are made of UV-stabilized high-density polyester material, then they are resistant to stress, atmospheric weather and wear. Due to special fixings, these devices are easy to

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program and can be placed on structures in the presence or absence of a perimeter wall. A frequent solution is the *roll-on* system, with automatic control. The system usually has two configurations: closed or opened. The curtains may be characterized by different colors but similar texture and properties.

For example, Arienti s.p.a produces fixed or motorized curtains for barn, entirely made of stabilized polyethylene monofilament, with a tightly woven and warp-knit weave, very resistant to wear or breakage. The fixed net is packaged with a galvanized support structure, a border reinforced by a tape of 50 mm and "V180" eyelets spaced apart. The motorized net can be packaged in any size and, normally, the shaft on which it is wound is anchored in the center by the net so that, in the closed position, the tube can act as a reinforcement between one pillar and another. A three-phase motor from 0.55 Kw to 0.75 Kw is mounted (according to the size of the system), a control unit as well as the possibility of adding 2 more functionalities: the remote control and the anemometer (indicates the direction and intensity of the wind).

4.2. Existing non-farming applications

There are different motorized systems for shading curtains, that allow to control all your curtains easily through smartphone or a single remote control. Effortlessly protect the curtains from tearing and keep them perfectly aligned. Shading devices can perform one role or all three. Shading systems in building is divided into two as internal and external systems. Accordingly, sun shading curtain systems are applied in order to allow the passage of these harmful lights in the buildings or especially in front of the windows as desired

Another application context of shading curtains is the in factories. All of those building weaves are effective for controlling glare. They must be chosen based on the global geographic location and the layout of the buildings. Solar protection fabric enables the window's level of luminance to be controlled (natural light diffused in the room) and a reduction in disturbing light & dark contrasts within the field of vision. Depending on its color, a solar protection fabric can become a light source if sunlight strikes it directly.

4.3. Potential farming applications

Weather is always changing, and a farmer can't be at the beck and call of the barn curtains, adjusting through the day. Most suppliers offer automatic solutions of this systems in the form of thermostatic controls. It makes sense to take full advantage of any advancements in livestock barn design. The environmental sensors are available and can be useful tools for controlling light, ventilation and overall climate control.

Advantages of automation solutions

- Proper housing is to protect animals from sunburns, rain, hot and cold winds of inclement weather conditions.
- To provide clean and comfortable shelter for dairy animals.
- Providing better accommodation at a cheaper cost.
- To protect animals from wild animals.
- Maintain optimum weight by setting feed levels based on a reliable, quality supply of feed. Any changes in animal eating habits are quickly spotted and rectified. Also, help to save costs on feed wastage.

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- Increased production of milk.
- Production of higher quality milk.
- Better health of animals.
- Decrease in the mortality rate of calves.

4.4. Best practices/typical combinations with other technologies

Comprehensive models provide combined measures of temperature and humidity in parameters such as standard environmental temperatures. Ventilation rates for typically livestock housing have been based on temperature control when warm outside (maximum ventilation rates) with a fixed proportion between 0-1 and 0-2 for minimum ventilation rates. A better technique for establishing minimum ventilation rates should depend on other factors such as upper and lower critical temperatures, frequency of occurrence of ambient temperatures and control of environmental contaminants.

Light to dairy cows is frequently discussed and it is known to affect both production and behavior. The most commonly used method for quantifying light is lux meter but there are other options. Several research studies have tested the effects of different light treatments on dairy cow production and welfare. However, the illuminance is often mentioned but not how the lux was measured.

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Appendix 22: Electric tractor

1. Technical description

The efforts of automotive industry are currently focused on reducing emissions and dependency on fossil fuels, while maintaining driveability. Multiple researchers and manufacturers have thus been working on reducing the energy consumption of agricultural machinery, which is almost universally powered by diesel-fueled internal combustion engines, without compromising their functionality and performance [318]. There are various research paths regarding renewable drive options, with electric motors seen as a natural step in the evolution of heavy vehicles [319].

Electric vehicles are vehicles that use a single or multiple electric motors for mobility and are classified into Battery Electric Vehicles (BEV) and Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEV) [320] (Fig. A22. 1 [321]).

Fig. A22. 1. Electric Vehicles Classification.

BEVs' drivetrain consists of 3 major subsystems: (a) the electric motor propulsion, (b) the energy source and (c) the auxiliary.

The electric propulsion subsystem which consists of the vehicle controller, the power electronic converter, the electric motor, the mechanical transmission and the wheels.

The energy source which along with its management unit and the charger (energy refuelling unit) makes the energy source subsystem.

The auxiliary subsystem which consists of the power steering unit, the climate control unit and the auxiliary supply unit [322].

Based on the control inputs from the accelerator and the brake pedals, the vehicle controller provides proper control signals to the electronic power converter, which functions to regulate the power flow between the electric motor and energy source. During braking if the BEV has regenerative capabilities, there is backward power flow to restore the energy into the energy storage system [323].

HEVs use 2 power sources, an internal combustion engine and an electric motor. One of them acts as a primary power source and the other one as a secondary. HEVs bear the main advantage of overcoming the barrier of limited stored energy in BEVs [321].

1.1. Classification

Replacing the conventional internal combustion engine with an electric drivetrain without affecting the vehicle's structure is currently the most applied concept for tractors, wheel loaders and forklifts.

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According to [324], the electrification process for tractors can be roughly assorted into 3 basic expansion stages as presented below (mild hybrid, full hybrid, fully electric) (Fig. A22. 2 [325]).

Fig. A22. 2. Electrification options.

Mild hybrid system

From 2019 onwards, a further reduction in diesel engine emissions will follow as new limits, the so-called Stage 5 (“Stage V”) requirements, will become effective. This new Regulation will introduce Particulate Number limits and emission limits for the smallest and biggest engines used in agricultural machines (<19 kW & > 560 kW). With this step, EU environmental requirements for agricultural machines will become the strictest in the world. This requires major changes to tractors and other agricultural machinery as new engines need to be installed in all these vehicles [326,327].

A first approach that does not require any changes in the vehicle’s structure is to downsize the internal combustion tractor’s engine that is powered with diesel. Along with that, there will probably be a requirement for an added oxidation catalytic converter and a diesel particulate filter, but no additional SCR³⁶ is required.

The rest of the power required (e.g., another 20 kW) can be covered by an electric motor which is going to be in parallel operation with the diesel engine. The space saved by the downsizing of the diesel engine will be enough to mount the electric motor, the battery (approximate capacity category of 6 kWh) and the necessary power electronics.

A strong advantage of mild-hybrid systems is the overall brake protection they provide as the tractor can either slow down when the opposite current (power) flow in the electric motor is activated or maintain a constant speed in case of downhill (regenerative braking). Energy is gained and stored in the battery during braking or in case the diesel engine serves lower loads, and when it comes for demanding field tasks the electric motor can be reinforced by a battery boost, in combination with the diesel engine, in order to efficiently carry out the intensive work.

Given that for Tier 2 interim vehicles with a diesel output of less than 76 hp (56 kW), there is no distinction between hydrocarbons and nitrogen oxides emissions, a rational strategy would be to integrate tractor systems of this size avoiding European emission Stage 4 (and the upcoming Stage 5) especially when it is about special crops or municipal tractors that this size covers completely the power requirements.

³⁶ Selective Catalytic Reduction (SCR) is an advanced active emissions control technology system that injects a liquid-reductant agent through a special catalyst into the exhaust stream of a diesel engine. The reductant source is usually automotive-grade urea, otherwise known as Diesel Exhaust Fluid (DEF). The DEF sets off a chemical reaction that converts nitrogen oxides into nitrogen, water and tiny amounts of carbon dioxide (CO₂), natural components of the air we breathe, which is then expelled through the vehicle tailpipe. Source: <https://www.dieselforum.org/about-clean-diesel/what-is-scr>.

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Full hybrid system

If there is space for more components to be integrated into the mild hybrid system, then full hybrid version can be achieved, based on the mounting of an additional battery that – except power peaks – will allow the tractor to operate in short-term fully electric mode too (also called “gliding”, currently widely used in urban transport and fully electric loaders).

With an addition of a second electric motor (that is rated with the same power output as the diesel engine) the whole procedure could be supplemented. Especially for applications like animal feeding or storage work, it will be possible to completely deactivate the diesel engine and operate in electric mode and avoid all emissions. However, space limitations would only allow the approach of a fully electric front-axle drivetrain.

Having a second electric drive unit provides 2 significant advantages. Firstly, shift assistance is possible achieving smoother gear shifts as the drive torque can be maintained via the parallel electric drivetrain (also achieving less wearing of shifting components). Secondly, the agility of the tractor is greatly increased due to the boost provided by the front-axle electric powertrain in tasks like pulling the vehicle around the corner (pull-in-turn effect).

Full electric system

This holistic approach comes with no structural adjustments for the tractors but requires replacing all the components related to the diesel engine by a central electric motor, a large battery unit and the necessary power electronics. All the available space under the hood is used for the necessary electric power units (this concept is followed by Fendt and Escorts companies). Further battery packs can be added if the transmission is removed but it must be taken into account that in tractors the transmission not only transmits the traction power. It is designed as a structural component and serves as a support component for all other subsystems like the rear axle, the cabin or the front axle. If it is removed nevertheless, a 2-speed gearbox (between the electric motor and the rear axle) could be a possible installation when the tractor’s structure is ideal.

However, the above modifications will lead the centre of gravity of the vehicle to be shifted towards the front axle due to the heavy battery pack. All this weight redistribution can heavily affect both the handling and ballasting of the vehicle in a negative way. To solve this issue, the centre of gravity displacement can be compensated by placing most of the batteries between the axles and at the same time all the light weight components can be installed in the front.

Regardless the configuration, the strongest disadvantage is that the wheel loads and the components are not ideally matched with each other. Moreover, costs arise due to a corresponding system structure, which can hardly be justified by the given functions. So, the construction of such systems based on current vehicle structures already shows the first possibilities of this technology but it is far from exhaustive [324].

In summary, it can be foreseen that despite the increasing number of limitations, diesel engines will remain in the tractor industry for the near future. By manageable adjustments in the course of a mild or a full hybrid solution, the power of the internal combustion engine can be reduced both for the benefit of the environment and for the use of new functional potentials. Thus, not only the system costs will stay in reasonable levels, but also the vehicle structure will be known for the user, which is also considered an important factor in the market implementation of electric solutions.

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At this time, the number of commercial hybrid tractors is very limited. A known product is *Landini REX4 Electra – Evolving Hybrid*, which also received the EIMA Technical Innovation Award 2020-21³⁷. This tractor features an innovative electric front wheel drive with independent wheels, brake energy recovery, a cabin with electronically controlled semi-active suspension and a semi-automatic transmission letting the user select the speed using a joystick. REX4 Electra is equipped with a 110 hp Diesel engine, Reverse Power Shuttle transmission and 3 Powershift speeds (H-M-L). It includes a fully electric front wheel drive with suspended axle, sporting two independent electric motors and associated sensors, electronic controls, a generator and a battery dedicated to energy recovery under braking and deceleration. The entire system is controlled by the PMS (Power Management System) which supervises the operation of all devices. The Diesel engine powers the front electric motors through the generator and the battery, and continuously communicates with the conventional mechanical rear final drives. The result is basically a parallel hybrid with a system that is independent of the mechanical ratio between the rear and front wheels of the tractor [328] (Fig. A22. 3 [329]).

Fig. A22. 3. Landini REX4 Electra – Evolving Hybrid.

2. Performance

2.1. Environmental impact

Electrification enables the use of renewable energy – ideally produced on farm – instead of direct fossil fuel consumption.

Vehicle electrification is seen as one of the main methods for reducing vehicular emissions and reliance on fossil fuels, both on and off road [330].

2.2. Factors affecting performance

The battery electric drives are less compatible with the normal working hours of tractor drivers. That's because the energy storage capacity of batteries is generally too low to support several hours of heavy field work, which would require recharging repeatedly during the working day or choosing a large battery. Using a battery electric drive tractor would lead to a trade-off between a longer working day

³⁷ EIMA International: <https://www.eima.it/en/>

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for the driver (because of the recharge time which can last about 3 to 4 hours), or reduced time in the field in total.

2.3. Efficiency

A diesel engine achieves about 35-40% efficiency in converting thermal to mechanical energy, while the overall efficiency of charging/discharging batteries is at 80% and electric motors can reach an efficiency of up to 80-90%.

Most farming activities require machinery with very high torque. Unlike internal combustion engines, electric motors provide constant torque in the low-speed region from the start and also provide constant power in the high speed region. Indicatively, a tractor with an internal combustion engine has a torque reserve of around 40 %, while an electric tractor of around 300% [331].

2.4. Stability/continuity

Two ways for these limitations to be overcome appear to be: a) autonomous drive systems and b) rapid recharging systems. Autonomous drive could allow the field operation for a larger proportion of the day compared to a manned tractor while on the other hand, rapid recharging could minimize the recharging time either by optimized, high-power contact chargers or battery exchange (battery-swap) systems. The latter is commonly used in industries such as forklifts for warehouses or city-buses, where high vehicle up-time is essential just as in most agricultural applications [319]. However, regarding the electric vehicles (EVs) in general, battery swapping is quite a controversial issue, having its supporters and opponents, so the corresponding appliance in tractors requires a separate approach, weighting the advantages and the disadvantages [332,333].

2.5. Practical lifetime

Regarding practical lifetime, there is not yet enough data on the electric tractors. It can be safely assumed, however, that it is expected to be a combination of that of a conventional tractor, namely its frame and the various subsystems apart from the main power source; and that of an electric vehicle, namely the electric motor/motors and the battery/batteries. It should be noted that the average expected lifespan of an electric motor is 29 years, which is two times the average lifespan of a conventional tractor.

3. Cost

Several farm machinery manufacturers such as John Deere, Fendt, Soletrac, Rigitrac, Claas, Escorts, Kubota, Schaffer and more have conducted research on the electrification of farm machinery and have already showcased their electric tractor prototypes at various exhibitions³⁸ [321]. Even if in the near future more and more companies are expected to release market-ready electric tractors, only a small number of them are currently available. An idea about their buying cost can be given by the following list; however, no estimation can be made regarding the conversion costs of a conventional tractor to electric or hybrid.

FT25G by Farmtrac

The all-electric FT25G tractor from Farmtrac unifies all the functions and features of a compact tractor, with the benefits of electric power. It is designed for a number of applications including greenhouse

³⁸ Agritechnica: <https://www.agritechnica.com/en/>

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work, municipalities, equestrian centres, livestock farm jobs and more. It gets its power from a 72 V lithium-ion battery supplying a 15 kW (20 HP) electric motor. Some of its features are oil-immersed brakes, power steering and position control hydraulic linkage. It can be charged by a domestic socket to 100% in 5 hours and is able to run for up to 6 hours (Fig. A22. 4³⁹) [334,335].

Base price: €23,132 EUR

Fig. A22. 4. Farmtrac FT25G.

Compact Electric Tractor (CET) by SOLECTRAC (by Ideanomics)

The 30 HP (22 kW) diesel-equivalent (22 HP/16 kW at the PTO) CET is a versatile, 4WD utility vehicle for vineyards, greenhouses, golf courses and municipalities. It can run up to 3 to 6 hours powered by a 22-kWh battery pack, depending on the load. The battery can be charged in under 4 hours from a 220 VAC, 30A outlet or overnight from a 110 VAC, 15 A outlet. The battery life spans to 10 years (pending operating cycles and depth of discharge (DOD) – 3,500 cycles at 80% DOD). Finally, CET accepts all Category 1 – 540 RPM PTO implements, including hydraulics on its rear hitch (Fig. A22. 5⁴⁰Fig) [336,337].

Base price: \$26,800 USD

Fig. A22. 5. Soletrac CET.

³⁹<https://www.machinerydealer.co.uk/>

⁴⁰<https://soletrac.com/>

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eUtility Electric Tractor by SOLECTRAC (by Ideanomics)

The 40 HP diesel-equivalent eUtility is a tractor for any small farm or livestock operation, equestrian centres and other utility type work. It can run up to 4 to 8 hours powered by a 24-kWh battery pack, depending on the load. Its runtime can be extended with optional exchangeable battery packs. It supports Level 2 fast charging for 80% charge in 4 hours or full charge overnight. Its battery management system (BMS) automatically protects the batteries during charging and discharging. The battery life spans to 10 years (pending operating cycles and depth of discharge (DOD) – 3,000 cycles at 80% DOD). eUtility just like CET accepts all Category 1 – 540 RPM PTO implements on the rear hitch. Finally, its linear actuators provide a lifting power of 454 kg for dynamic loads and 1361 kg for static loads (Fig. A22.6⁴¹) [338,339].

Base price: \$46,000 USD

Fig. A22. 6. Soletrac eUtility.

eFarmer Electric Tractor by SOLECTRAC (by Ideanomics)

The 30 HP diesel-equivalent eFarmer electric tractor will be available in the Q4 of 2021 (international availability in 2022). It will be able to run up to 4 to 8 hours powered by a 28kWh battery pack, depending on the load. Its runtime will be able to be extended with optional exchangeable battery packs. It will support 3-hour quick charge for one pack or an overnight slow charge for 2 packs. Its battery management system (BMS) will automatically protect the batteries during charging and discharging. Its speed and steering will be controlled by a simple joystick, allowing easy navigation between row crops. Rates of speed will also be variable and controlled by the joystick position. Finally, eFarmer will include a front hitch for low lift loader or reaper, a mid-hitch for precision cultivation tools and a rear hitch for all Category 1 - 540 RPM –PTO implements (Fig. A22. 7⁴²) [340].

Base price: \$49,500 USD

⁴¹<https://soletrac.com/>

⁴²https://soletrac.com

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Fig. A22. 7. Soletrac eFarmer.

Monarch tractor by Monarch

The tractor by Monarch offers 52 kW peak power (30 kW PTO power). Its operational run time is 4 to 10 hours depending on the usage. The charging time utilizing the Monarch 240 V 80 A charger is 4 to 5 hours at 200 VAC. The manufacturer provides 10 years battery warranty. Monarch tractor accepts all Category 1 – 540 RPM PTO implements [341,342] (Fig. A22. 8⁴³).

Base price: \$58,000 USD

Fig. A22. 8. Monarch tractor.

Concluding, it is clear that full electric drive offers farmers many benefits and this will lead to the technology appearing in some smaller tractors. For larger arable tractors, it is likely to be in the form of a hybrid system, thereby giving combustion engines a reprieve. However, a relatively new research project could pave the way towards a full electric drive for arable tractors as well. The GridCON project is an initiative by the economic affairs, energy ministry and managed by the Aerospace Centre eV in Cologne, Germany. It is a joint project of John Deere, University of Kaiserslautern and B.A.U.M. Based on a John Deere 6210R tractor, the machine utilizes a cable connection from the field border to the machine, which transfers power continuously at over 300 kW. A 100 kW electric motor powers the

⁴³<https://www.monarchtractor.com/>

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continuously variable transmission, and there is an additional outlet for implements powered by a 200kW electric motor. Compared to battery-powered equivalents, the prototype delivers around 50% lower machine and operating costs. A drum fixed to the tractor carries up to 1,000m of cable, which can be extended if required. In the field, the cable is fed out and reeled in while guided by a robot arm to keep the operation friction free and at low load. An intelligent guidance system is also used to prevent the tractor running into or over the cable. Capable of autonomous operating speed of 12mph (20 km/h), the vehicle can also be guided manually using a remote control. The total empty weight of the working prototype GridCON tractor including cable drum and robot arm is about 8.5 tonnes, about the same weight as a conventional 6195R tractor but with twice as much power (Fig. A22. 9⁴⁴) [343,344].

Fig. A22. 9. John Deere GridCON.

4. Applications

Electric tractors for farming purposes can potentially be paired with any RES technology for electrical energy production, in order to support their charging process.

⁴⁴<https://electricvehicles.in/>

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